

D5.3 Networks of Engagement in Deliberative Policy-making: Expert Reflections on Barriers to Participation

Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research and Innovation Transition

D5.3 - Networks of Engagement in Deliberative Policy-making:
Expert Reflections on Barriers to Participation
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Abbreviations

APC — Article processing charges
CAP — Common Agricultural Policy
CS — Citizen Science
CSO — Civil society organization
CV — Curriculum vitae
D5.1 — ON-MERRIT Deliverable 5.1
EC — European Commission
EU — European Union
FAIR — Findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability
GMO — Genetically modified organism
LMIC — Low- and middle-income countries
NGO — Non-governmental organization
OA — Open Access
OECD — Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OS — Open Science
RI — Research Innovation
RRI — Responsible Research and Innovation
SDG — UN Sustainable Development Goals
SSH — Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM — Science, technology, engineering and math
STS — Science, technology and society
UN — United Nations
WHO — World Health Organization
WP — Work Package

Executive summary

The ON-MERRIT project aims to critically interrogate whether Open Science (OS) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) live up to the positive claims of their proponents in a multitude of ways and whether the Matthew effect in academia, or other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage, may be present within or even exacerbated by OS and RRI practices. We set this project against the backdrop of the grand societal challenges that are reflected in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which imply required collaboration between research scientists, policy-makers, civil society actors and broader publics. Reflecting this context, we focus our work within this project on three relevant domains: agriculture, climate, and health.

Of particular interest to ON-MERRIT Task 5.3, on which this deliverable reports, is whether OS does in fact support scientific uptake by policy-makers, and, to the second point, whether the Matthew effect or other forms of cumulative advantage or disadvantage may be at play and impacting participation in policy-making. We approach this research with recognition of the fact that, as yet, there is little empirical evidence as to the impact of OS practices on research uptake by policy-makers—a finding established by the earlier ON-MERRIT Deliverable 5.1 (Reichmann, Wieser, and Ross-Hellauer 2020). We also recognize that RRI is intended to equitably reconfigure the science-society relationship by bringing together public policy, societal relevance and effective implementation in novel ways, drawing on elaborated methods and conceptual frameworks from the long history of negotiating the science-society-relationship. To that end, researchers who conduct projects aligned with RRI principles and practices work with a broad range of societal actors to engage them in participatory practices that seek to provide a knowledge basis for policy-making. As such, these researchers are often important gatekeepers as well as enablers for engagement in participatory research. In response to these conditions, we ask two primary research questions (and two sub-questions):

RQ1: What factors influence scientific uptake by policy-makers?

RQ2: Which societal actors, both within and outside of academia, participate in OS and RRI research and policy-making?

- Which societal actors are excluded, and why?
- Who influences public participation in policy-making?

To respond to these questions, we conducted a qualitative study composed of in-depth interviews and workshops with policy-active researchers who either practice RRI or whose research resonates with RRI practices. Our 18 participants, gathered from diverse institutions across the EU and beyond, participated in one of three workshops focused on ON-MERRIT's three domains of interest: climate, agriculture and health. Our workshops, guided by a facilitator from our team, guided participants through three discussions, focused on 1. How to further enable the uptake of scientific research in the process of policy-making; 2. How to improve equality in representation, access and impact in policy-making in terms of individuals who have access to this sphere and in terms of whose interests are (or are not) represented; and 3. Whether OS can change the uptake of science in policy-making. Our team collaboratively coded and analyzed transcriptions of workshops and interviews and worked collaboratively with participants to co-create preliminary findings during a later workshop.

In response to RQ1, we found that key factors that influence scientific uptake by policy-makers include the following:

- Understanding on the part of researchers of the policy sphere in which they operate, because this determines the set of strategies that one should use in order to achieve uptake.
- *Congruence* between research aims and policy goals.
- The strategic development and maintenance of relationships based on trust and credibility, on the part of researchers with policy-makers.
- Policy positions taken at certain international organizations, like the UN, WHO, or OECD, which serve to define the normative foundation for policy-making at national and sub-national levels.
- Political culture, or receptivity to input.
- Upstream engagement between researchers and policy-makers, and with civil society actors and impacted communities.
- Fostering relationships between communities and their policy-makers.
- Cognitive accessibility of research findings and outputs (rather than physical accessibility of primary research outputs).

In response to RQ2, we found that:

- Who participates in RRI-resonant research and policy-making is largely determined by the policy sphere in which a researcher interacts (representative, deliberative or participatory), and the research design and methods they use to create the scientific knowledge relevant to the intended sphere. We identified three different approaches to research among our participants that largely overlap with the three policy models described above and found the following.
- With a **traditional academic approach**, it is primarily researchers and policy-makers who participate.
- With a **multi-stakeholder approach**, the range of actors is opened to include various stakeholders selected for their relevance to the problem at hand. These typically include researchers, other experts, representatives from the business world, policy-makers and other civil servants, representatives of CSOs and NGOs, and sometimes, representatives of local.
- With a **strongly participatory approach**, the range of actors is further broadened to include people who have historically been marginalized from processes of both scientific knowledge production and policy-making, ranging from average citizens to some of the world's most poor and vulnerable people.

In response to the sub-questions to RQ2, we found that the following actors remain excluded from RRI-resonant research and policy-making:

- Researchers who are perceived as not credible or legitimate, due to inequalities related to race, gender, age, geography (in the geopolitical sense), as well as institutional affiliation.
- Researchers without adequate funding or institutional support for policy-oriented work.
- The world's most poor and vulnerable remain largely left out, despite the best efforts of our participants who practice strongly participatory research, because these groups are difficult to reach due to the digital divide, language marginalization, and limited resources for this type of research.

Finally, we found that the following actors influence public participation in policy-making:

- Researchers, through their choice of research design and methods.
- Policy-makers, through their willingness (or lack thereof) to engage with the various approaches to research that the siting of the science-policy interface implies.
- Research funders, by offering only limited support for RRI-resonant research that engages diverse members of the public in policy-oriented research processes.
- Academic and scientific institutions, by maintaining norms and values that run counter to this aim and discouraging and disincentivizing researchers from facilitating it, which has a particular impact on women and people of colour within these institutions.

Based on these findings, we conclude that while there are several key factors that influence scientific uptake by policy-makers, OS is not chief among them. Additionally, OS and RRI, as they are currently practiced within the contexts of academic and scientific institutions, are not doing enough and are not yet widely enough adopted to have a significant impact on expanding equitable participation in scientific knowledge production and policy-making. Further, we conclude that the Matthew effect and other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage are present within both processes, and are interacting with historical systems of inequality, including racism, sexism, ageism, classism and the lingering effects of colonialism.

Based on these findings, we offer the following selected recommendations to researchers, funders, and academic and scientific institutional leaders. (See [Chapter 8](#) for a longer list of recommendations and [Annex 1](#) for a more detailed policy brief intended for funding institutions.)

To increase the uptake of scientific evidence by policy-makers, in pursuit of socially beneficial outcomes,

1. **Researchers** should practice upstream engagement in the context of multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory research designs, develop trust-based relationships with policy-makers, and aim for congruence between research objectives and policy goals.
2. **Funders** should specifically fund (more) research that uses upstream engagement and multi-stakeholder and participatory research designs and fund the interactional work that takes place at the science-policy interface.
3. **Institutional leaders** should provide training and support for interacting at the science-policy interface, and support and reward research that involves upstream engagement and multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory research designs.

To make scientific knowledge production, the science-policy interface, and participation in policy-making more equitable (particularly as regards the inclusion of historically marginalized actors),

1. **Researchers** should take a multi-stakeholder or strongly participatory approach to research rather than the traditional academic approach, cultivate diverse research teams and networks, foster relationships between impacted communities and their relevant policy-makers, practice open and accessible dissemination and data sharing practices, and share skills and knowledge with diverse colleagues.
2. **Funders** should specifically fund research that takes a multi-stakeholder or participatory approach rather than the traditional academic approach, researchers who are marginalized within academic and scientific contexts, research that seeks to include marginalized groups, and collaborative

research proposed by diverse research teams that include non-scientific actors. They should also add flexibility to both funding calls and stipulations of use to allow for the unknowns that are part of participatory processes and for the allocation of funds necessary to support the participation of marginalized people.

3. **Institutional leaders** should support and reward research that takes a multi-stakeholder and/or participatory approach rather than the traditional academic approach, seek to balance inequalities within academic and scientific institutions by hiring and supporting the career development of researchers who are marginalized within these contexts, support and reward research practices that take an open and accessible approach to dissemination and data sharing, and support and reward research that seeks to include marginalized people.

1. Introduction

1.1. The role of RRI and OS in fostering equitable participation and scientific uptake by policy-makers

Proponents of OS claim that one of its virtues is that it helps to facilitate the uptake of scientific research by policy-makers, and that it will do so in ways that democratize both science and policy-making, by offering greater transparency, accessibility, and accountability in ways that bring more societal actors into these realms. Simultaneously, the European Commission (EC) has fostered its own version of inclusive, participatory forms of research and policy-making under the banner of RRI (Owen and Pansera 2019). Researchers who conduct projects aligned with RRI principles and practices work with a broad range of social actors to engage them in participatory practices that seek to provide a knowledge basis for deliberative policy-making. As such, these researchers are often important gatekeepers as well as enablers for engagement in participatory research. Especially when authoring project reports, RRI practitioners even become spokespersons, giving voice to the accounts of both powerful stakeholders and more peripheral civil society actors. But every inclusion is also a choice. In response to these conditions, we ask two primary research questions: **1. What factors influence scientific uptake by policy-makers? 2. Which societal actors, both within and outside of academia, participate in RRI research and policy-making?** Secondly, we ask: **Who influences public participation in policy-making? Which societal actors are excluded, and why?**

Therefore, Task 5.3, upon which this document reports, aimed to engage researchers who take part in participatory evidence-gathering for projects aligned with RRI via a series of three expert workshops, each themed for one of the ON-MERRIT case-study disciplines (climate, agriculture and health). Experts invited to these workshops were asked to share experiences of participatory processes and to reflect on possible barriers to participation, to reflect on their own experiences with facilitating policy-making through their research, and to question how the voices of various stakeholders and civil society actors (including their own) were or were not heard, for which reasons. Additionally, we invited them to reflect specifically on the role of OS and RRI in fostering equitable participation in and access to research and policy-making. Bringing together preliminary one-on-one interviews and group discussions, the experiences and reflections of our participants inform knowledge about the Matthew effect and other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage in the participation of public actors in evidence-gathering activities and the uptake of research by policy-makers. This report therefore draws on a wealth of experience with policy-relevant research and working at the science-policy interface to respond to our research questions.

This work seeks to contribute to a larger body of literature suggesting that governance increasingly relies on expert knowledge (Hilgartner 2000; Weingart 2001), with science providing a mythology of universality and manageability (Drori 2008) while at the same time being increasingly politicized. Having produced an extensive literature review (Reichmann et al. 2020) in preparation for this research puts us in a position to connect our empirical work to the existing literature and to formulate answers to open research questions. Before presenting the findings of our empirical work, we briefly summarize the main results of this review.

1.2. The state of the art regarding OS uptake by policy-makers

The use of publicly available scientific outputs by policy-makers is claimed to be one of the benefits of OS. However, we found that there is yet little empirical evidence as to the impact of OS practices on research uptake by policy-makers. In the health policy literature, the relationship between evidence and policy is

frequently described as a “gap”, highlighting the difficulties that prohibit the use of scientific evidence in policy-making. How can OS impact on policies, then, if policy-makers do not make sufficient use of scientific outputs as it is? Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1) of the ON-MERRIT project (Reichmann, Wieser, and Ross-Hellauer 2020) addressed this question systematically, by summarizing the evidence to date on how policy-makers use scholarly resources with a special focus on OS practices to lay the groundwork for the empirical research presented in this report. D5.1 sought to answer a number of questions:

- 1) What are the mechanisms of knowledge transfer identified in the literature?
- 2) Which factors influence policy outcomes?
- 3) Why do policy-makers use academic literature/research evidence?
- 4) Which contextual factors impact the use of evidence by policy-makers?
- 5) How does access to scientific results impact on the use of evidence by policy-makers?

We found that researchers and policy-makers are described as living in different and frequently incompatible worlds. According to the reviewed literature, policy-makers seek information that is timely, relevant, credible, and readily available, while at the same time struggling with knowledge management and appraisal of research outputs, in addition to a lack of resources, knowledge, and skills to utilize research. Research awareness among policy-makers is described as low, and few academics participate directly in the policy process. Conversely, factors conducive to research uptake are access to relevant and clear information and good relationships between researchers and policy-makers, as policy-makers prefer receiving information through personal networks rather than academic publications. The reviewed literature suggests that the availability of information in the form of academic publications and other research outputs is of secondary concern for research uptake at the science-policy interface. Research on the use of evidence in policy-making is frequently criticised for falling short on current theories of policy processes, which suggests that these processes need to be better understood before assessing the impact of OS.

The report further suggests understanding both RRI and OS as continuing earlier attempts to negotiate the role of science in society. Indeed, the relationship of science to its public(s) has a long history. The public character of science has been fundamental for the development of the peer review system and the contemporary OS movement. Building upon earlier experiences, RRI attempts a reconfiguration of the science-society relationship by bringing together public policy, societal relevance and effective implementation in novel ways, drawing on elaborated methods and conceptual frameworks from the long history of negotiating the science-society relationship. The way in which science and research have contributed to policy-making has undergone a considerable evolution in the second half of the 20th century. As the science-policy interface itself evolved, so did the conceptual models used to describe it developed by social and political scientists (Gluckman et al. 2021).

1.3. Changing forms of knowledge integration

From the beginning, modern science was (also) understood in utilitarian terms. The utility of science was evident in the fields of maritime navigation, warfare, commerce, and industry. With the development of statistical calculus, the social sciences, too, met immediate interest amongst political rulers (Höflechner 2008, 108; Foucault 2010; Porter 2020). Nineteenth century universities responded with autonomy claims to protect self-governance and freedom of research and teaching (Stichweh 1994). By the early 20th century, the economic value of scientific knowledge became increasingly obvious and closer ties were developed between these two domains (cf. Godin 2016). Governments increasingly sought researchers’ advice in pursuit

of economic prosperity. During World War II, science became eminently important in the context of defence and intelligence.

In the USA, Weingart (1983; 1999) observed an increasing formalization of communication between science and policy (which he referred to as “scientification of politics” and “politicisation of science”, respectively) that started with President Eisenhower’s appointment of a science and technology advisor and a respective committee in 1957. Many of these earlier approaches are founded in the idea of policy-advice as a linear process, working rationally from problem-identification to solution—accompanied by the notion that the appeal to scientific data and established facts will lead to a better problem characterization and, by extension, better policy. Europe, too, saw increasing numbers of scholars engaging with policy in an era of increased investment in science (Sokolovska et al. 2019). It should be noted that the linear model of the science-policy (and society) relationship was neither an invention of post-war science policy, nor has it been discontinued as an explanatory factor. This approach still exists, at least in part (cf. Felt 2003, 19; Gluckman et al. 2021), but has been supplemented by more sophisticated models of science advice.

Maasen and Weingart (2006) point towards several historical developments that were conducive to the changing relationship between science and policy-making during the 1960s and 1970s. A general push for democratization in industrialized countries with an associated development of political movements operating outside the formalized political process (e.g., the anti-nuclear, environmental, civil rights, and feminist movements). Contemporary scholars who have analysed the developments of the science-policy interface since then have observed a variety of approaches that can be clustered in different ways. In their review study, for instance, Sokolovska et al. (2019) describe three historical phases that the science-policy interface has undergone during the second half of the 20th century. They label these ‘linear’, ‘interactional’, and ‘embedded’, respectively, with each of these phases corresponding to an associated policy model.

- 1) **Linear models** of science-policy advice correspond to the notion of policy-making as an elite system. In a linear understanding of the science-policy interface, scientific advice is understood as a one-way communication process. This model is defined by its emphasis on the reception of knowledge by policy-makers.
- 2) **Interactive models** of the science-policy interface correspond to policy-making as a deliberative process (Fischer 2005). It is characterized by the assumption that both scientists and policy-makers collaborate in a non-hierarchical way in search of the best problem solutions. In our reading, the defining feature of this family of models is their emphasis on emergent consensus between policy-makers and researchers.
- 3) **Embedded models** are characterized by an increased scrutiny of policy-makers by the broader society. They regard the science-policy interface as a discursive process between researchers and policy-makers (Sokolovska et al. 2019) and are similar to interactive models in this respect; they are further characterized by intense reflection on “formats of societal engagement and the language of communication on the science-policy interface” (Sokolovska et al. 2019).

These three types of models now exist side-by-side and continue to evolve. For instance, the dissemination of scientific evidence is still a common practice, which falls to the knowledge broker, as described in Roger Pielke’s book *The honest broker* (Pielke 2007; see also Gluckman et al. 2021). Interactive and participatory approaches move beyond dissemination and science communication (Fischer 2005) as they emphasize the integration of scientific knowledge into policy processes. Beyond the different approaches to policy advice summarized by Sokolovska et al. (2019), there are other prominent attempts to advance knowledge

integration in policy-making. Especially in European contexts, research that contributes to effective responses to urgent societal challenges was promoted in the last Framework Programme Horizon 2020. Increased attention to societal needs implies a divergence from earlier approaches (Owen, Macnaghten, and Stilgoe 2012), in the form of mission-oriented research with a normative starting point. Importantly, it requires a type of knowledge that goes beyond traditional (both positivist and hermeneutic) scientific epistemologies. This approach implies that civil society actors are integrated in processes of knowledge production in order to foster effective on-the-ground implementation. Furthermore, it requires that engagement begins already at the stage of problem formulation and is maintained throughout the entire process of knowledge making and implementation. This approach was developed systematically as RRI (see Schomberg 2013). Notably, several elements of RRI are well-established practices outside the European context, although not necessarily labelled as RRI, as the accounts of our participants demonstrate. For that reason, we suggest an alternative terminology to Sokolovska et al. (2019), who have not taken into account these recent developments. Accordingly, we propose to call the third model the '**participatory model**'.

1.4. Overview of the report

In the chapters that follow, we take an empirical approach to unpacking how researchers working at the science-policy interface understand their own work. We analyse how they frame knowledge integration in the policy domain, how they see their own role when engaging in policy relevant research and what strategies they deploy to make their contributions effective. As we will show, the different approaches taken by our participants correspond with those described in the literature. Yet, we do not assume a preconceived structure to cluster the various ways in which researchers engage in policy-relevant knowledge work. Instead, we propose an empirically grounded differentiation of knowledge integration in the policy domain (Chapter 3, lead author Bernhard Wieser). Against this backdrop, we inquire into how researchers develop and maintain relationships with policy-makers (Chapter 4, lead author Stefan Reichmann). In response to our research questions, it is of particular interest to us to reveal how choices regarding research design and methods shape the broadening or narrowing of access and representation within processes of knowledge production and policy-making (Chapter 5, lead author Nicki Lisa Cole). Finally, we address the role of OS and how our participants assess the contribution of related practices to knowledge integration in policy-making (Chapter 6, lead author Tony Ross-Hellauer). We then present an integrated overview of our results and discuss their significance and implications (Chapter 7) before offering some conclusions and preliminary recommendations (Chapter 8), which will be further developed during the recommendations phase of the ON-MERRIT project. A preliminary draft of our recommendations for science funding policy-makers is presented at the end of this document in [Annex 1](#).

2. Research Methods

2.1. Research design

The objective of Task 5.3 was to identify the factors that influence the uptake of science by policy-makers, which societal actors participate in RRI policy-making, and who influences the latter. We sought to fulfil this objective through qualitative research methods used to engage researchers working at the science-policy interface. Because we are specifically interested in understanding the role of participatory evidence-gathering in policy-making processes (either for RRI projects or research that embodies some principles of RRI), we focused on constructing a sample that includes researchers and other experts who are engaged in these types of knowledge-production activities. Our research design consists of three expert workshops (conducted online), each themed for one of ON-MERRIT's case-study domains: climate, agriculture and health. In preparation for our workshops, we conducted preliminary one-on-one online interviews with participants in order to get to know them, their work and experience in the policy realm. These interviews also served to help us develop the structure of our workshops and allowed us to offer guidance and support to our participants on how to prepare for the workshop. Following our final workshop and the conduct of some preliminary data analysis, we conducted a co-creation workshop where we presented our preliminary findings and offered participants the chance to validate, question or critique our findings, as well as to offer new insights on the themes discussed. While we planned the workshops and interviews as a team, just one of us, Nicki Lisa Cole, acted as the interviewer and facilitator of all workshops (henceforth referred to as “the interviewer” and “the facilitator”). We treated both interview and workshop recordings as data, compiled them into a dataset, and analyzed them as a complete dataset. Details on each data collection phase, our sample, and data analysis processes follow.

2.2. Sampling and participants

The target population for this task was researchers who regularly, as part of their work, engage with policy-makers to provide advice or expertise based on scientific research findings. We aimed to recruit 5–7 participants per workshop, for a total range of 15–21 participants. The geographic focus for our sampling strategy was primarily within the European Union (EU), however we also targeted researchers and experts from other regions, or whose work focuses on other regions, with the aim of generating data that could provide comparison and context. Our strategy was to construct a diverse sample in terms of gender (aim of a 50-50 gender split), race/ethnicity, academic age, institutional affiliation and professional role, as well as area of expertise/research focus within the three domains of climate, agriculture, and health. In addition, in keeping with the ON-MERRIT cross-cutting issues of sustainable development and gender inequality, we aimed to include participants whose research or expertise is directly related to one or both of these issues.

To construct our sample, we relied on a combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. For each workshop we compiled an initial list of potential participants based on our existing professional networks. We broadened these lists through desk research focused on key institutions where a strong science-policy link is known to exist, as well as through web searches of selected topics within the scientific literature to identify researchers with policy engagement as part of their research program. We used our diversity objectives to prioritize recruitment and recruited using a formal and standardized email invitation text with reminders sent 1–2 times ([see Annex 2](#)), depending on response or lack thereof. At this stage in the recruitment process we sometimes received recommendations of additional participants from targeted

persons who declined to participate. As targeted persons either agreed or declined to participate, we reprioritized our recruitment list with our diversity criteria in mind.

These efforts resulted in a total of 18 participants, with 7 in the climate workshop, 6 in the agriculture workshop, and 5 in the health workshop. As illustrated in Table 1, half the participants are employed at research institutes (independent of universities), and the rest are employed at civil society organizations that conduct research and policy engagement, and at universities as faculty members. Our sample includes slightly more men than women, and is majority persons of white European descent. Academic age, as defined as years since highest completed degree, is fairly evenly distributed between the values of 1 and 29, with just one participant with more than 30 years since their final degree, and one participant currently enrolled in a doctoral program (and counted in the first age range). Participants are primarily located in Europe (9 countries represented), but also in Africa, Asia, and North America.

Academic disciplines represented within our sample include geography, history, education, Asian studies, sociology/social sciences, STS, international development, economics, health economics and policy, environment/environmental science and natural resources management, environmental law and policy, biology, and medicine. Areas of research focus and expertise within the three workshops include:

Climate sciences

- Climate change adaptation, resilience and risk management
- STS Studies
- Energy systems transformations and policy
- International climate change policy

Agricultural sciences

- RRI, OS, science policy
- Policy analysis & stakeholder engagement
- Agricultural policy
- Sustainability research
- Environmental policy and development

Health sciences and medicine

- RRI, RI policy
- Leadership and gender inequity
- Occupational health & safety
- Air pollution
- Health policy

	CLIMATE	AGRICULT.	HEALTH	TOTALS	% OF TOTAL
Affiliation					
Research institute	2	5	2	9	50.0%
Civil society organization	1	0	3	4	22.2%
University	4	1	0	5	27.8%
Gender					
Women	3	3	2	8	44.4%
Men	4	3	3	10	55.6%
Race					
White	6	4	2	12	66.7%
All others	1	2	3	6	33.3%
Academic age					
1-9	1	2	3	6	33.3%
10-19	6	1	0	7	38.9%
20-29	0	2	2	4	22.2%
30-39	0	1	0	1	5.6%
Location					
Europe	6	4	3	13	72.2%
Africa	1	1	1	3	16.7%
Asia	0	1	0	1	5.6%
North America	0	0	1	1	5.6%

Table 1: Participant demographics by workshop domain

2.3. Data collection, preparation and analysis

2.3.1. Data collection methods

The first method of data collection we deployed were one-on-one preliminary online interviews with each workshop participant (excepting P7, who was unavailable to participate in a preliminary interview). Preliminary interviews were designed for the facilitator and the participant to become acquainted with one another in an effort to foster a comfortable social environment for our online workshops, and they also served as an opportunity for the research team to get further acquainted with each participant's research, expertise, and experience in the policy realm. After a participant agreed to join a workshop, a standardized follow-up email was sent to request a preliminary interview ([see Annex 3](#)). With the confirmation of a scheduled preliminary interview, participants were then asked to complete an online informed consent process (presented using the Limesurvey tool and securely hosted by Graz University of Technology) wherein it was made clear that their participation would be kept anonymous throughout the research and dissemination process ([see Annex 4](#)).

Interviews were planned for an hour in duration, though some were shorter or longer, depending on participant availability. Interviews were structured around the following topics ([see Annex 5](#) for the detailed interview guide):

- 1) Participant's research or expertise and its relationship to policy
- 2) Participant's experience participating in policy-making processes
- 3) The populations represented by participant's research and expertise in the process of policy-making
- 4) Participant's experience with or awareness of OS and RRI principles and practices and their (possible) relationships to policy-making
- 5) Discussion of workshop design, preparation process and participant's feedback on both

Interviews were conducted using Webex online conferencing software provided by Graz University of Technology and video and audio were recorded with participants' consent. Interviews were conducted as guided conversations through these topics and generally followed the structure outlined above, though in some cases structure varied due to participants' interests and/or initiative in the conversation. Regardless of structure, effort was always made to cover all topics on the list given that time allowed. When time was short, attention was paid primarily to the first, second, and fifth points. As part of the end of the interview, the interviewer advised participants how to prepare for the workshop.

Following the preliminary interview and in preparation of the workshop, participants were sent a standardized email to remind them of the upcoming event, requesting the preparation of some brief materials that should be submitted a week prior to the workshop, including a brief professional biography and an overview of a successful case of achieving research uptake within the policy sphere and a failed case that should include reflection on issues of access and representation within the research process ([see Annex 6](#)). In addition, participants were asked to read a brief overview of OS and RRI principles so that those unfamiliar with them could be prepared to discuss them in the workshop ([see Annex 7](#)) and a schedule for the workshop was provided ([see Annex 8](#)). Additionally, participants were asked at this stage to complete a brief demographic survey administered by Limesurvey that captured individual characteristics including gender, nationality, race and/or ethnicity, field of work, highest educational degree and academic age, the results of which were presented in the previous section ([see Annex 9](#) for the full survey).

The three workshops, organized around the overarching themes of climate, agriculture and health, are the heart of this task and of our data collection efforts. The primary objective of conducting them was to deepen understanding of participatory processes in the production of scientific and expert knowledge, and in turn, in processes of policy-making. The secondary objective was to illuminate who is (and is not) included in these processes, in terms of the researchers themselves, the participants that they work with, and the groups that their participants may (or may not) represent. The tertiary objective was to evaluate the extent to which RRI and/or OS values and practices are present and/or influential in the science-policy relationship.

To achieve these objectives, we gathered the identified experts in three different online workshops that occurred during the autumn of 2020 and the winter of 2021. Workshops were initially planned as in-person, 2-day events that would take place in Graz, Austria, hosted by the project team based at Graz University of Technology and Know-Center GmbH. However, due to the global COVID-19 pandemic, the format was shifted to online workshops and the time commitment greatly reduced in response to the general increase in demands for online meetings among our sample population. However, after the first workshop with climate science experts, we found that three hours left us feeling rushed, so we extended the agriculture and health workshops to four hours each. Like the interviews, the workshops were conducted using Webex and the recordings securely stored on an institutional server.

Though focused on different research domains, each workshop had the same organizational structure and set of key questions that drove the discussion ([see Annex 10](#)). Each workshop began with an introduction period wherein the project team was introduced and various members of the team gave short presentations about the ON-MERRIT project, Work Package 5, and the aims of Task 5.3, for which the workshops were conducted. This was followed by an introduction of workshop participants, an overview of the workshop agenda and a verbal agreement to the plan. Following that, the facilitator guided the participants through three separate discussion periods organized by the following questions:

- 1) How can we further enable the uptake of scientific research in the process of policy-making?
- 2) How can we improve equality in representation, access and impact in policy-making in terms of individuals (including academics, policy-makers, civil society actors, practitioners, and the public at large) who have access to this sphere, and in terms of whose interests are represented and whose are not?
- 3) Does or can OS, specifically, change the uptake of science in policy-making?

To facilitate the discussion of question 1, participants were asked to reflect upon and share their successful and failed cases, and in particular, to reflect on key moments of breakthrough or breakdown that led to either outcome. They were also asked to reflect on what these experiences illuminate in terms of enablers of or barriers to the uptake of scientific research and expertise by policy-makers. To facilitate the discussion of question 2, participants were asked to reflect upon which groups and whose interests are (or are not) represented in their research and expertise when interacting with policy-makers, how their research design and methods do (or do not) work to improve equality of access and representation within scientific knowledge production and policy-making, as well as the factors that serve as enablers of or barriers to efforts to improve equality. Finally, to facilitate discussion of question 3, participants were asked to reflect on how OS and/or RRI influence the ways in which they engage with stakeholders and participants, how they might impact the evidence that is presented to policy-makers and how they engage with policy-makers ([see Annex 10](#) for an exemplar workshop facilitation guide). Throughout the workshops, the facilitator fostered and moderated the discussion by asking follow-up questions, fostering transitions from one topic to another, and reflecting on the points of agreement or disagreement in the discussions. Other project team members sometimes participated when questions or topics arose that required contribution of their specific expertise.

Following the completion of the three workshops and preliminary analysis of interview and workshop data, we invited all participants to join a two-hour online co-creation workshop in May 2021 in order to seek their feedback on our preliminary results. We wanted to know whether our preliminary findings made sense to them or seemed off the mark, given their experience as participants in the workshops. Due to scheduling conflicts only five out of eighteen participants attended, but among them, represented all three of the previous workshops.

This workshop began with a brief presentation of preliminary findings and then went directly into one-on-one breakout sessions wherein two participants shared their initial reactions with each other for 15 minutes, out of view and earshot of the project team. An online collaboration tool (IdeaBoardz) was used to document their feedback and to facilitate sharing it amongst the larger group. To facilitate feedback, we posed four questions to participants and asked them to document their responses using the collaborative tool (see Figure 1) ([See Annex 11](#) for the full schedule and facilitation guide).

The screenshot shows the IdeaBoardz interface with the following sections and content:

- Initial Feedback**
 - What are your initial impressions?**
 - might need some more information for better understanding (+0)
 - comprehensive collection of relevant results (+0)
 - great overview and very good points (+0)
 - What was surprising?**
 - not so much - I heard lots of aspects/arguments I can share based on my own experiences (+0)
- What have we missed or can we improve upon?**
 - These findings apply mostly to a pre-covid world. During the pandemic, many processes (trust building, knowledge translation etc) have changed radically. It is a grppen question if post-covid, we'll go back to the pre-covid (+0)
 - what do the results mean for the future of open science policies? (+0)
 - How to educate and train young people who will become desicion makers in the future. (+0)
 - How to overcome the difficulties of religions. (+0)
 - Zoom fatigue! (+0)
- What are your questions?**
 - How to access data in the politically difficult countries such as Russia, China North Korea, and Tanzania (+1)
 - What measures is on-merrit taking in regard to result uptake/policy impact (in case intended :-)) (+0)
 - what is the relevance of OS as a super broad concept in regard to (+0)
 - Public trust in science and power dynamics shifting as a result of changing ways of interacting. (+0)
 - Institutional gatekeeping through administrative and institutional guidelines and policies that restrict data sharing (+0)

Figure 1: Collaborative feedback from co-creation participants

Following this 15-minute breakout session, participants re-joined the project team in the main meeting room to discuss their initial reactions together as a group. The facilitator and other project team members asked follow-up questions to foster further and deeper discussion of the issues raised in the sharing of initial feedback. During the full-group discussion, the facilitator compiled feedback offered by participants in another online collaborative tool (Miro) in order to capture and organize feedback in the service of ongoing data analysis (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Organizing feedback from co-creation participants

2.3.2. Data processing and preparation

In total, our data consist of 17 interviews, 3 topical workshops, and 1 co-creative workshop. This resulted in approximately 30 hours of audio/video data that were transcribed by a professional transcription service. All data, including audio, video, and text, were organized and securely stored on the server network provided by Graz University of Technology. The transcribed interviews and workshops compose the data that will be further discussed here and that are the focus of our research and findings.

Following transcription by the external service provider, all transcriptions were carefully checked by project team members for accuracy against the audio/video recordings and corrected where errors or omissions were made by the transcription service. After data were cleaned, they were imported into MAXQDA 2020, a leading qualitative data analysis software package, to facilitate processes of data organization and analysis. Following the flexible coding method developed by Deterding and Waters (2018), data were first organized through a process of index coding. Index coding is a process of structuring qualitative data that allows for it to be organized by large topical areas. We chose to index our data based on the four key discussion themes that are present in both interviews and workshops, that proceed chronologically across each piece of data (in terms of interview and workshop structure) and that serve to encapsulate all data within them. They are as follows (see [Annex 12](#) for more details):

- 1) Q1: Descriptions of participants' research and expertise
- 2) Q2: Discussions of science-policy interactions
- 3) Q3: Discussions of access and representation
- 4) Q4: Discussions of OS and RRI

The process of index coding was carried out by two team members with data divided between them, and each coded a different selection of interview and workshop transcripts, and when completed, checked the

other's work to validate the results of this procedure. During this process these team members compiled notes to support the development of a thematic code system that would be used in the next phase of data coding. These team members discussed, refined, organized and defined these potential codes before sharing them with the other members of the team. Following this, the full team met to review, discuss, debate and finalize a first-round thematic coding system for the data. This first-round system provided the basis for the first round of thematic coding which was conducted collaboratively by the full team ([see Annex 13](#)). This code system was considered a 'horizontal' system by the team, in that all codes were believed to be applicable across the entire dataset.

In order to accomplish coding collaboratively, a division of labour was organized based on the index coding and distributed according to areas of expertise of each team member. A master project file was created in MAXQDA with the first-round code system implemented and each team member received a copy of the master in which to carry out their individual coding assignment. Each team member coded their assigned data using the same coding system with agreed upon code definitions, ensuring that the entire data set was thoroughly and consistently coded. In addition to applying the horizontal code system, team members were free to develop their own set of 'vertical' codes which were agreed to only be of relevance to the section of data (Q1, 2, etc.) that each team member coded. Throughout this process, team members used in-project memos to document emergent data trends and codes, and documented in a shared methods journal issues with the coding system that would require discussion and potential revision.

Following this first phase of coding, the project team met to review initial results, discuss issues with the existing code system, and discuss vertical codes and new horizontal codes that should be added to a revised system. The team spent multiple hours discussing and revising the code system. Following agreement of a revised code system ([see Annex 14](#)), individual MAXQDA projects were merged into a new master project file, the code system was revised as agreed, and then updated projects were disseminated once again to each team member for the second phase of coding.

During the second phase of coding, each team member applied the revised code system to their area of data and flagged any further issues with the code system for discussion. Following this phase, the team met again to discuss emerging results and the functionality of the code system. At this meeting minor changes to the code system were agreed, as was the ongoing addition or adjustment of vertical codes by individual team members. At this meeting the team also discussed and agreed the plan for carrying out data analysis, thinking toward the big picture of the entire dataset as well as focusing on the individual work and interests of each team member (elaborated in the next section). The individual projects were once again merged in MAXQDA to unify the fully coded dataset, agreed minor changes to the code system were made and projects distributed to each team member for the conduct of a final phase of coding (as necessary) and data analysis.

2.3.3. Data analysis procedure and writing

The division of labour for data analysis (and later, for reporting on findings in subsequent chapters) was organized in the same way as for coding. Team members used the code system to identify and examine data trends within, across and at the intersections of coded segments. While each team member focused on their assigned section of data, they used the code system to identify themes and trends across the entire dataset.

After a two-week period of data analysis, the team met to discuss and debate emergent findings and to reach consensus on important questions or areas of focus for continued data analysis. Following another two-week period of independent data analysis and outlining of findings, the team met again to share findings and to

reach consensus on those which would be presented in writing in the subsequent chapters of this document. This point marked the commencement of the active writing period in which the team began to collaboratively compose this document, with each member responsible for leading the authorship of a chapter that reports on the findings primarily derived from the section of data that they analyzed. Team members worked collaboratively on the writing process through the Google Docs platform and met for a writing workshop after a two-week period of individual work. Using both online and in-person feedback and discussion, the team workshopped each member's contribution and developed together a conceptualization of theoretical framing and overarching findings, and analytic and narrative threads. Following a multi-week period of intensive writing, the team met again for the same purposes. The outcome of this work is the substantive chapters that follow. Bernhard Wieser is the lead author of Chapter 3, Stefan Reichmann is the lead author of Chapter 4, Nicki Lisa Cole is the lead author of Chapter 5, and Tony Ross-Hellauer is the lead author of Chapter 6. While each team member focused on a section of data as described above, using the code system they also examined the entire dataset. Therefore, there are some overlaps in the findings chapters that follow.

3. Findings (1): Framings of the science-policy interface

3.1. Introduction

The work in this report is part of a larger research effort that aims at understanding the uptake of scientific knowledge in the policy domain. As we described in the introduction to this report, as a first step, Reichmann et al. (2020) conducted a literature review to learn from existing research. They found that conceptions of uptake and implementation are often grounded in idealized and even naïve assumptions of how policy-making works. Paul Cairney and colleagues note, “Very few of these studies [on the evidence-policy gap] draw on policy theory” (Cairney, Oliver, und Wellstead 2016, 400). We take this as an invitation to contribute more knowledge on the science-policy interface and the role of scientific knowledge in this regard. Against this backdrop, this report aims to contribute to a “more differentiated view of policy-making” (Cairney, Oliver, und Wellstead 2016, 400).

Mapping out different models of policy-making, this chapter seeks to facilitate a better-informed understanding of the various ways in which researchers engage with policy processes and seek to make meaningful knowledge contributions. Taking an empirical approach, we map different perspectives on policy processes taken. Asking our participants how they understand policy processes and how they position their own research in relation to the policy domain, it is possible to move towards a more informed understanding of the uptake of scientific knowledge in the policy domain. We found that three different perspectives were relevant for the participants’ understanding of science-policy interface:

- The first perspective focuses on institutions and proceedings of *representative democracy* (cf. Schmidt 2019). Constitutional laws define who has a mandate to make political decisions and how decisions are made in parliament (or respective assemblies). Furthermore, representative democracy defines a framework in which policies ought to be implemented. Not least for the high efficacy of parliamentary decisions, the workshop participants viewed elected politicians as important addressees of scientific policy advice.
- Secondly, a perspective was identified commonly known as *deliberative democracy* (cf. Habermas 2005). Processes of deliberative democracy seek to engage a much wider set of actors, scientific experts, practitioners, various stakeholders, civil society organisations (CSOs) and members of the public. The main idea is to enhance policy processes through participatory forms of deliberation. In this way, policy processes are expected to be more inclusive and accessible to a wider set of societal actors. Furthermore, deliberative democracy is suggested to advance public acceptance through a broad consensus.
- A third perspective promotes *participatory democracy* (cf. Owen, Macnaghten, and Stilgoe 2012; Owen and Pansera 2019). The core idea of this model seeks to expand policy processes beyond the institutions of representative democracy and to integrate processes of knowledge production and policy-making. Here knowledge is not only produced collaboratively with practitioners and affected communities but those engaged in the knowledge creation should be able to benefit directly from it. With its strong emphasis on effective application, this policy model promotes the integration of knowledge making, deliberation and decision-making processes. Bringing together scientific experts, civil society actors and policy-makers, participatory processes are framed as an opportunity to overcome accustomed boundaries between different societal domains. If knowledge is co-produced

by such a broad set of actors, it is no longer necessary to deliver, transfer or translate knowledge in order to advise policy decisions. Instead, collaboratively produced knowledge can be implemented in the context of its creation.

The three described models can be read as an historical development of the science-policy interface; a development that is reflected in the accounts of the workshop participants. In their statements, they explain the difficulties with each of the respective models and thereby reveal how newer approaches responded to the shortcomings of the preceding one. Beginning with scientific policy advice for institutions of representative democracy, the participants point to the limitations of this type of science-policy relationship (cf. Schomberg 2019). The institutions and actors of the political system were criticised as inaccessible or resistant to scientific advice. As a response to this criticism the promoters of deliberation endorsed a much broader participation of societal actors in political processes. Over time it became clear that also the deliberative model had shortcomings as it was faced with low rates of uptake among policy circles (cf. Loeber, Griessler, und Versteeg 2011). Once more, attempts to further advance the uptake of scientific knowledge combined with higher degrees of public engagement can be observed (Owen, Macnaghten, und Stilgoe 2012). Pursuing a participatory approach promises more efficacy (valorisation) by systematically engaging policy-makers, scientific experts and civil society actors from the beginning, in the form of upstream engagement (cf. Owen et al. 2013).

Although the three described models have appeared in a consecutive order, it is important to mention that none of them have lost their relevance. Rather, today they co-exist. The participants of the three workshops present a variety of forms in which researchers provide scientific knowledge and engage with a broad set of societal actors and policy-makers over the course of policy-relevant research and the implementation of its results. The analysis of their accounts presented in this chapter follows the aforementioned three models. This structure sheds light on how the workshop participants understand policy processes and how they seek to contribute with their own work. This work responds to Cairney et al.'s (2016) request for a more informed understanding of policy processes when inquiring into the uptake of scientific knowledge in the policy domain and what can be done to enhance it.

3.2. Representative democracy and scientific policy advice

In the political science literature representative democracy in its contemporary form is often described as an elite system (Schmidt 2019; Seifert 2002; Cairney, Oliver, und Wellstead 2016). Representative democracy is defined through its constitution and epitomised by its institutions and actors. The parliament as the primary site of policy-making lies at the centre. The constitution defines the framework for what happens in parliament. This is precisely why the political science literature foregrounds the significance of the constitution and how it pre-structures policy processes (Schmidt 2019).

Without doubt the parliament is relevant for policy processes. Accordingly, it is interesting to know how the parliament receives scientific knowledge and how this knowledge is used in respective decision processes. Uptake of scientific knowledge in the policy domain moves to the centre of interest. Indeed, there is a large number of institutions and procedures by which processes of scientific policy advice take place (cf. Halligan 1995; Dagger et al. 2004; Hilgartner 2000). Besides legislative assemblies, ministries and public administration are crucially relevant institutions of policy-making. In addition, there are institutions of parliamentary technology assessment (Grunwald 2002), Advisory Boards (Bogner and Torgersen 2005), Ethics Committees (Emmerich 2009), think tanks (McGann 2007) and so on. Finally, individuals of recognised expertise are relevant, too (cf. Jasanoff 2005). During the COVID-19 pandemic, institutions and individuals

appeared on the frontstage of policy-making. Most of this policy advice work, however, remains publicly unnoticed.

If we now ask what contributes to the uptake of scientific expertise in the policy domain it is possible to give a clear answer to this question: congruence. The term congruence suggests that scientific expertise is more likely to enjoy uptake if it is in line with political goals and the provided knowledge promises hints of how to achieve these goals. This is exactly how a respondent put it during one of the workshops:

But I think a key moment actually in this type of issue is whether in terms of scientific information you have or you want to share with policy-makers, whether it fits to an existing problem definition. So, if you have an established problem definition in policy or even previously in politics, then of course you have a higher chance of being successful in getting into this. (P8, agriculture workshop)

The core idea behind the congruence argument is as follows. If scientific expertise meets given policy goals its uptake in the policy domain is more likely to happen. In other words, scientific expertise will be taken up by policy actors if it can be utilised to their (instrumental) goals.

A participant of another workshop articulated a similar argument. P4 suggested that scientists would influence politicians only to a minimal degree, since the latter would pursue pre-existing policy goals. If politicians take up expertise, they do so because it is congruent with what lies within the scope of their political goals.

My both unsuccessful and successful experience with policy-making was that oftentimes scientists are used as a mascots or marionettes to justify what the politicians want to do. But it's good that if they have some experts, some scientists that they can somehow refer to and that they can mention that this is based, what they propose is based on some scientific findings. (P4, climate workshop)

From P4's point of view, the use of scientific expertise is rather instrumental. Right at this point of the discussion during one of the workshops, P5 affirmatively commented on the presented example. He noted that the congruence with policy goals is not the only factor that matters. In addition, it would also matter if policy-makers hold the power to enforce their policy goals. Only if this is so, scientific expertise would be effective eventually. P4, too, confirmed this point of view and stated:

Yeah, it's a good point. I agree. So, it was a chance that that was something that they wanted to do anyway. But if I brought on something different, they would probably never read that. But maybe one more aspect is that it's [a minor political party] and they are not the dominant force or the major party in the government. So, maybe it actually might also slow down in a way because if a party who is in opposition proposes something then the main party might be actually unwilling to accept it in a way. It might not necessarily lead to a final success at the end because it's not the party who has the majority or who is in the coalition in the parliament. (P4, climate workshop)

Here P4 draws on the argument of policy enforcement of P5 and confirms this view on her own part as can be seen in the cited extract. Against this backdrop, we can conclude that politicians are accessible for scientific knowledge especially if the offered expertise is congruent with their own policy goals. This allows

us to argue that uptake takes place when the conditions are favourable. On the other hand, it has become clear that this is not always so and in the latter case the policy domain is rather inaccessible.

Another important aspect of policy advice is whether scientific experts are invited or not. P4 argued her point and highlighted that congruence is often linked to invited consultation. P4 suggested that invited consultation is a constellation in which scientific advice is well received in the policy domain. P2 made a similar point when he explained how he gladly took the opportunity of reporting climate policy activities on behalf of the national government. This invited consultation gave him the opportunity to aid such climate policy activities with scientific expertise. He explained:

As you know, the [national] government, like all governments that have signed the Agenda 2030 in 2015, also have to report about their activities in a five-year period. Also, [this member state] has to report to the European Union. So, basically if you phrase it in a negative way, you could say that the government was outsourcing the work. Maybe they should have gone to the universities, but we have also taken it up in a way, gladly to help. It's an attempt to provide input and to basically strengthen the knowledge basis which should help develop more profound strategies for advancing sustainable development in [this member state] and beyond. (P2, interview)

P4, too, explained that she and her team have been invited to write a policy brief on the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic. More participants explained that their work can be described as invited advice. The (national) government or the parliament asks for expertise on a defined issue and those invited seek to answer this request. Another participant noted:

We really try, based on research process and research results, we produce some expertise for the policy-making. The way we do that, we do that in several processes. Some are just expertise like we produce for the European Parliament where they pay for that. There is a call, we answer the call, that was on the CAP and the Green Deal, it was this type of process. That's very classical. The Parliament asked for an expertise. (P10, interview)

P10 is aware of the normative framework in which she works, but the policy goals are externally defined by policy-makers. Her part is meant to be instrumental to these external policy goals. P10 continued to explain that she needs to follow the normative demands of her clients. She explained that whenever she proposes some measures to meet policy goals (e.g. climate goals, public health goals, etc.), she needs to demonstrate their economic viability. Without that, the proposed measures will not be considered and not even noticed by policy-makers.

The first question is okay, but you're going to decrease the yield. Yes. So, we are going to try to design measures to help agriculture. Okay, how much money are you going to give to support? So, after it's just question of money. If you can't produce an impact assessment saying if you make this effort, you will lose that and the policy in [this country] is going to give you that and we're going also to change, for example, to change the markets and to improve also the price of the products and so on. But if you can't put, if you are not able to produce an impact assessment, it's not possible. (P10, interview)

What is outside the demanded rationale is not welcome. It is important to acknowledge that the presented approach of P10 is a function of the circumstances in which she works, as an advisor to institutions of representative democracy.

3.2.1. Critiquing inaccessibility

In light of the rather differentiated institutional landscape that informs democratically legitimised policy decisions, a considerable amount of uptake of scientific knowledge takes place (cf. Gerhardt 2004). Despite this fact, a criticism cannot be ignored that views representative democracy as elitist and inaccessible (cf. Dagger et al. 2004). For outsiders it would be almost impossible to be heard. Only those who are asked (“invited advice”) have a chance of contributing with their expertise to policy processes. Consequently, the proposed criticism raises the following question: what makes the political (elite) system more accessible? How is it possible to make policy processes more responsive to contributions from outside? Before I return to the question, how this might be possible, I turn to the critique of inaccessibility to show what precisely is at stake. One participant shared his experiences with political institutions:

It’s really a big black box, so it’s very difficult to get entry there and to have an impact and to have a sustained impact. (P14, health workshop)

The respondent continued to explain that the elite-system would work to a certain degree, but he also critically noted, experts who enjoy reception would also belong to an elite. In other words, the elite system would not be inclusive, not with regard to policy processes and not with regard to knowledge-making processes either. He further detailed his criticism of inaccessibility:

Sorry for being so lengthy but I think we really lack that the processes how we get science and research into policy-making. The traditional ones of having some expert boards, yes, to a certain extent it works. But also, these people who are in the expert boards, they are also privileged within the research community. So, these are also not the counter-voices. (P14, health workshop)

In this extract, P14 draws on the congruence argument and adds to it that the political elite system would be inaccessible for counter-voices, who articulate incongruent perspectives. Once more he emphasised how much the political system would block outsiders. P14 articulated very clearly that he experienced the policy domain as rather inaccessible due to what he calls “structural inertia” and the social structure of impermeable political networks.

Similarly, P3 voiced his criticism of the inaccessibility of the elite system. He shared his experiences where it was not possible to convince policy-makers to participate in engagement processes. P3 assumed that policy-makers would not come if they did not see a clear benefit for their own agenda:

Just one quick experience which I had in several projects at European or also national level is not so much a breakdown but that it never takes off. So, these are projects which include some stakeholder engagement and workshops with stakeholders where there is a naïve expectation that you influence policy by inviting policy-makers there. Also, we had projects for example about smart grids and energy transitions at the urban level. Very often, I mean it’s a kind of coalition also that between the funding agencies are expecting that you would involve politicians and also then in the project proposal, people then wrote you have a—I don’t know—community of practice where you have then different actors

from civil society, but also politicians. I think it underestimates or has the wrong concept of how you can influence policy-making processes. It's not just through the participation of politicians but also what would motivate such people to participate. So, I have seen quite—I've participated myself in quite a few projects which had this element of engaging policy-makers and they failed in not being able in the end to bring policy-makers on board. It was not the project failure, but this element was often very weak then in the end. (P3, climate workshop)

In this extract, P3 goes beyond the point of inaccessibility of the political elite system. In his last point, he claims how difficult it would be—and often not possible at all—to persuade policy-makers to engage in participatory processes. It is possible to read this statement as a crucial aspect of the inaccessibility of the political system. At the same time however, the respondent critically reflects that the assumption would be naïve that by participation alone impact on the political domain was to be achieved automatically. In light of this, accessibility goes beyond the mere opportunity of sitting together around the same table. For an effective implementation more is needed.

Another dimension of the inaccessibility of the political elite can be seen in frequent observations by our workshop participants suggesting that policy-makers do not read scientific literature.

I don't have the illusion that the person I'm working with in [a competent authority] who's responsible for the next adaptation strategy is going to read whatever I write in Nature Climate Change. (P1, interview)

The same view is taken by other participants (e.g., P4, P5 and P14). Agreeing with the general thrust of the workshop discussion, P4 noted that the political system is not equally (in-)accessible on all accounts. In her experiences, for instance, persons from lower ranks would be more accessible than their counterparts in higher ranks. Similar to P14, P4 pointed out that the political system would indeed not be completely hermetical, but that there always were approachable individuals. P4 shared her positive experiences with individuals of lower ranks or those who belong to the support staff. Nevertheless, P4 also addressed the difficulty of finding access. The political system is perceived as inaccessible even when basic difficulties can be overcome. The respondents of the workshops broadly shared the presented conclusion of the inaccessibility of political elites. They not only pointed to the inaccessibility of the political system, but they also pointed out reasons why this is the case: primarily, power dynamics.

3.2.2. Power dynamics

From P1's point of view, the perceived shortcomings of the political elite system result from the antagonistic structure of politics. If conflicts of interests are to be negotiated only a minimal consensus is possible to be achieved. Circumstances dominated by power dynamics, would not be accessible to scientific expertise. P1 gave an example:

There was a very toxic power dynamic going on in the background. There was a high-level commission that meant to have input into the actual process. The preparation of a flagship report was constantly interrupted by all sorts of non-substantive issues. In the end, the report came out that is pretty much the lowest common denominator of things that people could agree on. (P1, climate workshop)

The content dimension of the mentioned flagship report was overshadowed by power dynamics among the participating policy-makers. P1 continued to explain that the committee he was attending discussed further steps of disseminating the report. The main point of discussion was, however, who would appear as the leader.

It was absolutely amazing how they were unable to reach agreement including whose name comes first and stuff like that, where an enormous amount of time and effort was wasted on procedural issues. We spent more time actually getting the outline of the report approved by the commission members than working on the actual report. The commission members were CEOs of companies, government ministers, heads of international organisations and civil society. (P1, climate workshop)

P1 pointed out that, in the mentioned case, the content of his scientific input was of secondary interest. What dominated the described situation, P1 saw as political vanity and power-play of politics. He perceives the political domain inaccessible to reasonable argumentation. The reason behind the described constellation suggests that politicians do not only pursue their own political goals, but they exploit every opportunity to present themselves as decisive actors. In light of this view, politicians do not only seek to enforce their positions, but it is especially important for them to show that it was precisely their merit of having achieved just that. Accordingly, the congruence of goals has to coincide with what can be called the ‘success of effective political action’. At this point an important aspect comes to the fore. Policy-making cannot be reduced to finding solutions to technical problems—even though some of the participants found this idea appealing (cf. Cairney, Oliver, und Wellstead 2016, 400). However, the negotiation of competing interests is central to policy-making and accordingly it is decisive for policy-makers to demonstrate the negotiation success achieved on their own part. For that reason, policy-makers engage in competitive relationships with one another.

The vital importance of power dynamics can be observed in other workshop contributions. The respondents reported about experiences where such ‘success of effective political action’ was under threat. P18 notes:

The governors were quite offended by the fact that they felt we were comparing them, especially the counties where family planning indicators were not doing very well were very furious and they felt that the data we used and how we went about it, first of all we excluded them; second, we completely did not consider other very unique factors that affect their communities. (P18, health workshop)

In the cited extract P18 argues that the mentioned politician felt threatened by the presented scientific expertise, it undermined his role as a politician. As P18 suggests, the mentioned politician took it as a proposition that the unfavourable indicators would be his responsibility. The example of P18 is not about a conflict over political goals, but it is about the threat to power in the form of scientific evidence.

Other respondents, too, explained that in their experience, power dynamics lead to inaccessibility. Especially if authorities feel challenged, they are not responsive or open to contributions from outside and there are many things that may be perceived as threats to power. Another aspect that impacts on the uptake of scientific knowledge was linked to reputation. P9 concluded that her personal and institutional reputation, and her gender in particular, influences whether or not she is taken seriously and met with respect. Sharing his experiences, P5 explained another facet of power dynamics in our climate workshop. He first explained how a nation committed itself to meet specific climate goals and to the transition to a low-carbon economy,

but abandoned this commitment when a coal deposit was discovered. As he saw it, the political leaders prioritised short-term economic opportunities over climate policy goals. In other words, the definition of policy goals is not only a political act, but also a matter of power exercised by politicians who chose to change previously agreed policy goals. Under the described circumstances P5 found it challenging to contribute with scientific expertise.

Taken together, power dynamics were presented as a barrier to the uptake of scientific expertise in the policy domain. More generally, the political elites of representative democracy are often viewed as difficult to access. In the next section, we shed more light on the approaches intended to make the elite political system more accessible.

3.2.3. Policy goals and the role of international organisations

Traditional forms of policy advice assume responsibility for the definition of policy goals on the part of political elites. Increasingly, this assumption has been called into question. Many of our respondents made clear that they sought to engage in the very formation of policy goals. Thus, the role of knowledge integration in the policy domain is no longer restricted to supplying political elites with science-based solutions to predefined problems. However, when attempting to contribute to the formation of policy goals in the first place, the question arises how this is possible (and what role policy-relevant research may play in this regard). One of our respondents, P8, pointed exactly to this difference between predefined policy goals and the involvement in the process or their formation. P8 notes:

The interesting cases of course is whether if you have scientific information which would show—would or should make policy change that problem definition. This is normally a much harder task. This is a much more political task and this is happening of course in the context where lobbyists and scientists concert. So, that's not an entry point I think in policy-making where scientists join a particular lobby group. This is an instrumentalization of science as well, of course. (P8, health workshop)

In the cited extract the respondent draws a boundary. Policy-making can be viewed as the implementation and the achievement of political goals. He contrasts a second central dimension of policy-making which concerns the very shaping of these goals. This leads to the question of the role scientific knowledge can play in both of these dimensions respectively. According to the traditional framing, scientific knowledge has an instrumental role; it should help to solve predefined problems (cf. Weiss 1979). The knowledge in question needs to be causal, to allow political measures to be derived from it.

The second dimension concerns the establishment of policy goals themselves. Without doubt, this is the home ground of policy-making and elected representatives do precisely that. The formation of policy goals is a normative process. According to a conventional understanding of science (which is grounded in the ethos of “disinterestedness”; Merton (1996 [1942]) or Weber’s (2002 [1914]) “*Werturteilsfreiheit*”) this would be of no concern to science. The part of scientific knowledge is to help with causal knowledge over the course of the implementation of policy goals, but not to engage in processes where political positions are negotiated. From this point of view policy work is normative and interest driven.

Arguably, the described separation between science and politics is artificial or perhaps even illusionary. Contemporary approaches rather seek to integrate knowledge and norms meaningfully in the policy process (cf. Gohl 2004). It is impossible to set political goals without reference to propositions of what is the case. In other words, it is impossible to set political goals without a consideration of facts and what can be done to

alter the circumstance of the case (cf. P5's argument on the health and environmental risks of coal). It is crucial to consider that the process of problem definition is in itself a genuinely political act. Accordingly, those who engage in such formation processes become political actors themselves. This political role, however, clashes with traditional forms of scientific identity and compromises the epistemological idea of "impartial knowledge" (cf. Speth 2004), however flawed that assumption may be.

Against this backdrop, the positioning of scientists as policy actors, the above cited statement of P8 appears in a new light. For him it is exactly the point where the question arises, what are legitimate forms of engagement? Lobbying, P8 understands as overstepping these boundaries. Beyond the aspect of boundary work, it is furthermore interesting to ask more generally how policy goals can acquire the status of legitimacy?

Our respondents were acutely aware of this implication. P15 presented her solution to the legitimacy challenge. She frames her work in indisputable values. Human rights and gender rights are viewed to have this quality.

Yeah, a really great point and I can share one of the methodologies. Again, this is coming from a... We're bipartisan in the sense we don't pick a political party when we're a non-profit here in [this county] but our movement is global. So, it makes it almost easier to be even more not associated with any political party because we're targeting all countries and our focuses, human rights, gender rights, and they are very political issues and in each country they can be different. But they're universally a common agenda that we're focused on. So, I think that helps in one way because of what our interest is and how it's not a party-based interest necessarily." (P15, health workshop)

The way in which P15 constructs legitimacy is instructive. The normative grounding of policy goals can be justified by ethical norms, which can be presented as "universally a common agenda". The claimed universality suggests that such ethical norms are beyond debate, they can be taken for granted. A similar legitimacy construction can be found in relation to the sustainable development goals (SDGs). Accordingly, the SDGs serve as a firm basis for the justification of policy goals derived from this normative foundation. Despite their significance, the SDGs are not universal, but a product of political decisions. This is precisely the point, where the role of supranational policy-making plays a key part.

The UN is a form of representative policy-making. Member states send delegates to the general assembly. The UN is a form of "consocial democracy" (cf. Schmidt 2019). In order to secure the highest levels of legitimacy, decisions are preferably unanimous. UN decisions are highly effective because they bestow political goals with legitimacy. This is precisely the reason why researchers seek to get access to the political arena of the UN. The idea is to create a normative grounding for concrete policy goals. The normatively legitimizing dimension of the SDGs can be traced in the accounts of our participants. The reference to the Paris Climate Agreement is an example of the importance of supranational policy decisions.

But on other topics, now [...] we're definitely talking with the UNFCCC. I think we've got a better entry point now because the Paris Agreement mentions [that]. (P1, interview)

The described strategy is of great significance for advocacy work. UN decisions such as the SDGs in particular justify the political work of advocates. In such a way it is possible to draw on a normative foundation. Furthermore, it is possible to demand compliance with these principles from national (or local) political actors

and demand realisation. In other words, the non-responsive political elite system can be addressed via a detour using supranational policy arenas (such as the UN or the WHO). The UN as a leverage is of greatest significance, since it promises efficacy and because it provides a viable solution to the legitimacy problem.

Other international organisations such as the WHO, the EU, the OECD or the World Bank have a similar function in justifying policy goals and they hold the potential to move national policies forward. P1 explained the momentous leverage of the OECD.

Whether you looked at the [various countries], they just weren't ready for that yet. And then again, the OECD—and I have a lot of respect for the OECD because I think many of the sort of policy breakthroughs at least in my field that I've seen over the past few years have come through OECD picking up an issue and convincing member states that this is important to them. (P1, interview)

In the cited extract, the OECD is presented as a decisive policy actor, which if addressed successfully exercises momentous effects on other policy actors.

Summing up, our participants pointed to the significance of individuals and institutions of representative democracy ranging from local to supranational policy arenas. Especially international organisations were conceived as highly effective policy actors due to their legitimizing power at defining policy goals. Uptake of scientific policy advice is more likely to happen when it is invited and congruent with policy goals as defined by the political elites. In addition, our participants explained that in many cases their work goes beyond the provision of scientific expertise, but they seek to contribute to the formation of policy goals in the first place. With that, however, the role of policy-relevant research is taken to another level of the science-policy interface—the interactive deliberation of political issues amongst a broader set of societal actors.

3.3. Deliberative democracy

The past three decades saw the development of a wealth of methods aiming to make policy processes more inclusive (cf. Fischer 2005). How is it possible to include a broader scope of the public in political decision-making? The efforts sought to go beyond the mere possibility of a plebiscite and to allow for deliberation. Not just the decisions in the narrow sense, but especially processes of exchange and debate were valued. The aim was to understand and contribute to how arguments and positions are constructed, to consider a multitude of perspectives and to facilitate dialogue and thereby lead to better results (cf. Gohl 2004). All of this requires debate and not just a dichotomous yes-or-no decision as prompted by a plebiscite.

During our workshops our respondents drew on deliberative democracy and expressed the core idea behind it. P17, for instance, shared his experiences in a project of his. The objective was to investigate environmental factors of cancer. To this end, he and his colleagues brought together a group of different stakeholders to understand their knowledge around the issue. He explained:

What we hoped to do was facilitate a dialogue between those groups and medical experts, doctors, oncologists with that expertise and knowledge in cancer to see if there was any merit in doing any further investigation of these stakeholder groups' beliefs or perceptions about what might be possible causes or triggers. (P17, health workshop)

Here P17 presents himself as 'facilitator of dialogue'. He himself does not take on the role of a scientific expert, which was reserved for the participating oncologists. His task was to organise a process during which

deliberation could take place. Political controversies have fuelled a boom of deliberative methods. It is fair to say that deliberation was in demand when politics shifted from the parliament to the street. This is precisely what happened over the course of the Genetically Modified Organism (GMO) controversy. Many European countries responded with an increased application of deliberative processes (cf. Seifert 2002).

It is important to recognise forms of deliberative democracy as a policy innovation. The point is that deliberative democracy refers to processes which are not (or only partly) defined by the constitution (cf. Schmidt 2019). Participation is not grounded in an (constitutionally legitimised) electoral process of its participants (cf. Gohl 2004). This results in a basic difficulty of deliberative democracy. The results of such processes are not constitutionally obligatory but merely recommendatory. If, however, deliberative processes are constitutionally not obligatory its results can simply be ignored. For this reason, the merits of deliberative processes have been called into question. Critical analysis in the wake of the heyday of deliberative processes has produced rather disenchanting appraisal. It is difficult to claim broad political efficacy for deliberative processes (cf. Loeber, Griessler, und Versteeg 2011). There are some exceptions where deliberative processes succeeded to impact on the decisions of representative policy-making. These remain, however, the exception rather than the rule. Even the Danish style Consensus Conference has received criticism in this respect (Horst 2014). By and large national parliaments have been rather unresponsive to the stimuli of deliberative processes.

The workshop participants have been aware of these developments, which is reflected in their statements. P3, for instance, pointed to the fact that participatory methods tend to attract those who are more resourceful to engage. P3 explains that in his experience those who engage in deliberation are often individuals who represent CSOs who he sees as having improved their repertoire in terms of knowledge production and to some degree may even work in scientific contexts. P3 explained:

*So, they have the higher share of people who have higher education backgrounds who often do their own research, they get research funding, research resources, so they have started increasingly also to use science and become the research actor also on their own.
(P3, interview)*

This observation leads P3 to critically conclude that the limited inclusiveness of public participation in deliberative democracy is rather symbolic.

Even though the respondents of our workshops were aware of such critical views, they were at the same time in favour of public deliberation. In his statement, P17 noted that the goal of engagement is not solely defined by its debated issues, but they are also directed towards a procedural objective that is democratisation. For this reason, the successful application of participatory deliberation is in itself a policy goal. Accordingly, the facilitation of such processes becomes an urgent task in order to utilise public policy as a means to enhance policy processes. For those, who take on the role of a facilitator it is important to maintain a self-presentation as someone who does not pursue a particular policy goal themselves, except for one, that is to aid democracy.

P17 reported a success story in which the results of a deliberation he facilitated could be presented at parliament. On this occasion a number of “lay-persons” came along to give first-hand accounts. The case of P17 exemplifies a specific “political culture” that resonated well in the respective country. In the presented example of P17, two forms of uptake are at stake: a) uptake of knowledge (lay-knowledge, situated

knowledge, to some extent medical knowledge from the fringes) and b) uptake of a specific policy goal; that is democratisation through public deliberation. Both of these goals are expressed by the statement of P17:

We managed to hold... it was taken up by a MP. We did have a committee meeting in one of the Parliamentary select committees, they held us a special working group where we got some of the lay participants in and we got a few people on the fringes of medical profession involved, but not the real medical doctors and oncologists that we were hoping to engage with. (P17, health workshop)

The goal of the reported deliberative exercise was to submit its results to the political elite system (the Parliament). As the example of P17 impressively shows, this goal was achieved in this case.

3.3.1. Reflexivity

Deliberation does not necessarily involve members of the general public. There are also other forms such as stakeholder consultations and collaborative research with practitioners and CSOs. In an interview prior to the workshop P3 explained how he sees his role in such deliberative contexts. The main goal for him is to enhance reflexivity. Understanding socio-technical change as a co-production of diverse elements is a good starting point. P3 goes on to explain that the main goal is not simply to provide evidence and knowledge, but to aid reflexivity of policy processes:

I think if we talk about policy-making there then it's also important to have a more differentiated view of policy-making. It's not just policy-makers. You want to get at policy-making, I'm not sure whether trying to get policy-makers into projects is the way of change with research. So, it's also about understanding, unpacking, reflecting about these processes of how policy and science is interlinked. I think words might have or should have, could have also a long-term impact on how policy-makers think about science. (P3, interview)

The declared goal of enhancing reflexivity of policy goals corresponds with a specific way of casting one's own role when engaging in policy deliberation. P3 presents himself as a "facilitator". His goal is to facilitate collaboration of social groups with different types of knowledge, but also actors with a variety of political interests. At the same time, P3 is aware of the normative component of his work. Aiming at sustainable transition requires careful boundary work in order to maintain the desired role as a facilitator of deliberation and collaboration. If engaged with a diverse set of actors, a facilitator is required to balance the different interests coming together over the course of the collaboration.

In a sense, there's this constant facilitation, negotiation, boundary drawing going on in such projects. But this plays out always very differently, so I wouldn't say, so I am a facilitator. (P3, interview)

Similar to P3, P2 explains how he frames his role as consulted expert. Rather than "making" policies on his own, his primary goal is to aid policy processes with more reflexivity. As will be shown later in this chapter, other participants were less hesitant to ground their work in a normative standing. If reflexivity and facilitation is foregrounded, the primary goal is to advance policy processes through participatory and more inclusive forms of deliberation, which can be seen as an end in itself (cf. P17).

3.3.2. Political culture and socio-political context

The three workshops carried out in this project offered insights into the role of political culture and the socio-cultural context. It strongly depends on the context as to how deliberative practices are being received by the policy domain (cf. Richard Owen and Pansera 2019, 41–42). Countries with a more responsive political culture are more open to absorb the outcomes of deliberative processes as opposed to countries whose political culture is more elitist and closed. This cultural difference may materialize in respective legal regulations (as P10 points out) or the lack of it. The example of P17, too, shows that in his country the appreciation of deliberation (on the part of parliamentary committees) is part of the political culture.

Another respondent, P16, emphasises the significance of democratic structures. Policy processes need specific framework conditions in order to realize their positive potential. Without a legal framework, there is no effective representation of interests. Yet, more is needed than merely a formal legal framework. Deliberative democracy needs the willingness to take up its outcomes. Deliberative processes can only fully unfold their potential if carried out in a responsive political culture.

The significance of the political culture in a given context is broadly shared by the participants. One, P9, shared her views on the significance of the cultural context:

I guess it'd be good to reflect on it further with others. But just off the top of my head, I think it's not as simplistic as one assumes and that we're working in contexts where democratic processes are not the norm or the custom and we're trying to impose participation on groups of people that are not used to participation. (P9, interview)

P12 also spoke to the significance of the political culture. He noted that it would matter if “policy engagement” would be carried out “in a more democratic system or an authoritarian system.” P11 shared a similar view when emphasising the role of socio-political context and how this backdrop impacts on the uptake of science in the policy domain. P11 explained the democratic nature of engagement and participation. Yet, the context where such ideas are introduced are sometimes anything but democratic. Policy-makers act in a hierarchical system, which according to P11, is not democratic at all. For that reason, the democratic characteristics of engagement processes or participatory deliberation may be received with reservation or cause irritation if inserted in undemocratic environments. P11 suggests that the flavour of democratic processes seems to cast a considerable threat to authoritarian environments. At the same time the presented view can also be interpreted as further evidence of the inaccessibility of the policy domain and low rates of uptake. Undoubtedly, the workshop participants foreground the significance of the political culture for the uptake of deliberative democracy. This view is reflected in the literature which suggests that deliberation works particularly well in the Netherlands, Canada and Denmark. The Danish Consensus Conference, especially, was met with great enthusiasm around the world. Although often tried, it proved difficult to export the method to socio-political contexts outside of Scandinavia. It may furthermore be added that relative low uptake of the results of deliberative processes in the policy domain has led to considerable disappointment. This may have contributed to what is known as “participation fatigue” (cf. Hayward, Simpson, and Wood 2004).

In sum, the participants shared experiences and views that resonate with the model of deliberative democracy. They saw participatory methods as a meaningful way to include a broader set of social groups in the deliberation process and suitable to enhance reflexivity. However, they also pointed to the limitations as they experienced them when engaged in respective activities. Political culture, notably, can be a hindrance.

In the next section, we trace how the participants presented accounts of recent advancements of the deliberative approach and thereby seek to strengthen its efficacy in the policy domain.

3.4. Collaborative engagement

A long and rich tradition of public policy has led to success, but also to failure and frustration (Fischer 2005). The experience of inaccessibility and non-responsiveness of policy-makers persists. This is not to say that there would be no contradictory examples. Indeed, there are and they continue to inspire researchers and civil society actors to keep pushing for more inclusive forms of knowledge-production and policy-making. Nevertheless, the awareness of the limitations of deliberative democracy and public policy came to the fore. It is important to understand the evolution of recent developments as a response to a broader assessment of the science-policy relationship and its rather modest achievements. New methods and forms of engagement as well as new ways to achieve and facilitate change towards desirable societal goals are in high demand. This recent trend is also reflected in a shift from government to governance and more specifically to “sustainable governance” (Gohl 2004).

In the following section, we turn to strategies that try to overcome the observed drawbacks. Recent attempts to advance knowledge integration in policy-making processes comprise a number of elements. They include: a) proximity to decision-makers and practitioners, b) co-production of knowledge, c) communities of practice, d) upstream engagement and e) normativity (mission-oriented research). In practice, these elements come together in a variety of ways and not all of them are necessarily present in a particular case. Our participants explained the ways in which they realise these elements in their own work. Together they articulate an approach here summarized as “Collaborative engagement”.¹ This approach not only holds the promise to enhance uptake of knowledge in the policy domain, but also to facilitate higher degrees of implementation (efficacy) (cf. Owen and Pansera 2019, 29; Angelaki 2016).

The idea behind this strategy implies a significant shift. It does not target elected policy-makers as recipients of knowledge presented to them such as Bulmer (1990) has suggested with his “engineering model” (ibid. p. 125). Instead, it is viewed to be important to integrate societal actors who are in position to deploy knowledge to desired ends (policy goals). This draws on a broader discussion on how and what type of knowledge can help to meet societal needs (cf. Schomberg 2012; Owen et al. 2013). The knowledge in question has also been called “transdisciplinary knowledge”, a type of knowledge that ensures applicability by collaborative forms of knowledge production in which practitioners, affected groups (e.g., patients) and other societal actors are included (Fischer 2005). This can be best realised in close proximity to the context where knowledge (implementation) is needed. Such close collaboration can best flourish when researchers, civil society actors and decision makers are brought together in processes of knowledge production and implementation. A variety of different forms of expertise and social roles can be aligned to pursue a shared (policy) goal in communities of practice. It has been found that such integrated collaboration is most effective if it begins early on and already strives for participation during phases of problem definition and research design (upstream engagement). A final point mentioned by the workshop participants concerns normativity. Instead of separating normative influences from knowledge production, an integrated collaborative approach tries to overcome such accustomed division of labour. Societal needs constitute a normative starting point for research that is expected to provide solutions to the grand challenges of our times. Scientific

¹ Although it comes very close to what has been coined Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) we do not use this framing because a number of the workshop participants come from or work outside of Europe and are not familiar with the term RRI even though they articulate and use several of its characteristics (cf. Angelaki 2016).

knowledge can best contribute if it is collaboratively produced and implemented with societal actors and policy-makers. This idea is a significant diversion from a doctrine which suggests that elected policy-makers of representative democracy need to be made more attentive to unheard and dismissed scientific advice. In this section we trace the elements of a participatory approach in the accounts of the workshop participants.

3.4.1. Proximity

Proximity is an important element of the idea to take knowledge to where it is needed (and used). In the following statement P12 suggests that it matters who actually conveys knowledge. Uptake is more likely to happen when local people speak to the actors in their own contexts. Advisers and experts are often perceived as distant, disengaged or unaware of local priorities and circumstances. Embedded knowledge brokers are more likely to overcome such obstacles. In a conversation where these considerations came to the surface (P8 and P11), P12 added his own experiences of how locality and proximity to local policy-actors matter.

I think for the case of the local communities that we work with a lot, it's also a way for which they can then take up some of the issues that they get involved in their research when they engage with their own leadership at the local level and so on. They are much better able to understand the issues and much in a better position of course to articulate them. (P12, agriculture workshop)

Proximity is a methodological principle that P12 applies not just to local practitioners, but also to policy-makers, as he explains in the cited extract. Against this backdrop, it can be noted that local engagement does not exclusively remain at the level of practitioners. The intended effect on wider circles of the policy domain remains important. What becomes clear, however, is that P12 proposes proximity in two ways, a) towards practitioners AND b) towards policy-makers. The analysis of the cited extract furthermore reveals why researchers try to create proximity. Ideally it is possible to enrol a broad variety of actors and stakeholders and gather them around the same table. P12 continued to describe the importance of proximity. In his statement, proximity is interpreted as enculturation and belonging:

But the other part to that was also the proximity between the researchers that are involved in the research and the policy-makers. In many cases, I think P9 may also have experienced this—we work on international projects. When you have researchers that have a long proximity—say, for example, you're in [a given country] and you're implementing a project in [a country on another continent], the ability to be able to engage policy-makers diminishes because of the lack of social interaction, not being part of the social networks. In [a global context], most of the cases that we find are successful relate also to more interaction that happen in informal processes and settings rather than the more formal processes of writing letters and petitions and things. (P12, agriculture workshop)

P12 brings a variety of important aspects to the table. First, he notes that he refers to a small project in a local context (that he describes as an “authoritarian regime”). P12 continues to ask how existing policies (sustainable agriculture) are to be implemented. If tried by deploying a top-down strategy, theory and practice drift apart. The reason being because local communities pursue alternative priorities, which is to produce more. At this point P12 concludes that there was no uptake—the participants got disinterested, because their own goals differed from these policy goals. What's more, they did not see how P12 could help them implement their policies. Finally, P12 suggests that proximity is the key to success. He furthermore

explains that proximity is both an effective way to counter low uptake, inaccessibility and elitism. Notably, he foregrounds proximity to policy-makers. Other respondents relate proximity to practitioners.

3.4.2. Co-Production

The emphasis on proximity to the context where knowledge (implementation) is intended to happen is closely related to the concept of knowledge co-production. In order to ensure knowledge to be effective it is important to engage a variety of different social actors in processes of its creation. Such collaboration is key for the co-creation of knowledge. P9 explained this approach:

The types of methods that I usually use are participatory research approaches. I'm very interested in using knowledge co-production and working closely with multiple and diverse stakeholders to design research questions as well as identify problems and have solutions. On a higher level, I think the policy analysis, the legal analysis, that kind of governance type of work relates directly to policy because we examine—or I examine how can sustainability be enhanced in the certain context that we're working and are there legal parameters that allow for these actions to take place. And then on another level, in working with stakeholders it is to try to help them identify problems and design research questions so that they can arrive at solutions. I think it's very important to work with diverse stakeholders. When we think of policy-makers, when we think of policy change, but it's an ecosystem of people that influence changes in policy or changes in the way that we think about the environment, changes in our understanding with certain situations. (P9, interview)

This links back to proximity as P9 continued to explain co-creation allows to integrate local and context-specific knowledge. This approach is better suited to create “meaningful impacts”. Following the line of argument presented by P9, it is furthermore clear that this type of approach, aiming at proximity and co-creation, is ultimately linked with policy processes of representative democracy. The point is to close the gap between the policy domain and the world of practice via Collaborative engagement.

The idea is so that we can bring these perspectives to the government and say, here is what different people feel about the bioeconomy. There needs to be a different approach that's not top-down because how small holder farmers, large farmers, millers—we're looking in the sugarcane sector—the way that they understand equity in the bioeconomy is different from how the government sees it. (P9, interview)

The reason why P9 favours this approach is its effectiveness. In her view, there is no direct route to access policy-makers by simply providing them with scientific expertise. Co-creation processes where all stakeholders as well as policy-makers engage are more suitable. More participants explained co-production as a research method (e.g., P11, interview). P17 explains how he used Citizen Science (CS) and creative methods of engagement for environmental data collection. He continued to state that the applied approach was furthermore suitable for engaging policy-makers:

But the other co-created one I think was much more valuable for them in that what they did ultimately was collect or record environmental problems or challenges they had around their neighbourhoods, document them using smartphone photographs, map them, and we could produce a map to highlight where these problems were. And then, we were able to use that to create a dialogue with the local authority which meant, I think

when we last checked about half of those problems had been solved or fixed in some way. So, there was quite a radical impact if you like on the ground for the community from collecting the data, presenting it in a way that was useful for the policy decision-makers, and then seeing some changes on the ground. So, that was really valuable. (P17, interview)

3.4.3. Communities of practice

Co-creation refers to collaborative processes of knowledge production. However, what brings the participating civil society actors and policy-makers together is a shared concern, which is a societal problem for which they seek to develop a solution. In other words, the desired knowledge needs to be applicable and feasible to facilitate change. Ultimately it is these practices that connect a diverse set of participants, which can therefore be called ‘communities of practice’.

An important element of this approach is the integration of a practitioner’s perspective in order to respond to their needs, but also to integrate their local and practical knowledge (cf. P9, interview). The rationale behind the integration of practitioners is that it facilitates change. As important as practitioners are, in practice it is a challenge to keep them engaged. For this reason, it is vitally important that practitioners benefit from their participation. One participant, P4, shared her experiences with engagement in participatory events, and pointed out the danger of disengagement.

Especially, it’s interesting in the German part, in the Lusatia region, the stakeholders don’t really want to participate in our activities because they say there were so many projects before about this topic and they were asked to participate in workshops and they never had heard back something from the organisers. So, they feel even like used up that researchers write their papers, invite them, but they need the stakeholders to invite them for the workshops but they never send anything back and there’s no follow-up. (P4, interview)

Thus, transformative knowledge needs to be beneficial for affected social groups. Processes of knowledge production are more inclusive if securing immediate benefits of the generated knowledge for affected members of society. In this sense, knowledge is political. It is the politics of empowerment and emancipation; it is the attempt to aid wellbeing and sovereignty over one’s own life.

3.4.4. Upstream engagement

An important strategy to enhance uptake is the attempt to move engagement further upstream. P8 elaborated on this reasoning behind upstream engagement. Gathering a variety of stakeholders (including policy-makers) is crucial for impact. P8 further detailed that the type of impact in mind concerns the effect on political goals, which he frames as “mission-oriented”.

I think the example also what P13 just gave about RRI... I mean, the tricky point from RRI and Open Science is of course that you involve policy-makers earlier in a process than you normally have. This can happen in different degrees. You can have a radical case in which for example citizens or/and stakeholders with their problem definitions are already part of the research process itself. This is what we now organise in Horizon Europe under the so-called ‘missions’. You will see a massive input of stakeholders and even citizens in defining what actually the research question is and what we should address. So, if you do

that then of course that's a radical case and as you maybe have sensed, I'm a radical. So, I like to pursue that route. Of course, that has the advantage that the problem definition itself is co-defined by stakeholders but this can be a long process. But at the same time, when successful then of course the influence on policy is also high. (P8, agriculture workshop)

The cited extract shows how the presented strategy responds to a perceived problem of low efficacy. The point here is that the reasons for low levels of efficacy of knowledge do not merely depend on the rights and wrongs of the knowledge at hand, but much more on the process of implementation. In other words, uptake depends on who is being engaged in the process and, importantly, if the participants had been integrated from early on, during agenda setting and planning. For P8 these are important preconditions of uptake in the policy domain. He goes on to acknowledge the inaccessibility of the policy domain. To counter this deficit, P8 favours the discussion of policy goals with a broad set of societal actors, stakeholders and policy-makers. Only then, the chances of uptake increase. Engagement early on, when problem definitions are made, is key for enhanced uptake and impact (of mission-oriented research). P5, too, emphasises the importance of engagement throughout the entire process. P3 makes clear that in his understanding such engagement takes on the form of a conversation that allows for mutual exchange.

3.4.5. Normativity

Over the course of the workshops, it became apparent that most of the participants felt committed to a particular policy agenda. Their commitment reflected the normative objectives related to the field in which they work. These include: action to counter climate change, the promotion of public health, and the advancement of sustainable food production. Many of the workshop participants did, however, not externalise these normative elements to policy-makers. On the contrary, they sought for ways in which the normative framing could be made an integrated dimension of their work. Rather than attributing responsibility for the definition of normative goals to policy-makers, they presented normative goals as constitutive elements of their work. P13, for example, takes a stand as a promoter of sustainability and social justice:

That was the project which was dealing with challenges and opportunities to make urban food systems with a specific focus on socially deprived areas in cities more sustainable and more socially just. (P13, interview)

This normative starting point is directly linked with the ambition to meet respective policy goals:

Okay. The goal, the overall goal was starting... The goals as I've told you to bring actors together who would have a slightly different view on how a sustainable food system would look like. That's the first thing, and how it could be fostered, brought forward. (P13, interview)

A similar position is presented by P11, and in an interview prior to the workshops, P8 declared the achievement of “societal desirable outcomes” as the normative objective of his work. Addressing social needs reveals the grounding in a normative agenda, intended to be useful for effective measures to deal with societal problems and its grand challenges.

In an interview, P11 explained that his work has a normative framing that is societal benefit and environmental protection. In his view, these values are somewhat reflected in European Framework

programmes. However, there are also constraints, grounded in the pro-growth mission of the EU. This is yet again a normative framing, but according to P11 one that is at odds with societal benefits.

Whether it will really influence the process, I'm quite sure that it is influencing much less than the business lobby is influencing. I'm too old to be naïve. What I see the EU is doing is following big business interest in the European Union. Not civil society interest, not the interest of the planet Earth or ecology. If you look at the Green Deal, if you look at the big EU policies, they are still talking about growth, economic growth, jobs, new jobs and so on. This is an old paradigm which they cannot leave behind. (P11, interview)

As important as a normative grounding is for collaborative engagement, it can be problematic if no consensus over the corresponding policy goals can be achieved. P17 continued to explain that there is a certain danger that policy relevant research might be diluted. He shared experiences gained while working on an urban traffic project. Even though the result was appealing, P17 saw the project as a “showcase” for policy-makers with elements of “window-dressing” rather than an example of substantial change towards sustainability. As P17 continued to explain, the mentioned project met quite some resistance from the local residents, which led him to state:

In a way what you're doing there is not co-designing a solution from the community's perspective and presenting that to the planners. You're packaging what the officialdom wants the community to buy into and using creative approaches to get them to be more amenable to it. So, it's a valid criticism, I think. I think there is the potential for these creative engagement approaches to be misused, if that's the right word. They can make people more amenable to the official agenda and official plans without really taking into consideration any local knowledge or concerns. (P17, interview)

Other workshop participants share their concern that the application of collaborative engagement might be compromised by existing funding schemes. Recent research programmes may be inscribed in societal benefits, but the definition of such would not challenge capitalist, state-dominated and elitist interests. Such criticism points to the danger that the ambition to promote sustainable change and social justice gets lost when operationalised in (European) funding programmes. Despite their tendency to de-politicise science, recent attempts would open up a space for important discussions on the politics of scientific knowledge production where domination, discrimination, exclusion and exploitation would be addressed (e.g., P11, interview).

In conclusion, policy relevant research that follows a participatory approach has its point of departure in policy goals. Ideally, corresponding research agendas are collaboratively developed through upstream engagement of a broad scope of civil society actors, stakeholders and policy-makers. Geared towards a solution to jointly identified societal problems, this type of engagement seeks to produce effective knowledge and its realisation. The implementation of research outcomes is viewed to be decisive for effective change.

3.5. Summary

The presented analysis of our data brings to light three approaches of knowledge integration in the policy domain. These three approaches are:

- a) the supply of political elites with scientific expertise,

- b) the public deliberation of societal challenges, and
- c) the engagement of civil society actors, researchers and policy-makers in policy processes.

These three approaches differ in the ways in which policy processes are to be endowed with knowledge. Each strategy corresponds with a respective policy model: a) corresponds with representative democracy, b) with deliberative democracy, and c) with participatory democracy. Furthermore, there are three different policy arenas. For a) the prime arena is the parliament and similar assemblies (UN, WHO, city council, etc.); b) engages with deliberative arenas (consensus conferences, round tables, citizen juries, etc.); and c) seeks engagement with communities of practice including policy-makers. The described approaches also differ in relation to their expectation of how knowledge should contribute: a) expects the reception of scientific knowledge by decision-makers, b) expects to create a shared understanding across society and c) expects efficacy in achieving actual change.

As accordingly, different strategies are perceived to be suitable: a) favours communication (translation, policy briefs, direct communication, trust relationships, etc.) strategies which can be summarized as dissemination model; b) invites citizens to attend public deliberation processes, in such a way relevant knowledge should be brought to the table and publicly shared; c) seeks to produce effective knowledge needed to act upon societal challenges and to bring about change; this is best achieved when a broad set of civil society actors and policy-makers are jointly engaged both in the creation and implementation of the relevant knowledge. It is important to note that such mission oriented, collaborative engagement differs from earlier forms of deliberation through its explicit normative grounding in agreed policy goals.

Policy model	Democracy model	Site	Role of knowledge	Expectation
A: linear model	Representative democracy	Parliament (assembly)	Provision of political elites	Reception
B: interactive model	Deliberative democracy	Deliberative arenas (agora)	Enhancement of reflexivity	Consensus
C: participatory model	Collaborative engagement	Communities of practice	Situated and communal foundation of action	Effectiveness

Table 2 - Three models of the science-policy interface

4. Findings (2): Building and maintaining the researcher-policy-maker relationship

4.1. Introduction: why study relationship-building?

In what follows, we focus on the ways in which policy-active researchers strategically develop and deploy relationships with policy-makers in an effort to influence representatives of the public, for example, in parliaments. Indeed, in representative democracies, the development of relationships and other channels of communication (among them policy briefs, academic publications, etc.) are indispensable to the uptake of research by policy makers, since in the respective policy model, parliaments and associated assemblies are the only places where policy-making happens. Gaining (physical) access to representatives is therefore essential to making a policy impact. We present in-depth evidence to elucidate the strategies of policy influence associated with representative democracy.

4.1.1. Studying relationships between researchers and policy-makers

The quality of relationships between researchers, policy-makers and (sometimes) intermediaries is a well-recognized research area. Based on a cursory analysis of the material presented here, it is evident that our participants view building and maintaining good relationships with policy-makers as key to making an impact on policy. However, the factors at play when building relationships are somewhat less well understood within the research landscape, even if the general findings corroborate the reviewed literature. For instance, based on a systematic review, Oliver et al. (2014) found that collaboration between researchers and policy-makers, along with developed relationships and skills, were the most frequently reported facilitators of research uptake. Collaboration (particularly in the long-term) and trust-formation between researchers and policy-makers may be hampered by the short-term nature of research projects, research employment contracts, and tenure in policy-making positions (Elliott and Popay 2000:467). The type of collaboration was also found to be important: upstream engagement, i.e., collaboration that starts already at the stage of knowledge production, was found to be desired by researchers and policy-makers alike (Choi et al. 2016).

Conversely, mutual mistrust between researchers and policy-makers has been described as a barrier to research uptake (Choi et al. 2005; Elliott and Popay 2000; Gold 2009; Gollust et al. 2017; Haynes et al. 2012). Gollust, Seymour, Pany, and Goss (2017) found evidence for mutual distrust—policy-makers question the credibility of research, and researchers question policy-makers' authentic desire to use evidence in decision-making. The two groups diverge on their assessments of the value of research in policy-making; negative judgements of the other's work corresponded with a high level of distrust for the other group. Researchers report that competing demands on their time (e.g., knowledge transfer is not featured in tenure/promotion criteria) hampers effective communication with policy-makers. Conversely, time constraints also keep policy-makers from engaging with research ("deluge of information"). In general, the literature suggests that the relationship between researchers and policy-makers is fraught with mutual mistrust, wherein both parties accuse the other side of vested interests (Gollust et al. 2017).

Academics are rarely represented in the networks of policy-makers (Oliver et al. 2017:122). Policy-makers' most frequent sources of information are local health experts, government websites and mid-level health service managers without any direct expertise in public health (Oliver et al. 2017). Policy-makers prefer opinion leaders; additionally, the latter tend to nominate each other as sources of information (as opposed to academics who are not central sources of information). Respondents said that they value researchers who

exhibit credibility in three core areas of trustworthiness: a) competence/reputation, b) integrity (faithful representation of research) and independence (more important to politicians), and c) benevolence/commitment (especially where policy directions have been decided). Trust is therefore critical. Taken together, these findings suggest that relationships, and with them trust and credibility, are key facilitators of research uptake in representative democracies.

4.1.2 Chapter overview

The present contribution scrutinizes their role and function of relationships between researchers and policy-makers, with particular attention to how relationships are formed, how they are sustained, and which other parameters are at play in constructing legitimacy and trust. Based on an in-depth analysis of our data, this contribution addresses the role of socio-demographic variables (race, gender, geography) and their impact on relationships with and access to policy-makers. In particular, it has been suggested that while some policy advice is invited, there is a sense in which some advocates follow their own agendas (which are frequently incongruous with those of policy-makers). Therefore, the role of congruence with policy goals in addition to academic reputation (and how this is formed/sustained) for trust formation will also be explored. This chapter thereby complements Chapter 3 by diving further into how relationships are formed between researchers and policy makers, which factors are decisive, and how that impinges upon research uptake, as well as Chapter 5, on equality of access and representation, which discusses the strategies policy-active researchers use to bring historically marginalized groups into the policy process. The line of argument presented in what follows suggests that researchers are not exempt from historical and cultural marginalization themselves, which has a discernible impact on their chances at influencing policy. The strategies used to build relationships with policy-makers and to make an impact in policy-making provide ample evidence. In the same vein, the concept of RRI, designed to reorient the entire research and innovation process along normative dimensions (e.g., the provision of public goods), can be interpreted as a means of strategic relationship building. In this way, RRI and associated methods such as participatory research design and co-creation can be viewed as strategic means to overcome a more profound marginalization experienced by many academics, either based on their ethnicity, their gender, or their epistemic allegiance. By (re)interpreting the entire research process in normative terms, some hope to turn their (relatively) marginalized position into a strategic advantage.

4.2. The strategic importance of (personal) relationships

4.2.1 Building relationships between researchers and policy-makers

To begin with, consider the following excerpt on the importance of developing relationships with policy-makers:

Sometimes people refer to them as partnerships, but I use the word relationships because it is individuals you're connecting with and it is that trust you've built with individuals, those interpersonal relationships that can really be useful when you're trying to accelerate action and drive a policy agenda. (P15, climate workshop)

The above excerpt well supports our general claim—that relationships with policy-makers are fundamental in research uptake and that these are concrete, interpersonal relationships, not (only) relationships between organisations. According to P15, interpersonal relationships can be “useful” when driving an agenda. Indeed, the quality of relationships with policy-makers and (sometimes) intermediaries is a well-recognized research area within the literature. For example, based on a systematic review, Oliver et al. (2014) found that

collaboration between researchers and policy-makers, along with improved relationships and skills were the most frequently reported facilitators of research uptake. Collaboration and trust-formation may be hampered by the short-term nature of research work (Elliott and Popay 2000, 467). Why does the quality of relationships come up so frequently when it comes to research uptake? The following excerpt speaks to the potential impact of OS. By dismissing the importance of Open Access (OA) to scientific literature for having a policy impact, P1 also explained why developing personal relationships with policy-makers might be important (while explaining why OS impact might be limited):

They're not going to read that stuff. What is important to them is the translation step between stuff being published in academic journals, whether that's Open Access or not. That translation step needs to show the relevance to their work and that's why I think over the past two years, I've written three times as many policy briefs as I've written academic journal articles. Not because they're shorter and easier to write but because I think that's where I can have [the] most impact. [...] most people would get their information from either presentations that I or co-authors give at policy forums or... (P1, interview)

Why is developing relationships (and the quality thereof) important? In the first instance, because policy-makers don't read academic publications (whether OA or otherwise), which puts all the burden regarding impact on processes of translation. The most impact is to be had through writing policy briefs, not academic papers, as P1 explains. Policy-makers' skills in terms of the ability to find and make sense of evidence are frequently found to be a facilitator of research uptake (Cambon et al. 2017; Oliver et al. 2014). Conversely, a lack of these skills is often bemoaned as an ostensive barrier to uptake. Policy-makers frequently struggle with knowledge management and a lack of skills to appraise research (Ellen et al. 2011; Head 2015), in addition to a lack of equipment or financial resources, knowledge, attitudes, and skills to utilize research (Ellen et al. 2011). As the above excerpt explains, however, an important explanatory factor for why policy-makers do not tend to read academic publications is that they don't need to in order to do their jobs; as P1 explained, academic papers usually provide an amount of detail and argumentative rigour that is not needed for policy work. In fact, policy-makers' needs were frequently reported to be ill-attuned to what research can offer (Abekah-Nkrumah et al. 2018). Our policy-active researchers also spoke to the inherent limits of book knowledge: "Many things you can't learn from articles or books, but when you talk to people who work and who come across problems and then speak about them" (P2, interview). Many aspects of policy processes, but also of concrete policy problems, are not processed in writing. Researchers wishing to learn about current problems have to find a way to interact with policy-makers. The role of book knowledge introduces an important material reason for the development of (interpersonal) relationships, as this suggests that there are aspects of the policy process that are beyond the reach of formalized reporting. What remains unclear, at least from the above excerpt, is the type of information in question, but the important passage of the excerpt (the last sentence) suggests that this information pertains to many things, including problem definitions and information only someone working with stakeholders on specific problems would have. Apart from the important task of translating research results for policy-makers, then, a fundamental aspect of building personal relationships pertains to the role of tacit knowledge in the policy process. Not all relevant information is available in writing, either to policy-active researchers or policy-makers. This sort of tacit information can pertain to different aspects of the science-policy interface. In the next excerpt, P5 is talking about the role of collaboration in educating policy-makers:

That's what we've been doing. We've actually collected most of the data, done the modelling, and then in so doing we also invite comments from all the various stakeholders, having regular workshops with them, and then now once we've now done the modelling then we now go back, now the final workshop to actually validate the model with all the stakeholders. (P5, interview)

Involving stakeholders and policy-makers in data modelling is expected to help them better understand the kinds of assumptions that go into academic work and that are rarely explicitly reported in publications (because they are assumed to be general knowledge within a discipline). So, tacit knowledge can be an important motivation for engagement with policy-makers, and it seems to work bilaterally:

One of the major challenges we find is that if you do the research without involving these major stakeholders, even the policy-makers themselves, you might realise that there are some salient issues that they have in mind that you're not taking into consideration. When you come to the implementation, they ask the question, why didn't you include this, why not that, why not this, why not that. But if you capture all that at the very beginning right through in the whole process then when it comes to implementation, all the various questions, all what they have in mind would have been asked to actually facilitate implementation. (P5, interview)

The above excerpt suggests an additional, more technical role for frequent interactions: to improve policy outcomes as frequent interaction ensures familiarity with aspects of problems that otherwise remain hidden from written interaction. There are then definitive advantages to developing personal relationships, not least of which is the possibility to stand out from the crowd. As the next excerpt about submission to an open consultation explains:

Now, just submitting something is one thing. Probably a thousand people submit something but this is also about developing a personal relationship. Often, I think in many cases, whether that's [one organization or another], it is because of personal connections. They don't have to be decades old, that helps, but the person in [the organisation] I first met just before [the COVID-19 pandemic] at a meeting. (P1, interview)

The next excerpt speaks to some advantages associated with personal relationships. The participant explains how “showing up” to relevant meetings eventually proved highly effective in terms of engagement. The excerpt hints at an important concept to be discussed in depth later: the idea that for research to have an impact, it needs to align with political aims (this participant spoke of “political will [or] interest”). While the excerpt refers, first and foremost, to consistent and constant interaction (“showing up”), there is also a conversational element to consistency, and that means bringing in the media to ensure that a given issue (the object of the research) is present and is being talked about. The media thereby become important policy actors as they can help to build pressure on policy-makers:

The first when we were initially working there, we wanted to use a top-down approach because we felt that it would be a way to really speed up the way that we were moving in the sub-national level. We approached the [...] water governance entity but that didn't go anywhere. So, we started working more closely with the regional government authority head, and a lot of them changed over the years that we were working there because we had elections and various people were reassigned. The process wasn't very systematic but we showed up, we ensured that we were consistently talking to different

line agencies and then eventually, I guess it was just political will or interest of the chief minister, the sub-national government agencies lead that decided this work on the [river] is of importance. I think there was some pressure from the top. I think [a political figure] wanted to see more environmental things taking place. It was also good that we were working very closely with [the] media. Water quality issues became something that was consistently talked about, so when the agencies were put on the spot by reporters, asked about what are you doing about water quality, they felt they needed to take action. I guess, it's carrot and stick measures, not really systematic processes. The power was very much in the hands of the chief minister of the regional government, so it just happened that relationships over time there was political will and interest to take action. (P9, interview)

The following excerpt speaks to the matter of consistency in developing relationships as well, in particular with respect to knowledge brokering. This participant speaks to the importance of consistent relationship building which, in their interpretation, is at the beginning of a group or organization becoming institutionalized in the policy process. Importantly, becoming established as a knowledge broker in this way entails that the organization in question is on record with policy-makers somewhere as an organization that should be consulted:

And then you realise that when you have an organisation like [ours], what happens is that because you do this over and over, you then start developing relationships with policy-makers and you become what I call institutionalised in the policy-making process. That institutionalisation doesn't mean, for example, now I can tell you that [organization branch is] institutionalised within the [conference] which happens every year. So, it doesn't require [me] to be there even though I'm the one who started it, but I start the process of [regional] Minister of Environment meeting every year to discuss priorities of environment for [the region]. They have on record that [our organization] is an organisation that has things to contribute on this topic. (P12, interview)

Frequent interaction can go a long way to building personal relationships which can then be leveraged, but there is still a strategic element to it, in that researchers who wish to influence policy need to pick their spot:

So, in the long run you could say the original aim was not fulfilled. That was not completely fulfilled, that's not right as well because just having those people in a series of interactions during a certain time period, of course, each person was engaged and the relationship between those persons changes as well. So, now we have food activists who would know someone, persons who to approach at the city council if they would like to talk to someone. And the person would not say no immediately by receiving an email from that person because he would remember, yes, I've been working with you, we had a nice atmosphere. (P13, interview)

This is not specifically about researchers, but about other stakeholders as well. The important point here is the role of sustained interaction with policy-makers (at the local level, in this instance), which means that stakeholders improve their position with respect to policy-makers through interaction over extended periods of time—as has been evident from the literature reviewed for D5.1 (Reichmann et al. 2020), however, this can be difficult due to the fixed-term nature of research (and policy-making insofar as the latter depends on election cycles). Contrary to the above example, this means personal interaction between concrete stakeholders and concrete policy-makers, not between institutional stakeholders (organizations) and policy-

makers. Depending on the level, there are different strategies that stakeholders rely on, depending on the possibilities regarding sustained personal interaction.

4.2.3 Developing and sustaining relationships with policy makers

Apart from providing the science, there is a need for dedicated knowledge brokering. This means that over time, organisations will develop ingrained relationships with policy-makers; institutionalisation here means that the relationships become abstracted from the particular individual actors (see, for example, the excerpt from P12 cited previously) and become more attached to the organisation and its reputation. The next excerpt speaks to the nature of the relationship with policy-makers:

The other side of lobbying is just to show, especially in terms of climate change and the catastrophe, because what we are facing right now is not only climate change but the results of it and the state of really global catastrophe which is really [what] we are facing in that very moment. So, if we see that from that perspective, we can see that what we are doing with the politicians is education. We are showing them why this specific thing should be changed or, for example, that specific goal should be increased and what will happen if we will do it, but what will happen if we will not do that. (P6, interview)

In the above excerpt, lobbying is recast as a form of education for policy-makers. This is interesting in the sense that all knowledge transfer can be regarded as a form of education, and it could also be regarded as a form of lobbying, even though not all our participants see themselves as educators or lobbyists. This explains why policy-makers are the primary targets of this sort of activity. P6 spoke to that further, explaining how efforts to educate mostly target decision-makers, which in this instance are parliamentarians:

I think most important are the members of the Parliament because they are the people who vote for the specific legislations. Right now, [...] it's again the members of the Parliament who are hit in the very first. Of course, they work in the different commissions and here like [commissions] as well. So, there's a lot of different institutions but mostly if it comes to specific rules, it's members of the Parliament. (P6, interview)

Parliamentarians' work is usually not restricted to certain topics. As we learned from building a sample of policy-makers in Task 5.2 (reported as D5.2: Uptake of Open Science in Information Seeking Practices in Policy-making (see Correia et al. 2021 (forthcoming))), parliamentarians are usually active in more than one policy agenda, as evidenced by memberships in multiple commissions. Given that the time of policy-makers is limited, then, getting access to decision-makers can become competitive, i.e., lead to competition between organizations or individuals wishing to influence policy-making, regardless of whether their agendas overlap. To be sure, the problem of competition for policy-makers' time is particularly salient where agendas are at odds, for example between research and business, or CSOs and business, but as the participant in the following excerpt explains, competition is frequently about ideas and concepts, i.e., about the intellectual tools needed to make a policy impact. Unfortunately, some stakeholders appear to be in it for the sole purpose of gaining influence, which is beginning to take its toll on the time policy-makers have available to talk to researchers. The power dynamics involved therefore lead to additional strain on policy-makers' time:

I wouldn't say big business but there's a lot of money in it and that means there are those who are very keen to listen to what others are doing but not share. What we notice is that there's quite a bit of competition and not always in a friendly way for ideas and we are concerned... and this is basically, we've learned from experience that we have to be careful, always showing all our cards before we can actually benefit. To me, I find that

really annoying. [...] These new power dynamics that getting access to high-level policy-makers or government ministers and so on suddenly becomes a competitive issue. I really don't like to play that game but if we have to then we will. But that also means that we have to be a little bit more careful about who we share information with. (P1, interview)

“Playing the game”, as the above participant chooses to frame their interaction with policy-makers, now frequently involves controlling for the content of the relationships that do develop, because the relationship between stakeholders is increasingly one of power and the desire to acquire more influence on the side of some stakeholders. To be sure, influence is what the above participant seeks, even though they frame their mission differently, as “solving a public policy problem”. When analysing the way our participants describe their relationships with policy-makers, then, their self-image (and that of other stakeholders) needs to be taken into account. The following excerpt speaks to the role of time in cultivating relationships with policy-makers. The relationships that policy-active researchers or organizations are eventually able to deploy are frequently long-standing relationships, as the next excerpt illustrates. Relationships that can be leveraged in the first place are elementary because the policy process is complex, and oftentimes, decisions are made on a short notice (at least for outsiders). Relationships of trust are therefore important because they ensure that this sort of information comes to policy-active researchers. Of course, this is no guarantee, but without established relationships, there is no channel for this kind of information:

One was that we had strong relations with governments that had the ability to both influence and drive that policy action at the global level. It was not a brand-new relationship that we were going to as a civil society organisation but one that we had been cultivating for a while, so I think it's really important to have relationships that you can leverage for policy change, especially on a short notice. The second part of it is really having the evidence already there to back up and say that one of the examples we had in the policy language was making sure that women are included in decision-making, in all aspects of the COVID-19 response. [...] And then, the third part is really knowing the language of policy-makers and keeping it exactly simple enough so that it can be integrated into a large document that's getting drafted. I'd say it would be at least those three key ingredients. (P15, interview)

The other important piece of information from the above excerpt concerns what has been referred to as the congruence of scientific information and policy goals at hand (see Chapter 3), and being able to draw upon the right type of expertise at the right time. Above that, policy-active researchers also need to speak the language of policy-makers. The above excerpt thereby speaks to three distinct elements (“key ingredients”) of successful policy advice: timeliness, which comes with established relationships; congruence of research and policy goals; and speaking in the right language when presenting evidence. Relationships with policy-makers thereby act as a mediator; they influence how well all other elements (timeliness of research outputs, congruence, language) can be deployed. As has been stressed by many participants in our study, the development of relationships (and therefore of the ability to make an impact) takes time. Even when this happens, it is notoriously difficult to ascribe any impact to the quality of relationships or to the quality of information. As in a previous excerpt, the media often play an instrumental role in shifting policy goals. So, even where there is a long-term relationship with policy-makers, this is no guarantee for policy impact:

I count policy measures as a statement from agency officials when they're talking with us saying, this is an important issue. I think I would really like to see policy change as a policy document comes out or a law occurs, but that's really not how... it's not ideal and it just

doesn't work that way. I think we've been working there for seven years, even in the initial stages people talked about how important it is that we were doing that work. But it was just lip service and nothing happened. [...] After years and years of work and after many administrations, it was formally recognised. We also counted policy changed as when the stakeholders themselves start taking ownership of some of the activities that we would have done. (P9, interview)

The next participant was more drastic about the necessity of keeping up relationships with policy-makers and how politics play into that as well. The excerpt begins with a vocal endorsement of informal relationships. The reason that the participant specifies is very similar to what has been said above regarding timeliness; established relationships provide a degree of efficiency to interaction, which is rooted in established contacts and means of communication (names, email addresses, phone numbers). Where these are missing, contacts would have to be established in the first place, with trade-offs for efficiency. This sort of intimacy also has downsides, in particular for those “outside the loop”, as we learn from the following excerpt:

Yeah, I totally understand. I'm very familiar with this as a sociologist, with the benefit of having established relationships and having also informal relationships because they work fast and they work efficient. But [...] they tend to become secluded. How can you keep these relationships permeable, flexible? How can you safeguard that there's equal access? Because for those people who are not in this loop of relationships there is actually no possibility of access to the political system, into the political process. So, I think there is this, and this is probably also a general problem of our expert advice is, how do you know who the right experts are? Who do you give access to? (P14, interview)

The problem for policy-makers is finding the right experts to give access to, because for those not in the loop, being heard is excessively difficult. Besides, access is granted more readily to those experts that already share the political opinion of the policy-maker in question; consequently, this respondent calls for more permeability of these relationships. The issue of “finding the right experts” will occupy us further below where we resume discussing the importance of the congruence of research and policy goals. The influence of politics runs deeper still, as it is policy which oversees science, thus incentivizing certain modes of interaction:

So, I think again, there certainly are barriers and this issue of having those conversations with policy-making. I think one of the barriers is that policy oversees science thus incentivizing a certain model of science-policy interrelation and how science can be policy-relevant. (P3, interview)

The above excerpt is elementary because it suggests that the way relationships can be developed with policy-makers is largely determined by policy-makers, not least by determining the extent to which policy engagement is a precondition for funding (for instance). Of course, funding is not the only precondition for (successful) policy advice. The above excerpt does suggest, however, that it is policy-makers who incentivize a certain model of science-policy interaction, and researchers follow suit (if and when they wish to influence policy). The next excerpt speaks to the same problem, in particular where this participant laments that policy-makers request information but then “do what they want” with it. Paradoxically, having strong relationships with policy-makers where “everybody knows their place” is construed as providing the space for researchers to speak their mind in the first place, i.e., to represent unpopular opinions without fear of reprisals (P10, interview). On the other hand, academia in particular, but also research in general is organized hierarchically, with tangible effects on the ability to influence policy processes:

I happened to be research director for years and I absolutely experienced this change of how I can influence things and how people above the hierarchy or below the hierarchy taking seriously more what I say than before—which was funny for me, because I am the same person, I'm saying the same things but from a different position. Now they listen to me. (P11, agriculture workshop)

This seems particularly important, not so much for individual researchers wishing to influence policy (since moving through any hierarchy takes time), but rather for policy-active research organisations in terms of nominating researchers to talk to policy-makers. The next excerpt suggests that the position is actually used as a proxy for competence:

I wonder also sometimes with your official position in the structure, I'm sure that to be scientific director helps to discuss with the policy-maker than when you're just at the beginning of your career. I think it's not just a question of skills, but it's also a question of position perhaps. (P10, agriculture workshop)

The above excerpt relates to P11's statement about the way a researcher's position in the (academic) hierarchy reflects back on their being perceived as trustworthy. The perception of competence is mediated by seniority; individual skills are usually not apparent to policy-makers, but what they can see is the (official) position and the seniority level (academic age and merits) of a researcher. On the other hand, public administrations are not homogeneous either, as pointed out in the following excerpt:

It's often, as I said, public administrations are not so homogenous either. Also barriers of interests [...] so it's sometimes possible to collaborate very well and close to policy with certain people in the administration but then you have the problems where they have the problems [...] There are problems of [...] forms of collaboration [which are] very often organis[ed as] projects which means that there is a certain dynamic also of continuity, for example. So, there are many ways of how this collaboration of science and policy [...] science in the policy is organised which makes it difficult to have an impact within certain critical problems. There's probably a lot of influence from traditional science. (P3, interview)

Heterogeneity accounts for multiple possible forms of collaboration between science and policy and relates to keeping social relationships permeable, as P14 (above) pointed out as well. The biggest issue with keeping up relationships seems to be continuity of (research) funding and policy cycles. Lack of continuity in research funding which is usually only given in the short-term hampers the development of relationships and puts a lid on efforts to establish continuity in interaction, not least because—as the next excerpt explains—researchers are a highly mobile group, but policy-makers are not. In terms of understanding relationship formation between researchers and policy-makers, then, there is a need to look especially to those cases:

But those relationships that you built with stakeholders or policy-makers are lost because you have no funding and you have no interest in continuous engagement. I think also, it's not only that maybe policy-makers don't always pick up our ideas but also the system is not... in a way it's not good. It was kind of short-term project funding and you switch from one project in China to another project in Romania and in two years you do a project in Germany. There's no continuity of relationships. (P4, interview)

As we have seen, the quality of relationships is key when it comes to policy impact, along with congruence of policy goals and research results and speaking the same language. So far, these findings have not taught us much about the way(s) science (or an individual's status as a scientist or an organisation's status as a research organisation) figures in building relationships with and exerting influence on policy-makers. We have seen how other parameters such as proximity and continuity, but also sociodemographic variables such as (academic) age or seniority impact upon relationships. We turn to the role of academic reputation in policy advice and academia's role in bestowing legitimacy next.

4.2.4 The construction of credibility

So far, we have seen how maintaining relationships with policy-makers is elementary for making a policy impact. Having seen what it means to be close to policy-makers, we now turn to the role of being perceived as academics or researchers in policy advice by discussing a case of successfully harnessing the legitimacy of academia to produce credibility, and cases where legitimacy breaks down, for various reasons. For some participants, in particular, working in academia is an agent of credibility:

The other thing I should say is also I do feel strongly about having at least one foot in academia. I could work for a consultancy and just keep doing the same thing and that's another way of having impact. But I feel quite comfortable having that one leg in academia and that one leg in the policy sphere. (P1, interview)

The above excerpt describes other policy-active agents such as consultancies, which in the context of policy-making have goals that are similar to those of policy-active researchers. In an important sense, then, doing policy advice in either of these two roles can be construed as similar as well. However, "having at least one foot in academia" comes with the added bonus that academia is (frequently) perceived as the locus of legitimate knowledge; therefore, working in academia means that the legitimacy "rubs off" onto policy advice from academics as well, an advantage that is difficult to harness from any place outside of academia. Of course, those participants who were open about this were then (mostly) quick to say that this is not the only reason they remained in academia:

Yes... I wouldn't say that's the reason I want to be involved in academia but of course it is important. I think without legitimacy in the form of publications or being involved in high-level research assessment activities like the [high-level expert body], I think that certainly helps. I think it rubs off on my policy advice but also that of colleagues and of the institute as a whole. I think that is important. But I think that's more of an additional benefit than that it's the purpose of being involved in a community. I'm not writing papers just so that I can keep up my legitimacy ranking or whatever it is. (P1, interview)

Remaining grounded in academia, then, is construed as intrinsically desirable, while the added credibility to one's own positions is construed as an added bonus. The same is true for other high-level (and thereby highly visible) activities such as research assessment. Importantly, legitimacy and credibility are functions of social positions (in terms of gender, age, seniority, etc., and not just academic standing). Consider the following excerpt on the role of gender and age:

Our impact is going to be different because of who we are and thus on a greater level where performance indicators and all of these are based on all the accomplishments that you've done, but some things you're not able to because of the realm that you're in and the body that you're in. (P9, interview)

For this participant, academic accolades—which are fundamental in bestowing legitimacy onto policy advice—are a function of broader social positions. Gender, age, and seniority all have an impact on the degree to which individuals will be able to gather accolades such as prestigious publications, positions, and prizes. The effects of gender, age, and position are thereby direct, in terms of influencing someone’s ability to talk to policy-makers, as well as indirect, in terms of affecting positioning within academia. As discussed above, P11 talked at length about the ways in which academia, and by extension academic policy advice, reflect and perpetuate geopolitical constellations as well as power relations and marginalization present in society at large:

These are mirroring our societies, how they are structured. The bigger power and social relations, social norms, what is routinized, what is normalised, what is expected or what is not expected ruled out. [...] At least these participative processes many times want to change these or influence these because they are the problem because they are creating the marginalised situations or they are creating all these issues we are struggling with and want to change. But this is not so much, of course, a neutral issue. So, I think science-policy interface, at the bottom line it’s a political issue. We should re-politicise this because this is a political activity and also an ethical/moral activity at the same time. This is many times denied and we are talking about it in a technocratic way, so to say that. [...] I was working [as a volunteer] for the [international organisation] for a science-policy interface for four years. These four years taught me a lot about how the colonial history of the world is still well and alive. Those researchers who were working with me at the same level, same position, but of course of their historical background coming from countries which ruled the world and colonise the world, they could influence global processes much more because their diplomats were influencing much more. I mean, this is a very complex issue but I could face to this situation that my word, even if I’m in the same position formally is not listened to. Of course, this is the same for many people because we are coming from [the] periphery. If you are coming from, for example [the] UK, you are the ruler of the world as a scientist in a global science-policy interface process and from the US also. Also, the scientific credentials—so, if you are not, so to say, top scientists in quantitative terms then you are taken more seriously even though if others are saying different things and debating what you say. In a sense, it’s interesting to experience that not the arguments count sometimes in global science-policy interfaces, but who says, who says something. (P11, agriculture workshop)

This excerpt is rich in information and background knowledge. Especially at the level of global institutions, there is a sense in which the colonial history of the world is still very much a force mediating the (power) relations between countries. This is particularly striking since P11 describes how colonialism is at play even where individuals (or countries) are formally equals; this mechanism even tends to override academic credentials (in terms of e.g., publications and other quantitative performance indicators). The first part of the excerpt discusses ways in which academia mirrors social relations (e.g., of power), and concludes that as a consequence, the science-policy interface is inherently political, i.e., defined by power relations. The participant thereby denies the view that policy advice can be construed as a linear (“technocratic”) process. At the science-policy interface, it is “not the arguments that count”, but rather who is talking, from what position. Legitimacy is thereby construed, at least in the above excerpts, as an effect of social position, which in some instances exhibits characteristics of a network effect where the position of a researcher within a network (position, university, country) is decisive. In particular, the above excerpt stresses the effects of

global positioning and the role of global diplomacy in influencing the chances of researchers to be heard. This raises serious questions about the role of privilege in policy advice. The next excerpt comes from a policy-active researcher who also mentors younger colleagues, talking about their own position of relative privilege:

If I were some unknown researcher doing exactly the same work I'm doing now in some provincial university in [a peripheral country], I obviously would not have that same kind of access. Is that fair? Probably not. Is there something I can do about? No. I don't know. It's not something I think about a lot. Of course, I benefit from it—not me personally, necessarily. I don't do this to benefit from it personally. I do this because I feel that whatever we've got to say is useful and benefits policy. So, in that sense I don't feel guilty about it. I don't know, if there are other approaches that are somehow fairer. [...] Like I said, I feel privileged and of course I use that privilege but I also realise it's difficult. It's sort of like you need to play the game in one way or another in order to be noticed. There are so many things that are part of that game. (P1, interview)

The above excerpt is especially telling for a number of reasons, because respondent P1 does start off by acknowledging their privilege, both in terms of academic position as well as institutional background and standing as an academic; this is then somewhat relativized by saying that they do it for the benefits of policy only, not for personal gain. The importance of “playing the game” is of huge interest to the present deliverable; policy advice works according to certain rules that benefit those in a position to follow those rules (a result that can be interpreted as a Matthew effect of sorts). Reputation, good research output, belonging to the right institution are all levers that can be used in “the game”. Seniority and associated confidence are a clear advantage in the opinion of this participant.

NGOs wishing to influence policy face a diverse set of challenges. This is particularly salient in what we would describe as a trade-off between maintaining diversity on the inside as well as maintaining an academic reputation. Both affect an institution's ability to engage with policy-makers, and both need to be understood as cases of building and maintaining relationships, as the following excerpt explains. In brief, it speaks to the difficulties that certain institutional actors face when trying to build and maintain meaningful relationships with policy-makers. Specifically, a large part of the problem stems from the social organisation of relationships with various groups—with activists, with research communities, and with policy-makers. This creates at least two challenges for institutional actors: given that building and maintaining these relationships takes a lot of resources, it can be difficult to build relationships with all these actors. Second, diversification of certain institutions (in particular non-governmental organizations (NGOs)) results in complex internal social structures which tends to negatively affect the institution's academic credentials as well:

There is sometimes a lack of credibility that's been expressed because we are an NGO, non-profit organisation. A lot of the established entities don't consider the work we do as rigorous as a result of the fact that we have such diverse teams. We have those that are academics and research experts to early career people to truly activists and those in the global health field that might not be as close to the research community. So, there is a lack of credit, there is a challenge to credibility, and we do struggle with being invited to the most influential academic tables. So, when commissions are being created by the Lancet, for example, we're often shortlisted. But then when the commissions are selected, we are not the ones that make the cut and that has a lot to do with, I think, this way of bringing everybody into your research, the mindset isn't quite there yet to say that that's the best research. We even find that within our team, when they're first forming, there

are people that say 'Well, wouldn't it be better if we cite our academic affiliation instead of the [organisational] affiliation because then it'll look like more legitimate research.' For us, it's like a double-edged sword. We want the credibility and we want the evidence to be out there but we want it to be credited to [organisation] and showing how movements are really creating knowledge that's important. But we face that mindset. (P15, health workshop)

An institution's reputation as (academically) credible creates double-binds that, according to P15, are tough to break in the current academic system, with a clear and sometimes destructive impact on their ability to form meaningful relationships with policy-makers. The first part of the above excerpt speaks her organisation's position as a non-profit organisation and how this impinges on its internal working arrangements and structures, and more particularly on the role played by scientists within that NGO. In particular, the management of multiple group memberships is described as a challenge in the above excerpt, which tends to impose barriers on diversity within institutions on pain of credibility trade-offs. On the other hand, there is a sense in which institutions are also under pressure to build an academic reputation to maintain their status as a credible partner. The above excerpt suggests severe trade-offs between those demands. In terms of relationship building, then, we can learn that relationships depend on group membership and regular interactions, the maintenance of which takes resources. The next section therefore focuses on the strategies used and the barriers faced by policy-active researchers when it comes to maintaining relationships with policy-makers. For NGOs specifically, a strategy that has proved effective is to bring in individuals and organisations from low- and middle-income countries (LMIC).

4.2.5 The quality of relationships with policy makers

Taken together, previous findings (as discussed in Reichmann et al. 2020, for instance) suggest that relationships, and with them trust and academic reputation, are key resources in research uptake and advocacy. As has been shown so far, policy-active researchers and organizations deploy them strategically where they want to influence policy. The following excerpts speak to the quality of the relationships, thereby illuminating the nature of the relationships between researchers and policy-makers, and the conditions under which our participants regard them as conducive to research uptake. An important aspect of relationship building is equity, as the following excerpt explains:

I know that I can say what I want to say and they know that they can say what they want to say. You have to be very confident to have this type of relationship between policy-making and researcher. It's not so easy to do that. To do that, it's exactly what you say. When you say how to practice and to have an equilibrate relationship. For example, when we produced the analysis for the European Parliament, it was clearly normative. They ask the question, we produce expertise, and after, they do what they want to do with that. I think to produce something else, you have to build a relationship, a strong relationship, to be sure that everybody knows his place and you can say what you want to say. (P10, interview)

In the above excerpt, the participant starts by describing the linear model of research uptake where researchers provide expertise and policy-makers choose how to use that expertise. The relationship is described as a one-way street where policy-makers ask and researchers give, with no way of influencing what comes after providing information. The second half of the above excerpt goes on to stress the importance of building strong relationships with policy-makers to ensure that researchers can speak freely and uninhibitedly. Indeed, as has been discussed above in the context of legitimacy, relations of power both

within and outside the science-policy interface are decisive for the formation of relationships, precisely in those cases where there are no established relationships to deploy. Where there is no trust, the next excerpt explains, this leaves a gap for mainstream (political) narratives and power to enter the science-policy interface:

My personal impression is the lower the policy level, the less awareness about how to use science is given, or research. At the national level, decisions are more likely to be legitimised by research studies and things like that even if it's not always the case. On the local level, my personal impression is that very much the local structure influences how policy-making is. So, it could be the case that if those who are in charge of making decisions have very established relationships to research organisations who they trust, then it's more likely that research results get into the policy field somehow. If there are no linkages and that also refers very much to personal linkages, if there are not then it's very much about power structures, about those mainstream narratives as a general political line of a certain party who is in charge of taking decision[s]. So, it makes a difference. If you have someone taking a decision on agricultural issues who is with the Conservative Party compared to someone who is with the Green Party. (P13, interview)

Developing personal relationships with policy-makers is therefore important for another reason: where there are no personal relationships, this leaves a gap for political opinions and narratives to influence decision-making to the disadvantage of scientific information. Another key aspect is the trade-off between interest ("stake" in an issue) and power where the relationship is often one of low power/high stakes versus high power/low stakes:

It's just basically this issue of whereby you have to make sure that all the different stakeholders' concerns, their interests, their perspectives, and also their relative power, because there may be some stakeholders, for example the policy-makers, they have very little interest but their power is very strong because without them there will be no uptake or they will not implement. But for the community, for the society, their power is very, very low but they have high interest because whatever will take place will be in their backyard. So, all these things you have to balance, not only on interest but the power as well and then try to see how you could engage them because if there's no interest, definitely no engagement. (P15, interview)

The trade-off between interest and power sometimes makes for very inequitable relationships at the science-policy interface because those with high interest have an incentive to present strong evidence, but have very little power to actually effect political change. Clearly, research uptake hinges not only on the (individual) chances of groups to be heard based on traits such as reputation, age, seniority, and gender, which impact the legitimacy with which they can speak, but also on the nature of relationships which then ensue, and where policy-makers, as per their position as decision-makers, are ultimately in a position of power relative to any other stakeholders. This leaves few mechanisms of impacting the policy process. We turn to one of them in the next section.

4.2.6 The strategic importance of congruence

4.2.6.1 Congruence of research and policy goals: It's a (mis)match!

We have seen how variables associated with individuals (reputation, age, gender) mediate their chances of influencing policy processes. We have also seen how the science-policy interface is further mediated by the quality of these relationships, i.e., whether they are equitable or not, and how interests and power create a trade-off. In what follows, we turn to another important mediator at the science-policy interface that has, in the first instance, been described as congruence ([see section 3.2](#)). As has been demonstrated in D5.1 (Reichmann et al. 2020), discrepancy between goals and values of academia and policy-making has been identified as one of the biggest barriers to research uptake. Turning the argument on its head, then, we suggest that congruence of policy goals and research findings is what explains cases of successful policy advice, and incongruence unsuccessful policy advice. In what follows, we show that congruence has at least two dimensions. The first relates to policy advice and has been discussed previously (section 3.2). In addition, however, congruence can be shown to be a mediating factor in relationship formation, especially where advice is sought from researchers who are expected to share the same values as the policy-makers in question. The same is true in cases where goals and values are incongruent, and where this is taken as explaining failures to influence policy. There is then a sense in which (lack of) congruence not only explains (lack of) uptake (section 3.2), but also acts as a mediating factor in relationship development. In this way, then, congruence (or the expectation of congruence on the part of policy-makers) is decisive when it comes to developing relationships with policy-makers. The following excerpt reflects on the essential tension between policy goals and research in terms of interest and power and how that impinges on the strategies of policy-active researchers:

There are two key issues of policy-making: power and interest. The policy-makers have the power but if they don't have interest in what we, the researchers, are doing with very little power, it won't go anywhere. For example, what P4 just said. She published a paper, Open Access, because that member of the Green Party has a political agenda, that's why they were now going out to look for data or whatever to back up their interest. That's why they eventually came up to her. But on the other hand, if P4 took that same paper and went to her and she had no interest about, there was no match between her political interests, she will be thrown away. So, that's how I look at it. That's why it's always good to do some sort of co-creation of knowledge with most of these policy-makers whereby you have to get the salient interest or whatever they want to do that was through their political agenda right from the beginning, and then see how you could include that in the scientific research and policy-making. (P5, climate workshop)

According to P5, it is the essential juxtaposition of power and interest that partly explains the appeal of co-creation as a method of engaging with policy-makers and revealing their political agenda. This is especially important to policy-active researchers as they are usually not the ones in power and therefore have to be very careful in finding out what policy-makers actually want so they can align their strategies. P1 spoke to the role of congruence when it comes to research uptake, suggesting a fundamental role for shared interest in relationship building (P1, interview). Conversely, it might indicate that where researchers (visibly) have an agenda of their own (whenever they are “advocates” of a certain issue or problem definition), this hampers their perception as “objective” and their chances of “being heard”. In this instance, when it comes to successful research uptake, this is due to congruent goals and values; and in the case of unsuccessful policy influence, this is due to a misalignment of goals and values. When looking at relationships, then, congruence

is especially pertinent in those cases where it is absent, i.e., where participants state a lack of congruence as a reason for failed uptake.

The next excerpt speaks to the salient position of policy agendas in the policy process. Crucially, congruence is described as a necessary (but not sufficient) condition for research uptake. Importantly, whether a relationship can be established depends, in the observation of this participant, on whether policy-makers hold the presented evidence to be compatible with their policy goals. This is especially pertinent since this participant clearly has been in a position where the evidence they had to offer was critical of certain dominant policy agendas, which is why, in their interpretation, no interaction was established with policy-makers. Conversely, where policy-makers perceived the position of an intermediary or research organization as “in line” with their own agenda, there was a lot more interaction and commissioning of research:

So, with this policy interaction, personally I always face a bit the challenge of that there is a policy agenda. The agenda is the thing which is on top and even scientific evidence, if it would not fit in the into the policy agenda or if the policy field could anticipate even that it might criticise the actual policy agenda, it's very difficult to get into interaction. I could tell you even for very concrete examples where we approach people from the city council, [and] follow-up activities [were] completely blocked. They did it in a very polite way, but they knew about the direction in which we would like to go and that was within I would say a very conservative political context. Too much left, so, no way. They're simply not open anymore in that regard. [...] If you go back to the, we call transition experiments, to those examples, the representatives from the city council would approach for studies, the University of Applied Sciences instead of us, for example, as they would like to make sure that the economic framing of whatever they would like to get provided is the right one, it might not be questioned. (P13, interview)

This is elementary in the sense that policy-makers clearly also perceive researchers as having a political agenda because policy-makers tend to anticipate criticisms to their political agenda. This is especially evident where this (perceived) agenda does not match those of policy-makers, causing researchers to be blocked from the process. This would imply, however, that in those cases where researchers are able to make an impact, this is also because of their expertise and the policy goals at hand are congruent in the sense already described in section 3.2. The next excerpt also speaks to this issue:

I mean, that's again a very easy conclusion. Biotech stuff... So, our studies were always very critically investigating green biotech applications which was perfectly in line with the policy at the time, with the government policy, the policy of the local government during that time. Well, if you go into the agricultural sector, our approach is more the alternative approach which is not in line with the current or with those in power in the agricultural sector. (P13, interview)

Another participant also spoke to policy congruence and which advice ends up getting heard. The following excerpt suggests that congruence is key in both successes and failures to generate policy impact:

I think it's that tension between [...] economic growth and development. A lot of the challenges people were putting forward were to stop a new development from occurring by understanding the existing pollution level and then showing that it's already above a threshold, air quality threshold that putting in fifty new homes plus all the infrastructure and traffic, that was going to get generated, that that was going to be damaging for the

environment and the community living there already. But then you've got that tension between the need or the desire to grow the city from the planners and the authority and the national policy of having more homes, because we're short of new builds or new homes with a push back from the community saying, 'Well, we don't want it here because of this.' It's which policy and which development goal takes precedence, I guess, and in that context, it was an annoyance that there was any challenge to that national goal to having x number of new homes within the city by a certain time period. (P17, interview)

The bottom line of much policy-making in late capitalism is often economic growth (job creation, etc.), and advice that is in line with this general aim has a bigger chance of getting heard. In fact, whichever advice is perceived as challenging existing policy goals is frequently silenced according to our participants. This entails that evidence is frequently cherry-picked to support a particular policy vision, opening multiple routes for how views that are incongruent with existing goals are excluded:

Also, I would say it's even not always an intentional thing. I would say like we are, they're socialised within something, within certain ideas of how our world needs to work, of our policy needs to work, and also about ideologies and worldviews as anybody of us. It is of course for them as well super difficult to leave that. If you would like to do something very innovative, you need to question the things the researcher is doing. Otherwise, it's not interesting for us. It might be interesting for someone else. But if you cannot critically question the things, you will not get forward in changing them. (P13, interview)

The comment about intentions is revealing as it means that which evidence is chosen might be beyond individual decisions of policy-makers. Indeed, as the next excerpt points out, the policy process is often characterized by inertia with respect to policy goals. It can take lots of dedication on the part of researchers to shift policy goals:

My ex-executive director [...] was always suggesting we sometimes need to keep repeating the same story to policy-makers before they start to get it and they embed it into their thinking. So, if you want to implement policy, I think sometimes the way science is always presenting the next innovation isn't necessarily the way you get to breakthroughs and change policy directions. We heard about that inertia in the policy process. I think that's a critical element. (P17, health workshop)

Congruence of policy goals and research results is then often the result of deliberate and long-term action by researchers to change policy makers' outlooks and problem definitions. In terms of engagement and impact, the repetition of key ideas of science/research is crucial, instead of jumping the bandwagon of innovation rhetoric. Whoever wishes to make an impact needs a long breath. Speaking from a place of intimate knowledge of a particular political culture, P14 was very explicit about the importance of congruence:

Coming from a country [...] which is highly politicised in each and every aspect of political domains or of entire domains, it's always that you choose the experts which share your opinion or which share your camp. So, it's not only through this expert advice or bringing experts into policy-making. [Policy advice] overlaps very strongly with political camps, with political interests. (P14, interview)

As P14 makes clear, experts are frequently chosen based on congruence of research aims with policy goals, which entails that there is considerable overlap between political camps and the kinds of experts policy-

makers are willing to listen to. As this participant further explains, this can even merge into corruption sometimes, which means that policy advice tends to become entrenched in political camps which tend not to be very permeable.

Duration of the relationship is also important when it comes to impact. The next excerpt reflects on this in relation to policy congruence, but casts the issue in terms of usefulness which suggests a linear model of research uptake:

Yeah, because I've been at it for such a long time, I think I'm in a fairly privileged situation where people either know me or my work or both. I do have relatively easy access to people because... I guess partly because of what you're saying is a certain respectability. Of course, that's only the first step. If you don't have nothing of use, nothing that's useful to say then next time the door won't open. (P1, interview)

The above excerpt also testifies to the fact that congruence with policy goals constitutes an important aspect of relationships, as reputation does not seem to be effective in and of itself. Another participant spoke to this issue in terms of the required political will: "I guess a political will amongst government actors. That's not only localised political change but also from a national level political change" (P9, interview). This is important in terms of convincing policy-makers, because most of the time measures seem to involve trade-offs (see P10, interview).

4.2.6.2 Challenges to congruence: Gender and the devaluation of "care work"

The term "care work" appeared in P13's discussion of how their work with communities (sometimes marginalized, sometimes not) at the municipal level is often devalued by decision-makers based on categorizing this sort of engagement as unscientific. In this context, "care work" refers to work (usually under- or unpaid) that pertains to the reproductive sphere in some way (e.g., parenting or taking care of elderly relatives). This type of work is frequently labelled as unproductive by the standard of capitalist market societies and is thereby devalued.² We shall dwell on care work here, both in the context of the impact of the label on policy congruence as well as the impact of gender at the science-policy interface:

I would link, I'd like to link up with what P11 has been saying because previously P10 was talking about her very privileged position of having time away to be dedicated to things which you would consider being relevant. Something which is quite interesting... the last years I've been also working on gender issues and gender in research organisations and something which is quite interesting is that type of research, participatory, transdisciplinary, action research, all those types of research which particularly those types of research which are dedicated to empowering marginalised groups are considered to be care work within the academic system, similar to all those teaching duties. This is the academically less acknowledged work which is interestingly carried out by specific groups of researchers often also linked to their gender. But it's a specific type [...] of researchers who are usually not the privileged and the powerful ones. So, this is also something I think it might be worth to have a look on if that would not reinforce inequalities of individuals within the research and innovation system as well or to do it or to take it the other way around, to make it as it was by P11 anyway, obligation of those who have the opportunity to take over such tasks as well. That's very often in this science-

² See ILO (2018) for a detailed discussion of care work and its economic significance.

civil society-interface, when it comes to the science-policy interface interestingly it seems to be different. There seems to be the reputation of consulting policy is a different one than carrying out community-based research with a specific focus on marginalised groups. That's just an observation. (P13, agriculture workshop)

Some parts of academia are generally less acknowledged, which is part of their being perceived as care work. Since this division between high- and low-status disciplines is also gendered, it seems that academia reinforces group divisions. This is especially pertinent to participants working with marginalized groups whose social position entails that the research is perceived as care work. This also translates to a differential perception of policy advice versus work with marginalized groups:

[...] market society is not prone to value care work because it seems not productive at the market. It's not marketable, it's not commodified, it's completely against commodity logic. It's a relational logic, and it has a different vision of society embodied in these activities. In that sense, again, back to the political visions which all these issues are raising and that's why I also feel that the Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation story should not lose these political messages. If I want to put it very straightly, we want to live in a different world. In a sense, we want to see that this care work in academia is appreciated and always in our society it is appreciated. (P11, agriculture workshop)

This excerpt is very important to understanding the fundamental role of policy congruence, as it suggests that taking certain kinds of work seriously involves an entirely different vision of society (system change). This is particularly true for care work as well as those parts of scientific research frequently likened to care work, such as community-based research. In that sense, misalignment of policy aims and research results can be construed relative to the dimension of system change versus system preservation—where researchers are perceived as closer to the system change pole, congruence of research results and policy goals becomes less likely (and vice versa). Of course, as the example of research on climate change and its resonance with the Green Party (discussed above) shows, where policy goals themselves can be construed as “system change”, alignment with such research positions becomes easier. The next excerpt speaks to policy-making as an ecosystem, a view that resonates well with the above concerns about congruence:

When we think of policy-makers, when we think of policy change, but it's an ecosystem of people that influence changes in policy or changes in the way that we think about the environment, changes in our understanding within certain situations. (P9, interview)

The metaphor of an ecosystem corroborates the thesis of policy congruence. If research uptake is conceived as a systemic issue, this helps to explain why there seems to be a systematic association of certain social positions and viewpoints with the ability to make an impact. As has been discussed in the previous section, the chances of making a policy impact depend on congruence with policy goals. We have seen how this form of alignment may be subject to dynamics of sexism. On another front, academic reputation is also gendered. As has been pointed out very succinctly by P11, that this should be so is hardly surprising given how academia reflects power dynamics of society at large: “Science is very problematic. It's colonialistic, it's gender-wise, racist in many senses, even unreflectively in that day-to-day activity” (P11, interview). The following excerpt speaks to the ways in which representation in policy-making is also sexist:

A lot of times it's these existing traditional norms that it must be the doctor, the chief medical officer, minister of health that leads a delegation and politically women are less

represented, so we know there's already existing societal drivers that put women in positions where they're less... (P15, health workshop)

As has been discussed so far, certain types of research are marginalized based on their perception as care work (which in turn is marginalized in capitalist societies). P13 spoke at length to her observation that when it comes to those parts of academia denounced as “care work”, it is frequently women doing that work. Participatory research is discussed as a primary example of the former by participants. But even where entire specialties tend to be marginalized, there is a sense in which legitimacy may be bestowed upon a marginalized field if only the right kind of people start to engage with a topic. Gender dynamics are also at play at an individual level though:

Our impact is going to be different because of who we are and thus on a greater level where performance indicators and all of these are based on all the accomplishments that you've done, but some things you're not able to because of the realm that you're in and the body that you're in. (P9, interview)

Intersectionality extends beyond the role of women, into the legitimacy of entire specialties because, as P13 pointed out, it is frequently women doing participatory research and engagement:

Just to respond to P13's point and also going back to [the facilitator's] question about the Matthew effect that in a way it has to be prominent Western scientists that take the tradition of leading—publishing a lot in this participatory research more gender type of work in order to pave the way for everyone else to be taken seriously in this area of work. (P9, agriculture workshop)

Marginalization based on gender is pervasive, which is more apparent to participants where they are disadvantaged based on their gender. P9 is very perceptive about the way metrics are gendered as well. Analysing the advantages of belonging to certain social strata when developing relationships with policy-makers, she said:

I think this really changes depending on the cultural context and even who you are as a... what shapes you, what is your social group. I know as a woman, a young woman that I cannot go on a one-on-one with a policymaker and have a chat about different policies or different aspects of the project. I know that colleagues of mine who are men, who are drinking buddies or people that we work with, they can have a lot more leverage in the way that I can't. I know that I have to change the way that I am, in interacting with all these different individuals, so that they see me in a different light. I have to be more polite; I have to be more feminine; I have to be more naïve so that I ask them questions instead of trying to be an expert. I think strategy-wise on an individual level, you really have to change who you are in order to have the best outcome for your project. (P9, interview)

The above excerpt is even more explicit about the ways belonging to certain social groups determines the kinds of interactions an individual is likely to sustain. P9 is describing emotional labour when she is talking about how she has to fulfil certain expectations regarding politeness.³ This can also be considered a part of care work. To be sure, P9 here refers to culture-specific constructions of gender. What makes this particularly insightful is that P9 compares her own experience as a woman working with policy-makers with that of her

³ See Arlie Hochschild's seminal book, *The Managed Heart* (1983) for a definition and detailed discussion of 'emotional labor'.

male colleagues in a similar cultural setting and (presumably) with a comparable ethnic background. In terms of making a policy impact, belonging to a social group can become a matter of strategic consideration, as becomes clear in the second half of the excerpt, where P9 describes strategies that she can use as a woman to influence policy-makers. This dynamic can even go so far as being perceived as threatening to male authority. In another excerpt (P9, agriculture workshop), the influence of sexism is even more pervasive as the gender dimension is described as directly impinging on the relationship between the two involved institutions, the government and a research organisation/knowledge broker. In the above example, we are faced with a culture where being proactive is deemed unfeminine, which in the above case meant that engagement with a government official (a person with a military background) was hampered by the fact that they felt that their authority was being undermined, even though there was a basic alignment of the two institutional actors.

While those directly affected spoke at length to the dynamics of exclusion that participatory approaches tend to face, other participants suspected that their devaluation (and the devaluation of anything labelled “care work”) described above is founded in market society (see e.g., P11’s lengthy statement above, P11, agriculture workshop). This is very important to understand the role of policy alignment, as it suggests that taking certain kinds of work (i.e., care work, both in academia and beyond) seriously involves an entirely different vision of society (system change). In that sense, misalignment of policy aims and research results can be construed relative to the dimension of system change versus system preservation—where researchers are perceived as closer to the system change pole, alignment becomes less likely (and vice versa).

4.2.7 Relationships and network effects

The position of researchers wishing to influence policy relative to other policy-active actors is decisive. An important aspect when building relationships with policy-makers is the number of collaborators one can deploy. This is suggestive of a network effect and explains why policy-active researchers frequently work for policy-active organisations and are not solely based in academia (at a university):

What I’m trying, and sometimes that works better than other times, is always to bring in colleagues so that first of all they see how it works and they also develop their own network. Of course, with colleagues you can be more effective than just on their own. The team that we have now with [our project], I think it goes particularly well. There’s a number of young colleagues who are very keen to, and think the same way, that we can’t just do research. (P1, interview)

While the above excerpt is about research institutions being inclusive with respect to early career researchers, it also suggests that there is an element of division of labour to making an impact. Bringing along colleagues in an act of supporting them to build their own networks also suggests a network effect in terms of policy impact (“with colleagues, you can be more effective than just on their own”)—the larger the number of (potential) collaborators, the more levers you have: “I think the biggest benefit I have is that I’ve been in this for a long time that I have a large network, I maintain that network and I recognise the value of it” (P1, interview). In the view of P12, this is precisely what is characteristic of an intermediary organisation:

I see this as a continuum that if you wish, in theory it can be characterised that you can have on one end really science-focused research organisation and on one side is a policy-focused organisation, which is actually the government and the government systems. So, [our organisation] would be an intermediary and even with it being an intermediary, there would be differences for example at the centre’s level depending on regional differences

but also differences on thematic issues. So, working with the tools which of course we do a lot is a knowledge brokering part because the data we use, normally we don't generate that data. But we transform that data to make meaning for policy-makers to take decisions in a certain way. So, it's not just knowledge brokering but it's also value addition to the knowledge and transformation. (P12, interview)

Knowledge brokering means working along the continuum from research to policy and using the tools of science (without necessarily producing scientific outputs) to develop e.g., policy briefs and communicate with policy-makers. Oftentimes, this happens through directly working on policies:

We have a project which we started with [a city government] which is initially to start to make the case for the city on the worsening air pollution situation of the city and have them respond to that through policy and measures. They requested us to support in terms of actually the development of the policy. What we do is actually constitute exactly what you are saying, a technical advisory team that's not just [our organisation]. [Our organisation] can convene that with the city government but that draws upon all the knowledge and the expertise and agencies that work on different aspects of air pollution, on waste management, on energy, on transport, and housing and things like that. (P12, interview)

Knowledge brokering comes in degrees, from writing policy briefs to publishing academic papers to (participating in) writing policies, with each of these activities demanding different skills and sensibilities from researchers. The next excerpt also speaks to this issue:

The research I have been doing on health rarely was this close to policy. It was basic research and looking at the processes in terms of... depending on the research question, in terms of, how does assisted reproductive technology, how is this assisted reproductive technology regulated in [our country] and in different countries or how is genome transplantation regulated or what are the regulation processes, what do they look like. So, taking a qualitative sociological and historical perspective and looking at policy-making processes and asking the question in what way have people, or how was it? The same question as you are asking, equality and the possibility of access to policy-making processes, how was the decision-making process? (P14, interview)

This is interesting in terms of postulating a continuum of closeness to policy, where e.g., research in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) comes off as far removed because it tends to reflect on how these processes work instead of providing knowledge to feed into these processes. But then, what is the role of research in this process?

This team then developed the technical bit and of course they expected us to then go to support the development of policy—that's not the domain of the Parliamentarians. We brought in the legal team which has supported the work with the Parliamentarians so then provide the fast track of the policy. Now we're also working with them to develop the regulations—the law, the bill, and the regulation that will come with a bill. So then, the question becomes at what point do we stop as [our organisation]? We claim credit because through demonstrating the science behind the worsening situation on air pollution, we were able to get the attention of the policy-makers and they were able to respond to that and ask us to support them in terms of developing the policy. We've

supported them to the point that now we move from working with—we still work with the executives but we also now work directly with the Parliamentarians in terms of, of course, making them aware about the science, they need that fast, but also getting involved in actually the Parliamentary process as this developed. (P12, interview)

The above excerpt contains a distinction between parliamentarians and the people “making the policy”, i.e., those that the organisation is actually working with in policy development. One area where institutional actors are able to deploy a lot of influence is where public participation is low (even though required by law):

So, we had a workshop with the Parliamentarians and I think one of the things that I’m saying is we did the policy cycle. Typically, what you’re going through is a process where at the moment we have the public participation on the policy because that’s the requirement of the constitution and there would not be—I was talking to the clerk, the Parliamentary clerk, and if he goes through his experience on other processes. There is hardly any input by scientists on the public participation process. So, I think that take was like, it seems that scientists would like to come and have a workshop [...] and talk to us but actually really never pay attention to the fact that on a day-to-day basis there are things that have been developed [either at the] sub-county level in terms of legislation or at the national level that would require the public to have an input into that process. Scientists never have an input in that process. (P12, interview)

Finally, there is a geopolitical dimension to scientific policy advice which is particularly salient at the level of global institutions, where the power structures inscribed into the geopolitical order reflect colonial heritage. As discussed above, P11 talked at length about the ways in which academia, and by extension academic policy advice, reflects and perpetuates geopolitical constellations as well as power relations and marginalization present in society at large (P11, agriculture workshop). The science-policy interface is inherently political, i.e., defined by power relations, and thereby resists being construed as a linear (“technocratic”) process. In particular, P11 stressed the effects of global positioning and the role of global diplomacy in influencing the chances of researchers to be heard. There is then a centre-periphery dynamic at play in policy advice, where what is considered centre/periphery is not determined solely based on academic credentials, but also based on more fundamental geopolitical considerations. In terms of understanding the power dynamics at play, comparing the perceptions of privileged versus underprivileged actors is instructive:

Each stakeholder will come at it from a different angle, maybe politics is at play, their ethnic background, their gender—the way that they interact with the environment is going to differ significantly to us. That’s why I think it’s very important to merge these two different types of understandings, engage with diverse audiences and stakeholders so that the question that we design, the research that we design is able to have meaningful impact. (P9, interview)

The above excerpt summarizes the role of sociodemographics (gender, ethnicity, age) succinctly, stressing how each of these variables can affect the outcomes of participatory processes. The following excerpt reflects on how an advantage in terms of resources might translate into a reputational advantage and increased access to policy-makers:

I can see how, for example, having a translation unit at a university or having resources available to increase access and translation capacity does lead to some, maybe an

extension or another type of Matthew effect where the reputational extension isn't necessarily within academia but within policy. I think we do see that people, certain individuals and organisations who tend to have a certain advantage among policy-makers because they are able to build on non-merit-based advantages. (P1, climate workshop)

This excerpt is very insightful on a number of points: First, it speaks to the importance of skills when it comes to research translation which puts those institutions at an advantage that are able to afford dedicated “translation units” to support researchers with producing e.g., policy briefs. This is clearly not an aspect of individual academic reputation (even though there is an association between individual and institutional academic merits). P1 explicitly links those resources to an advantage that extends into the policy world. This can be interpreted as an instance of cumulative advantage, even though, as P1 acknowledges, this type of advantage is “non-merit-based”, as it depends on the resources of the institution, and not the individual’s merits as a research scientist.

4.2.8 RRI and the normative dimensions of relationship building

So far, we have discussed relationship building as a case of certain variables occurring together, and the various ways our participants make strategic use of their various social positions within academia and policy-making in order to influence the latter. The final section of this chapter looks at the quality of these strategic relationships to ask whether RRI and/or OS may be conceived as a formalized kind of relationship building. It has been suggested (P8) that the RRI concept constitutes a methodological innovation with the aim of a) bringing the normative aspects of the science-policy relationship to the fore and thereby b) freeing scientific policy advice from the odour of “lobbying”. In that interpretation, RRI constitutes a conscious attempt at cultivating, e.g., through employing participatory methods, the science-policy relationship. There are therefore two dimensions to relationship building, one referring to the skills needed which also covers socio-demographic attributes, and a strategic/methodological dimension. It is the latter dimension that the concept of RRI primarily intends to formalize as an intentional, strategic development of (certain) relationships with a normative underpinning. There are thus two levels to relationship work and maintenance, one referring to the normative framework and one referring to strategic deployment. It is the second plane which under certain circumstances can be construed as lobbying and where the reference to normative goals is expected to make a difference in perception and goal attainment. The following excerpt speaks to the connection between scientific rigour and inclusiveness, thereby giving a round summary of the aims of RRI. There, P9 points to an essential tension between traditional and participatory methods:

I wonder if anybody has ever spoken about the scientific rigor and its relation to inclusiveness and making sure that the voices of a lot of people are heard because in scientific rigor, we're supposed to have a representation of x number of people from these certain groups, etc., etc. Does that methodology ensure that the most number of people I feel there are included in the process of policy-making or the work that you're doing? I don't know, I think it would be quite interesting to reflect on that. There's a disconnect between what is required of us in science and what is required of us in trying to engage people from different and marginalised communities. (P9, interview)

This excerpt serves to corroborate the interpretation of RRI as a method for strategic engagement introduced above. P9 envisions a kind of research where the development and maintenance are constitutive of the method. Relative to this ideal, the current situation is problematic because there seems to be a tension between what is expected in terms of scientific rigour and the demands on engagement, where the latter is

constituted by the development of (meaningful) relationships with stakeholders. Effectively, the normative structure of policy agendas is what (often) seems to stand in the way of co-creative processes:

Maybe I can say something in regard to that because that links quite well with activities which they have implemented recently, which was about trying to bring RRI in practice in a specific context which was related to the food supply system in [our] city region. [...] So, it was people from policy, from civil society, from research, from enterprises coming together, going through a certain process in order to reflect on what research and innovation activities could help to improve the current state of the art. The aim was to come up with a co-created RRI project concept in that context. We were starting with the problem definition, trying to do exactly what was addressed right now, to leave a bit the mainstream path, try to think outside the box, and try to think about other types of problem definitions apart from what the current definition in line with the policy agenda would be. [...] The experimental setting helped to get the people on board to also engage policy people and to try to think in a different type of approach. But the problem was exactly with the policy agenda. The policy context in reality does not change with that. So, trying to come up with different ways of how to define the problem on the one hand, but on the other hand being embedded in this quite stable policy agenda context which is out there. In our case, it was even only a regional context. I'm not talking about any higher-level governance issues and still that's a super difficult thing because I'm wondering how to bring that from this small group of people, from those single participating policy actors back into the whole policy landscape where they are supposed to act then. (P13, agriculture workshop)

The normative dimensions of RRI are evident in the above excerpt precisely where they clash with the normative dimensions of policy-making. The participant describes a project context where the aim was to use co-creation to try and come up with a common problem definition (normative) that (ideally) would not be in line with the problem definition of associated policy agendas. Assuming that only (opposing) normative agendas can clash, then, this is strong evidence for a normative reading of the RRI concept and associated methods (e.g., co-creation) on the part of participants. Policy agendas are described by the participant as (normatively) stable, which means that the development of competing problem definitions runs up against considerable barriers. Of course, the above example might be considered a radical case where researchers and other stakeholders collaborate on problem definitions with policy-makers.

Yes, I think so. I think the example also what P13 just gave about RRI... I mean, the tricky point from RRI and Open Science is of course that you involve policy-makers earlier in a process than you normally have. This can happen in different degrees. You can have a radical case in which for example citizens or/and stakeholders with their problem definitions are already part of the research process itself. This is what we now organise in Horizon Europe under the so-called 'missions'. You will see a massive input of stakeholders and even citizens in defining what actually the research question is and what we should address. [...] Of course that has the advantage that the problem definition itself is co-defined by stakeholders but this can be a long process. But at the same time, when successful then of course the influence on policy is also high. But this presupposes an organisation on the side of public authority like the European Commission now is doing with a mission-oriented process. But you can have also other degrees. My first point was

actually in the beginning, does it fit the problem definition in the existing agenda. (P8, agriculture workshop)

The above excerpt points out that involving policy-makers right from the start, at the stage of problem definition, is still considered a radical idea, even if the effect of this approach on policy can be profound. But even from a radical position, the excerpt acknowledges that the fit with existing problem definitions is a fundamental factor in stakeholder involvement. RRI is also described as a way of doing research rooted in ethics:

I would call [myself] a proponent of a conscious science, conscious research, research that is, that is rooted in—sorry—morals and ethics, rooted in democracy. So, I would be a proponent of that. Since this is what I'm interested in, this is also the topic I'm doing research on. Since I'm taking a constructivist perspective, I'm interested also who we are, what we are, and how is this related in what we do? (P14, interview)

The above excerpt illustrates the way RRI is not only about adding a normative dimension to research, but rather about reorienting the entire enterprise along normative dimensions (e.g., democracy, transparency, etc.), with a profound impact on the way research-policy relationships can be built, as the above excerpts suggest. As the previous discussions of the various ways in which researchers are marginalized based on their gender, ethnicity, institutional affiliation and professional background has shown, (re)interpreting policy advice in roundly normative terms—instead of the more pervasive linear or instrumental models—can now be interpreted as a strategy for marginalized groups within academia to have policy impact. Participatory approaches resonate well with, not only marginalized groups outside of academia, but also marginalized groups within academia.

4.3 Conclusion: What drives relationship building with policy-makers?

Direct and indirect communication with policy-makers is most closely associated with linear models of the science-policy interface, with the associated policy arenas of parliaments and similar assemblies. Several conditions dictate the strategies deployed by policy-active researchers in attempts to make a policy impact. Importantly, attempting to exert direct (sometimes indirect) influence on policy-makers is only meaningful where representative democracy is the dominant model. In other contexts, different strategies apply (see Table 3 below and Table 4 in the next chapter). As has been shown already, participants in our sample were acutely aware of the different spheres and their respective logics, adjusting their strategies accordingly. As we have seen from the analyses presented above, academics may belong to marginalized groups of various kinds. Accordingly, the various strategies of engaging with policy-makers directly are leveraged by different social groups to very different degrees. Developing relationships with policy-makers as a way of influencing policy is most prominent among (but importantly not restricted to) male, white European researchers working in prestigious Western institutions (P1, P2, P3, P8, P10, P12, and P14 in our sample). Members of other demographics tend to find other strategies more useful. Our findings thereby add an important dimension to the literature touched upon in the introduction to this chapter. They suggest that while there is a sense in which developing direct, personal relationships, respectively novel forms of communication (other than academic publications) with policy-makers is fundamental for generating policy impact, this strategy is restricted to one (very particular) policy arena and predominantly researchers with particular demographic characteristics, though not exclusively. Researchers from other demographics pursue different

strategies. With respect to the representative democracy model, we learned that developing and sustaining relationships with policy-makers is important to have policy impact for various reasons.

- 1) A primary reason for developing personal relationships is the (perceived) opacity of policy processes and limited access to relevant information: Some information pertaining to either the content of policy agendas or the policy process is tacit; this means that it cannot be obtained from studying e.g., written documents. According to some participants, this is an important motivation for researchers to (attempt to) develop personal relationships with policy-makers. Clearly, this explanation pertains predominantly to representative democracies where policy processes are most closely associated with parliaments and similar assemblies (as we will see in Chapter 5, other strategies of mobilization sometimes attempt to bypass the traditional representative policy sphere altogether).
- 2) Participants operating in the arena of representative democracy stressed the fundamental importance of credibility and trust: Personal relationships are important because they help to foster trust and credibility. However, the opportunities for doing so are spread unequally across various groups within academia. The above entail that relationships with policy-makers are built and maintained strategically—to gain information and influence agendas and outcomes.
- 3) The strategies identified for deploying relationships differ across social groups within academia, according to age (seniority), ethnicity/cultural background, and professional background/academic subfield. This extends to the methods used for engagement, which can be variously perceived as policy influence (when the participatory methods pertain to policy-makers) or denounced as care work (when participation is extended to marginalized groups). Developing personal relationships with policy-makers (linear model) is therefore restricted to a small group of academics while those belonging to marginalized demographics tend to resort to other strategies (see Table 3 for details).
- 4) Academic background is an important aspect of demographics and group adherence when it comes to developing relationships with policy-makers. This is evident in what has been described above as congruence; policy-making is driven by an essential tension between interest and power (which is held by policy-makers). Cases of successful policy impact can be explained by appeal to the congruence of policy goals and research findings; congruence can be the result of years of work, but it can also be more organic. Within the (linear) representative democracy model, the chances of making a policy impact are higher for those who can offer a certain type of knowledge/academic background. This is most evident in the very different opportunities for (broadly speaking) STEM fields to influence policy-making as opposed to (many) SSH disciplines, with the exception of (perhaps) economics. In general, congruence is more likely where knowledge can be put to an instrumental use (see Weiss 1979 for a discussion of the instrumental model of research uptake).
- 5) Participants can be grouped according to their position (age, gender, background, prestige, etc.). The degree of individual awareness of dynamics of inclusion/exclusion and how they impinge upon the strategic use of relationships is a function of social position: Participants from marginalized groups within academia were more outspoken and analytical about dynamics of exclusion based on gender (P9, P10), social position (e.g., P5), or professional background (P11, P14).
- 6) The RRI concept (which most participants did not use themselves to describe their work) can then be deployed to analyse relationship formation as a strategic means to gain influence, where different groups have various strategies at their disposal. The main thrust here consists in a (re)interpretation of the entire research process in normative terms to justify stakeholder engagement and to move from forming personal relationships to a more emancipatory strategy.

Policy model	How is policy advice given?	Which social factors are relevant?	What is the role of knowledge?	Expectation for uptake
Linear models	One-way communication of scientific outputs, either through personal interaction with policy-makers or via policy briefs	Socio-demographic factors (age, ethnicity, gender, seniority, academic background) and how they affect (individual) credibility	Knowledge is provided to political elites who are free to proceed as they see fit	Reception of scientific knowledge by elite groups
Interactive models	Interaction between academia and policy-makers via informal and formal channels	Organisation of dialogue, including relevant actors	Enhancement of reflexivity, shared problem definitions	Emergence of a consensus (shared view) among involved groups
Participatory models	Multiple-stakeholder consultations; inclusion of non-academic forms of knowledge	Inclusion of societal groups besides policy-makers and researchers (sometimes marginalized)	Foundation of action (situated and communal)	Effectiveness of knowledge in the context of its creation

Table 3 - Democracy models and their associated modes of interaction

We therefore conclude that problems of access and representation occur early in the process of policy impact (not just when trying to include marginalized populations), and that the specific forms of relationship building are a strategic means to overcome these problems in a specific policy sphere. Some of our participants belong to marginalized populations (to varying degrees) within academia that deploy relationships strategically to gain influence in policy. Depending on their position, the strategies used—and the importance accorded to being inclusive—varies greatly. The theory of policy models and associated policy arenas and strategies developed in Chapter 3 thereby explains why some participants prefer to engage with policy-makers directly (via personal relationships, direct communication, and policy briefs) as well as the extent to which they do so. It also lays the groundwork for explaining the prevalence of alternative strategies of policy engagement. The next chapter develops an in-depth account of these strategies by distinguishing between a traditional academic approach to research (associated with linear policy models), from a multi-stakeholder approach (associated most closely interactive policy models), and a strongly participatory approach to research (associated with participatory policy models). The chapter discusses the second and third research approach as strategies of bringing the perspectives of marginalized populations into research and policy-making.

5. Findings (3): Fostering equality of access and representation

5.1. Introduction

Building on Chapters 3 and 4, which illuminate different approaches to the science-policy interface and ways of managing social relationships within it, this chapter turns to research design and methods in order to tease out the ways in which our participants do (or do not) work to foster equality of access and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making. This aim is premised upon our recognition that researchers who work at the science-policy interface act as gatekeepers as well as enablers for engagement in both processes. Further, when they disseminate results, they effectively represent those who have participated in their research to the broader public. Those who participated in *our* research are all engaged, to greater or lesser extents, in efforts to represent and grant access to those who have a stake in the outcome of their research and the policy-making process. We, therefore, asked them to reflect on which groups are (or are not) represented in or given access to their research process and work at the science-policy interface, and what they believe can be done to foster equality of access and representation in both spaces. We take a critical look at their work, through the accounts they shared with us, to examine which voices remain unheard and why.

In what follows, we first describe the three approaches to scientific knowledge production that we find among our participants and discuss their alignment with the three models of the science-policy interface that were articulated in Chapter 1. Then, we present the bulk of the relevant findings from this section of data, which speak to the ways in which our participants work to foster equality of access and representation both within their research teams and in terms of bringing marginalized groups into processes of knowledge production and policy-making. We then turn to the barriers and challenges that they face in doing this work before discussing these findings in relation to our research questions, teasing out their broader significance and implications, and then offering some concluding thoughts.

5.2. Approaches to scientific knowledge production and the science-policy interface

Three distinctly different approaches to scientific knowledge production and to the science-policy interface (as described in the introduction to this report, as well as in Chapters 3 and 4) are present among our participants. These include a *traditional academic approach*, a *multi-stakeholder approach*, and a *strongly participatory approach*⁴. With the traditional academic approach, research conducted by participants is done so primarily within academia and without the direct participation of stakeholders. These participants then interact directly with policy-makers in an effort to have their scientific expertise taken up in the policy-making process. With the multi-stakeholder approach, policy-makers and other relevant stakeholders are included in the research process, either throughout it or at various stages. Problems, questions, research methods and solutions are co-defined and therefore the views of their participants are captured within the research findings that they use in their attempts to influence policy-making. With the strongly participatory approach,

⁴ Here we draw on Allen's description of 'strongly participatory science', which is aimed at achieving 'knowledge justice' by being 'deeply participatory' through all phases of research, inclusive and relevant to those directly impacted by the problem at hand, and based on thoughtfully enacted participation of those people (Allen 2018).

research is co-created with diverse stakeholders, similar to the multi-stakeholder approach, however in this model the knowledge and situated expertise of impacted communities, often marginalized and vulnerable populations, not only sits alongside other stakeholders in collaboration but is centred. Therefore, the perspectives of impacted community members are centred in the policy recommendations that stem from the research.

To tease out the implications of these different approaches to knowledge produced for policy-making, and in terms of access and representation within both spaces, it is useful to revisit the triad of policy models presented in Chapter 1 and further developed in Chapters 3 and 4. As demonstrated in Table 4, there are correlations between a researcher's approach to knowledge production, the policy model they work with, and the site of the science-policy interface (where this work takes place). The traditional academic approach predominates in the linear model and is also expressed through the interactive model. In both cases, researchers and policy-makers are the actors involved and the site of the science-policy interface is predominantly parliament, but deliberative arenas may also be used (when researchers and policy-makers interact and collaborate). The multi-stakeholder approach typically manifests as the interactive model but can also be deployed in the linear model, when policy actors are not present within the constellation of stakeholders, or when research that results from this work is presented by researchers to policy-makers outside of the research setting. Therefore, deliberative arenas are the primary site of the science-policy interface when this approach is taken, however, parliament may also be a site. Finally, the strongly participatory approach manifests as the participatory model, but can also manifest as the interactive model and as the linear model, depending on who is present when policy recommendations are made. In this case, two sites serve as the science-policy interface: communities of practice⁵, wherein participants drawn from impacted communities manifest the co-produced knowledge and related practices, and deliberative arenas, where diverse stakeholders including policy-makers are part of the knowledge production process. Additionally, parliament may serve as a site of the science-policy interface when research findings are presented independently of the work done in collaboration with impacted community members and diverse stakeholders.

Approach to knowledge production	Characteristics of knowledge production	Actors in the S-P interface	Policy model(s)	Site(s)
Traditional academic	Created by researchers	Researchers & policy-makers	Linear and interactive	Parliament and deliberative arenas
Multi-stakeholder	Co-created by diverse stakeholders	Researchers, diverse experts & policy-makers	Interactive and linear	Deliberative arenas and parliament
Strongly participatory	Expertise of impacted communities is centred	Community members, researchers, diverse experts & policy-makers	Participatory, interactive and linear	Communities of practice, deliberative arenas and parliament

Table 4 – Relationship between approach to knowledge production and the science-policy interface

⁵ We refer here to communities of practice as defined by Wenger, McDermott, and Snyder (2002), which are formed of people who experience and care about the same problems and work together to understand them and implement practical solutions.

If we consider these different approaches and their implications, it is clear that access and representation, both within processes of knowledge production and policy-making, are at their most narrow and exclusive in the traditional academic approach, widened and diversified in the multi-stakeholder approach, and at their widest and most diversified in the strongly participatory approach. Further, this progression implies an increase in equity, from an inequitable situation in the traditional academic approach to an equitable one in the strongly participatory approach.

The differences between these three approaches have implications in terms of the extent to which our participants are interested in or able to work to foster equality of access and representation within processes of research and policy-making. Therefore, when it comes to describing our findings in terms of how research design and methods can be deployed to do so, our reporting will focus primarily on those who take multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory approaches. But first, we turn our attention to how our participants, regardless of their approach to knowledge production, work to foster equality of access and representation within their research teams.

5.3. Fostering equality of access and representation within research teams

Participants recognize that the diversity of their research teams has implications in terms of access and representation within knowledge production and policy-making. On the one hand, there is the diversity of the team itself and, and on the other, there is the diversity of thought that is brought to the table by people with different standpoints (in reference to standpoint epistemology as described by Harding (1986) and many others). Participants spoke to the roles that mentoring and support play (to younger colleagues and to those with fewer resources), and to the importance of sharing knowledge and skills with other researchers about how to work successfully at the science-policy interface.

P1 explained that he uses his privileged position of having access to high-level policy arenas, due to his reputation as an academic and experience as a policy-focused research scientist, to mentor junior colleagues within his project teams in order to help them develop their own networks with policy-makers to facilitate their access to this space.

...What I'm trying—and sometimes that works better than other times—is always to bring in colleagues so that, first of all, they see how it works and they also develop their own network. [...] I guess I've been sort of mentoring [junior colleagues] without necessarily using that word and who now feel quite comfortable reaching out to people on their own and understand how that may work or may not work. (P1, interview)

In a similar vein, P13 spoke to the importance of bringing together teams of “experts” (research scientists) to collaborate so that those with accrued experience working at the science-policy interface can share knowledge and skills with those who have less or no experience in this realm.

If you have peers who are already familiar with the science-policy interaction, there is a spill-over effect to those who are not. [...] This is something which is really effective in order to bring new insights for those who haven't been participating in policy-science interfaces before by simply getting a type of information on what it might mean, what it might bring, what kind of advantages/disadvantages if talking with peers. (P13, agriculture workshop)

In the same workshop, P15 spoke about the importance of mentorship and sharing of resources within diverse research teams.

We also try to pair someone that can give more time—I don't want to exactly use the word mentorship, but that's the best relationship we can say, that people are paired up with someone that is a bit more seasoned or has more time to support someone that is maybe less experienced and has less time. (P15, agriculture workshop)

Here, P1, P13 and P15 all emphasize that collaborating and sharing information within peer networks is an important way of teaching others how to interact successfully at the science-policy interface. In addition, P15 explained that her organization intentionally cultivates new networks in geographic areas where they don't have any, or where they are limited, in order to broaden access and representation within the context of her organization's work. She offered the example of having purposefully cultivated networks with Francophone communities because the network had been primarily English-speaking, and also of building networks in LMIC. Doing this work means that diverse networks are in place and can be tapped when her organization begins a new research project, or when her organization is invited to give policy advice.

P15 also spoke about the values that underwrite her organization's efforts to build diverse and inclusive research teams. For example, rather than expecting all named authors on a journal article to contribute equal time and effort, her organization takes other factors into account in taking an 'equitable' approach:

We do give a little bit more flexibility to policy-makers, we do give a bit more flexibility to people that might be coming from under-resourced environments and are from non-profits and all that, that just can't give as much time and saying, well, thought leadership itself is a form of contribution, is a form of knowledge. So, we do try to create research teams that are very diverse from background and experience. (P15, agriculture workshop)

Taking such an approach allows for the inclusion of people within her organization's research teams that would likely be excluded in other contexts. Putting this approach in feminist terms, P15 stated that her organization is consciously and purposefully pushing back against and resisting "patriarchal" institutional norms that interpellate (in the Althusserian sense (see Althusser 2001)) and reward individualism. Instead, she deploys a "gender transformative leadership" framework to foster values and practices of inclusiveness and collaboration.

So, from mentoring junior colleagues to sharing information and skills within networks of colleagues, to expanding the diversity of research teams by developing new networks and working with inclusive values rooted in a feminist approach, (some of) our participants are working to expand access and representation within their research teams and within the science policy-interface. Yet, we recognize that the work described here is not equal in its outcome. While mentoring junior colleagues and sharing skills with colleagues is certainly worthwhile, this work may not necessarily diversify the range of actors at the science-policy interface so much as it expands the number of people doing it. Reflecting a more radical approach, what P15 described evokes the feminist tradition of standpoint epistemology (see for example Collins 2015; Haraway 1988; Harding 1986) by intentionally broadening *and* diversifying the range of actors involved in the research and policy work conducted by her organization.

5.4. Fostering equality of access and representation through research design and methods

5.4.1. Introduction

Turning now to how our participants organize their work with research participants, we observe that a key way in which they work to foster equality of access and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making is to purposefully seek to include the perspectives of marginalized groups either directly, by involving them in multi-stakeholder or participatory research, or indirectly, by involving NGOs and community organizations that represent their interests. Many of our participants described how they design research to do this throughout the research process, from question setting to selecting research methods, gathering and analysing data, to activities of engagement with policy-makers and dissemination of research findings. They also speak to ethical issues that must be addressed when working with marginalized groups, the challenges that they experience when doing so, what tactics they use to overcome these, and what they do to ensure that participation bears benefits, both short-term and long-term, for the marginalized groups that they work with.

The definition of ‘marginalized’ that we use here is necessarily flexible and contextual, determined in large part by the research and policy topic, geographic location of the research, the local social structure and the particular forms of inequality that are present within it. Its usage and meaning, therefore, varies among our participants. However, a commonality in its usage is that it refers to groups that are historically left out in regards to policy-making—their views and experiences are not typically represented, nor are they typically given access to this process (nor to that of scientific knowledge production). The diversity of usage of the term by our participants captures groups whose interests are perceived as niche by policy-makers and they are therefore excluded from policy-making processes (P11 spoke to this in our agriculture workshop); vulnerable groups including the poorest members of a society and those living and working in precarious circumstances (who are therefore historically marginalized in terms of both research and policy-making); ethnic minorities and geographically isolated communities; and socially and economically disadvantaged groups.

5.4.2. Indirect representation versus direct access and representation

Indirect representation of marginalized groups is a common tactic among our participants who take a traditional academic approach and a multi-stakeholder approach to scientific knowledge production. This can manifest as a perceived default representation of marginalized groups when the research and policy in question represent the best interests of everyone (e.g., policies aimed at climate change mitigation or adaptation) or as the representation of them through the direct participation of NGOs and CSOs that are thought to represent the interests of marginalized groups. Speaking to the first point, P2 described the assumed general interest and its inherent flaws in an interview:

...I would mostly say that it's an assumed general public interest which then the question is... is that really the case or is it really representative? But yeah (long pause) I think it's a good question and one shouldn't be naïve. So, I think, to think about the social dimension of one's work is key and the assumption of general interest might be problematic. Also, I still think we should be able to talk about welfare and humanity, despite all the... But of course, I can't deny that I'm a white older guy living in Western Europe and all I could say is [I] try and be more reflexive and open also to all kinds of concerns that might come up.

But of course, the work that I've described is mostly taking part in academic circles, maybe with some exchanges with people from the policy-making world. But those are also not the general public and it's also kind of an elite world if you want to say. (P2, interview)

P3 also described the way that he aims to ensure that the views and interests of marginalized groups are represented within his research through the inclusion of NGOs in a multi-stakeholder approach, but also clarified that this constitutes representation and not participation. He explained:

...[What] we also try to do sometimes is to ask [NGOs partnered with us] in the research process and projects who is marginalised, who is not... who is silenced in this policy and research processes? For example, that's what we are trying to do in this one project here on the digitalisation of the electricity system and also you require certain resources of different kinds of people who participate and even if it's a publicly funded process it focuses on particular groups, economic interests and such. So there, research can also have the function to shed more light on those groups and perspectives and then it's not so much a question there of participation. (P3, interview)

In sum, indirect representation is both a common assumption and tactic among our participants who practice a traditional academic or a multi-stakeholder approach. Though they recognize its limits, participants, especially those who take a multi-stakeholder approach, frame the inclusion of NGOs and/or CSOs as an efficient and effective form of representation of marginalized people, their experiences and their views, within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making. Yet, they recognize that there are limits to this approach; particularly, while this approach may provide a degree of representation, that degree varies widely and may be contested. Whether or not the interests of marginalized stakeholder groups are accurately represented within the processes of knowledge production and policy-making remains an open question, because direct access and representation are not present.

On the other hand, all of our participants who take a strongly participatory approach to research design their projects to include direct access and representation of marginalized groups. In the examples that follow, our participants describe the forms that these take in their research and how their research design allows for them. Doing so requires certain ethical considerations that our participants address through research design and methods, which are exemplified in the passages that follow.

In an exemplar case, P17 described the types of marginalized groups that he involves in his research through direct participation and what their participation looks like. As he explains, the research is designed to centre the perspectives, experiences and knowledge of “vulnerable groups” in East African cities:

Okay, I've got a project looking at the issues of travel in East African cities. We're trying to understand journey needs and mobility needs for what we're calling vulnerable groups. By that, I mean people that are excluded in some way from the formal transport infrastructure, so that means, people from poorer households, informal settlements, children, and older people that might struggle with access, those with some kind of physical disability. Also, we're including in that a gender dimension, so looking at maybe women's mobility needs. We're doing a mixture of things in it. We're trying to, first of all, understand the needs of those types of users, the demands they might have for mobility, and the barriers or problems they experience around mobility in those cities. (P17, interview)

He continued, explaining how the problem definition generated in partnership with members of these vulnerable groups will be deployed to “co-design” transport solutions with engineers and transport planners that serve their needs.

With this example, which is indicative of P17’s overall research program, he illustrates the difference that direct access and representation makes—research participants drawn from marginalized groups have a say in setting the research agenda, therefore co-directing the knowledge production process, and ultimately their lived experience and situated expertise feed directly into the policy-making process. In the subsections that follow, on themes such as inclusive methods, the costs and benefits of participation, the value of local knowledge, and forging relationships between marginalized groups and policy-makers, countless examples will further illustrate the differences between indirect and direct representation, and the benefits to marginalized groups that come with the latter.

5.4.3. Inclusive methods to bring in marginalized groups

Participants described using a variety of carefully crafted research methods in order to facilitate the participation of marginalized groups in their research. These range from CS approaches enabled by wearable technology, to the use of art, visualization tools and performance, to the selection of setting and storytelling. Participants explained the settings in which they deploy these methods, the marginalized groups that these methods work to include, and also discussed the power dynamics they consider when choosing methods with an eye toward flattening historical power imbalances in research settings.

P17 described a variety of creative methods, some technologically-enabled, that he and his team use to facilitate the participation of “vulnerable groups”. His strongly participatory approach sometimes uses traditional CS data collection methods and other times, more creative methods to both work with participants and to engage the broader community in a project. Reflecting a CS approach to data collection, in the project focused on mobility in East African cities described previously, participants were given smartwatches to wear to enable data collection to reveal how health indicators correspond to pollution and stress variables in urban settings. In another project focused on air pollution, P17 and his team deployed a range of creative methods that are not commonly represented within the scientific research process. (He also described using creative methods with similar populations to similar ends in other projects.) Describing this approach, he said:

...It was a fascinating project in terms of the range of the types of art-based methods that the community used to generate knowledge, but also to engage with those other stakeholder groups. It ranged from things like a music festival that was held in the community on the theme of air pollution. There were rappers and performers doing songs and dance around the issue as well as other performances and also, creative ways of collecting people’s understanding of air pollution. They had a sheet with a body marked on, and you got to put stickers or markers on where you thought air pollution was causing damage. It was interesting, just the differences in people’s knowledge of what impacts air pollution had and how they could understand air pollution better. (P17, interview)

P17 reflected in an interview on the strengths and weaknesses of different methodological approaches—namely “traditional Citizen Science” versus “co-creation” and the different benefits they offer to participants. Describing two projects that relied on community members to collect data on local environmental issues, he explained, reflecting the literature on this topic (see for example Herschan et al. 2020; Kimura and Kinchy

2016), that the “traditional Citizen Science” approach had the benefit of “sensitising” the participants to the particular environmental problem in question. Prior to the project, community members did not have an understanding of this particular problem. However, also reflecting the literature (see for example Allen 2018; English, Richardson, and Garzon-Galvis 2018; Godrie et al. 2020; Hendricks et al. 2018; O’Leary 2018), he believes that the “co-creative” approach yielded more benefits to participants and the broader community, in particular, by facilitating a connection to the policy realm. He explained:

But the other co-created one I think was much more valuable for them in that what they did ultimately was collect or record environmental problems or challenges they had around their neighbourhoods, document them using smartphone photographs, map them, and we could produce a map to highlight where these problems were. And then, we were able to use that to create a dialogue with the local authority which meant, I think when we last checked, about half of those problems had been solved or fixed in some way. So, there was quite a radical impact, if you like, on the ground for the community from collecting the data, presenting it in a way that was useful for the policy decision-makers, and then seeing some changes on the ground. So, that was really valuable. (P17, interview)

Affirming P17’s similar description in our health workshop of the methods he uses, P14, evoking the literature that speaks to the ethical considerations that must be taken when conducting participatory research (see for example Godrie et al. 2020; Hendricks et al. 2018; Kumar 2019; Timmermann 2019), emphasized the importance of using methods that allow for the equal participation of “people who are not experts” and how care needs to be taken to establish an equal playing field between them and other stakeholders. He explained:

And then, I think a second layer is, what I heard from P17, is you have to have methods in which you can engage people who are not experts to bring in their thoughts which might be considered unusual or also methods which don’t generate an asymmetry between participants. This is also important. So, first of all, get them in and then get them in a situation where they feel comfortable to talk and can exchange their views. (P14, health workshop)

P13 shared a similar sentiment in our agriculture workshop, speaking from her own experience of incorporating marginalized groups in participatory, multi-stakeholder research projects. Additionally, she raised the issue of virtual research settings, in light of the general shift to online meetings during the COVID-19 global pandemic. She elaborated:

The other thing which I think is quite important to consider, particularly if you’re working with marginalised groups is a very simple thing which refers to settings, to methods, to places where you... if you physically implement the cooperative work, consider if you do it in your environment or try to imagine what would be an appropriate environment for others and against the background of the actual COVID pandemic where so many activities have been shifted to virtual interaction—that even is more exclusive for socially marginalised people. This is something I think we need to put thorough thoughts in because this huge bunch of online activities which has its advantages, particularly in terms of travel and ecological impact, might be carried on more than it was previously and that means even more to consider that. (P13, agriculture workshop)

Also speaking to the importance of using “innovative methodologies” to effectively include marginalized groups in research processes, P9 spoke in our agriculture workshop to the fact that those who use creative qualitative methods may be ostracized and marginalized themselves within academic research communities. She explained:

I think, P11, you made this point earlier, but I think we need to have innovative methodologies on engaging different people, creative methodologies that use visualisation tools or other ways that are going to engage with people in a way that we haven't before and perhaps that won't be considered scientifically sound or methodologically robust. But these are the methods that are going to raise the voices of the people who are not used to speaking up. For example, I think the Oxford Merging of Knowledge methodology, which is used to identify multiple dimensions of poverty, uses methods of drawing, different assemblies for people who are illiterate to draw out psychological issues and different aspects of what it means to be impoverished. I think we need to have different methods and maybe we won't be considered as researchers if we use these tools, maybe that's just something that we have to sacrifice. (P9, agriculture workshop)

These extracts demonstrate that participants who use strongly participatory methods deploy a range of innovative and creative methods and carefully consider how they deploy their methods in the interest of including marginalized groups in processes of scientific knowledge production aimed at policy-making. Though there may be career implications for using creative methods, researchers who take the strongly participatory approach are committed to fostering equality of access and representation within research and policy-making. Further, they are aware of the ethical dilemmas that often arise when doing so. We turn now to a deeper discussion of these dilemmas and how our participants respond to them.

5.4.4. Meeting the material needs of participation and providing other benefits

Several participants who use multi-stakeholder and participatory approaches spoke to the importance of meeting the material needs and costs of participation, be they transportation, food, or compensation for time given to the project.⁶ Some also spoke to the importance of offering tangible benefits to participants. Responding to a question by the facilitator about the strategies and methods participants use to include low-income communities in their research and keep them involved, P12 explained his approach, working in East Africa, during our agriculture workshop:

It's actually quite a challenge given the sacrifice that some of these communities, like farmers, have to make to be involved in research. The first thing that we do, of course, this I think has issues to do with ethics, but is the fact that whenever we go to a community, say a group of farmers, that we have a project that we're working with, we make sure that if they have to be involved in things like workshops and so on, we actually meet the cost of their participation. If it's transport, we have to make sure that we give them food, and we also have to make sure that sometimes, if we have to go and do

⁶ While some within academia raise the question of whether monetarily compensating research participants biases them in some way, it is an accepted norm among those who conduct participatory research with poor, vulnerable or marginalized groups that it is unethical to *not* do so, as evidenced by the data presented here and in the relevant literature (see for example Kumar 2019; Saleh et al. 2020; Timmermann 2019). Based upon this evidence, bias does not appear to be a notable problem.

interviews in their homes and so on, we can go with some locally accepted compensation. It could be things that they might themselves express that they'd wish to get like soap or a packet of sugar. Things like that. (P12, agriculture workshop)

He then continued by pointing out that taking these aspects into consideration signals to participants that you are genuinely concerned about the circumstances they face and that you want the outcome of the research to benefit them directly. P12 then described how his team actually employs some of the participants they work with in a CS approach:

In one project where we work with informal settlement communities, what we just did was actually to work with a lot of young people there who are unemployed because we were measuring air pollution. Basically, just train them in terms of how they could use those gadgets and they then took that up as some activity which they were doing as fun activities. But of course, they got interested because they are actually working with us to collect data. In that way, we also are paying them as research assistants. So, it was also a way to help them get some employment. (P12, agriculture workshop)

Affirming P12's statement in the workshop discussion, P13 shared that she also compensates participants when working with marginalized groups in the Western European context. Specifically, she described compensating individual farmers for the time they take away from their farms to participate, as well as meeting the costs of participation and "valuing their contribution." For her, part of doing this is working to ensure that there will be some tangible, immediate benefits to participants, especially considering that co-creative processes can take a long time. She elaborated:

For us as researchers, it's kind of part of our job but I think it's also very important to thoroughly consider what kind of quick wins you could generate within the engagement processes which immediately would pay off for the participants and that needs thorough consideration, but that also needs exploration before. Because similar as we've been talking previously about that we as researchers also have our imagination about how the policy world would work or what their needs would be, we also most of the time only imagine what benefits would be relevant for those whom we would like to engage. So, having exploratory talks to them previously and things like that, that really helps in practice to get an idea about what could you include in the process that would immediately pay off for those who are contributing to the process, which usually you have been setting up. (P13, agriculture workshops)

In this statement, in addition to speaking to the ways in which marginalized participants can be compensated or how research can aim to provide "quick wins" in terms of direct benefits to the participants, P13 also speaks to the value of a co-creative, strongly participatory process that begin by seeking to identify these things through conversation with participants before a project even starts.

In our health workshop, P17 shared a similar sentiment and linked compensation for participants to the concept of division of labour and distribution of value across the research chain (our terms, not his). He said:

But in the work that we've been doing, most recently for, mainly work in East Africa, I've always incorporated some kind of remuneration for people because as we've heard, I think if you're asking people to divert time from the thing that's going to generate them an income to participate in research, it's only fair and equitable—I'm being paid to

undertake the research, I'm reliant on them to make the research a success. It seems only fair and equitable they get some sort of remuneration for the time that they're giving up to participate in that process. Particularly for when our work is revolving around vulnerable or some of the poorest members of society, to be mindful of that and make sure there is some sort of remuneration for them for taking part. (P17, health workshop)

Speaking to a different type of benefit in our agriculture workshop, P11 observed that collaborating with activists and CSOs can lend legitimacy to their cause. Further, he spoke about the “right for research” position within the tradition of participatory action research that directs researchers to teach research skills to community members so that they can address issues in their communities through self-directed research. P11 frames this as a way to “empower” the people he works with who do not have an academic science background.

This section demonstrates that our participants carefully craft research design and methods in order to bring marginalized groups into the research process, and not only bring them in, but value their contributions through forms of material compensation and through both immediate and long-term benefits to them and their communities. In doing so, they demonstrate critical awareness of structures of inequality and power dynamics that are at play within societies generally, the communities in which they conduct research, and within the research setting itself. They carefully consider these dynamics and use a diverse set of tools and skills in an effort to even the playing field within the research setting to allow for the equitable participation of marginalized groups. Therefore, the approaches described here result in broadened diversity of access and representation within scientific knowledge production, at the science-policy interface (when marginalized groups are in contact with policy-makers within the research setting), and in the policy-making processes in which related research outputs are presented.

5.4.5. Valuing and incorporating local knowledge into policy advice

Valuing and incorporating local knowledge in participatory research processes are primary ways of bringing in marginalized groups and are key ways that participants seek to improve equality of access and representation within scientific knowledge production and within policy-making processes. This aspect, too, resonates with the tradition of standpoint epistemology referred to previously, wherein this type of knowledge is variously described as ‘situated knowledge’ or ‘indigenous knowledge’. Our participants incorporate this aspect of work into preliminary research that takes place before a problem begins, as part of the work of defining problems and question setting, through to selecting methods, collecting and analysing data and disseminating results in inclusive ways. This work is therefore a key aspect in the strongly participatory research approach and is sometimes used within the multi-stakeholder approach. Reflecting how standpoint epistemology impacts research design, participants value local, situated knowledge as expert knowledge in its own right, and set it on equal footing alongside scientific and other forms of expertise. Overall, our participants find that this approach is important because it shows them where their own perspectives and assumptions may be misaligned with those in the local setting, it democratizes knowledge production, and it ensures that the perspectives of impacted communities are reflected in the scientific advice that is presented to policy-makers.

Speaking to the rationale for seeking out and incorporating local understanding as part of the research process, P9, who it's worth noting is a Southeast Asian woman working in Southeast Asia, observed:

I think it's really important because in working in developing country contexts, we are researchers that are not the experts on the issues that we're trying to inquire into. Though we can conduct literature review, we come at it from an angle, a very Western-centric way of trying to set up a research design. We come in and say, this is the research question, this is what needs to be done, these are the problems, we've done all the modelling and the literature review so this is the problem. But I think we need local understanding and local buy-in into the questions that we investigate. We can say that water quality is one of the main issues in the region but maybe that's not something that local stakeholders or local government are prioritising. Each stakeholder will come at it from a different angle, maybe politics is at play, their ethnic background, their gender—the way that they interact with the environment is going to differ significantly to us. That's why I think it's very important to merge these two different types of understandings, engage with diverse audiences and stakeholders so that the question that we design, the research that we design is able to have meaningful impact. (P9, interview)

Elaborating on the value of this approach in our agriculture workshop, P9 explained that it democratises knowledge production and access, and in doing so, works to “even the power dynamics” between different groups:

...Using a multi-stakeholder participatory approach can equalise the power dynamics between different stakeholder groups so that there is no elite capture of knowledge that one researcher or the policymaker is the one with the expertise, that everybody can have an opportunity to contribute and in their contribution there is expertise and there is an opportunity to even the power dynamics. (P9, agriculture workshop)

Reflecting a similar perspective in an interview and linking it to the participatory research approach, P11 reflected on his shift from being an economist and working in ways that are disconnected from the social world to being a social scientist who does fieldwork and therefore operates directly in relation to “how the world is working.” P11 articulated his preference for working in teams, and in particular, those that include “non-scientists”:

I became a scientist because I enjoy group work and I don't believe in individual scientific achievements. Although this is usually praised by Nobel prizes and whatever, but I think this is unfair because usually we are—at least I am—working in teams and all my knowledge is coming from these interactions with other researchers and not professional researchers, but other types of knowledge holders. So, very early on I was fascinated that I can learn a lot from non-scientists who have knowledge from a very different type compared to scientific knowledge but it is equally valid or even more valid in some contexts than scientific knowledge. But anyway, knowledge synthesis and synergies between knowledge types is fascinating, so that's why I like to identify with all kinds of participatory research—which participation is taken seriously in the sense that even the research question itself is negotiated or discussed or tailored to the needs of different social groups. (P11, interview)

P13 takes a self-described “strongly participatory approach” to research, which she described in an interview as taking a multi-stakeholder approach in combination with participatory methods. Her work begins with an “exploratory phase” with local stakeholders and policy-makers to define problems, questions, and ways of moving forward. Speaking about a particular project, P13 explained how she deployed workshops with

various local groups, including those from “socially disadvantaged districts” to develop a “state-of-the-art” understanding of her city’s food system and proposals for change that reflect local knowledge and situated expertise.

Making the link between access to and representation within research and representation within policy-making processes, P9 described how local knowledge and expertise captured through a multi-stakeholder, participatory research process was specifically targeted in order to present previously excluded views to policy-makers. She explained:

The goals are really to help the government realise their ambitions to have a more sustainable and equitable future using the bioeconomy. It’s written in policy documents, it’s quite lofty, but in interviews with a lot of government people, that is what they really want to achieve. They want to have a more socially equitable society through the bioeconomy. But the way that it is developing currently, it’s very elite-captured. The Ministry of Industry is the one that’s spearheading the development. Despite all these lofty ambitions, there’s no action on ensuring that different perspectives are heard in the bioeconomy, that bottom-up approaches are used. The scholarly way that we’re looking at it is, how is sustainability inherently tied to the concept of equity? We’re looking and we think that these concepts are linked together without needing to—we can’t separate one from the other. There’s no way to achieve equity without sustainability and vice versa. So that’s a sort of high-level investigation. But what we’re also doing is using that concept to develop a framework where we can seek to understand farmers’ perspectives on how they feel that they are being treated in the bioeconomy. It looks at their ability to participate in different platforms or for voicing their concerns, their satisfaction with different elements of the bioeconomy, whether they even want to be a part of the bioeconomy. The idea is so that we can bring these perspectives to the government and say, ‘Here is what different people feel about the bioeconomy.’ There needs to be a different approach that’s not top-down because how small holder farmers, large farmers, processors, the way that they understand equity in the bioeconomy is different from how the government sees it. (P9, interview)

Similarly, in an interview, P11 described a project that takes a participatory approach to get the views and experiences of “local people, farmers and other stakeholders” into the policy process for revising Europe’s CAP and launching its next iteration. He explained that the goal of this approach is to foster policy change in the CAP that responds to local concerns to “make better ecological and social impacts for the local nature and for the local social context.”

In another example, P17 described in our health workshop how he was part of a research team that used CS to engage community members in creating situated scientific expertise so that their local knowledge could be meaningfully included in a policy-making process. Additionally, he pointed out that there are sometimes political advantages for elected policy-makers to embrace CS within the policy-making process.

I did work quite some decades ago now around air pollution issues in the city where I’m based. It was part of a national policy to try and identify air quality management areas for cities where pollution was known to be a problem. There was a statutory process that the council had to undertake to commit to the policy. But we, collaborating with the city authorities, opened it up to be much more of a participatory process. So, we engaged

interest groups that were concerned about air pollution in the city to try and understand their knowledge on the topic that resulted in generating maps that showed where they believed air pollution was a problem. Luckily, those maps agreed largely with the council's monitoring and modelling work on air pollution. So, what happened was that, one, the map that the community generated became one option in a wider consultation sent out as a survey to all households and that was then, the response to the survey was an endorsement of the community generated map and data, which then gave the politicians in the city confidence to adopt that community generated air quality management area as the official boundary for the city. The reason that was politically challenging for them was the community map was much bigger than the council's official maps that had been generated from the modelling. So, having the community involved in the science meant we ended up adopting a larger air quality management area than I think the council officers expected. But also having the people involved in the whole process led to the politicians having confidence that they wouldn't be unelected at the next cycle if they adopted such a big air quality management area. (P17, health workshop)

Together, these examples illustrate that participants who take a multi-stakeholder or strongly participatory approach recognize the limits of their own knowledge and expertise because they understand that both are shaped by their positionality, and that this means that they do not see and understand things in the same way as those upon whom their research is focused. Therefore, they recognize the need to bring local knowledge into the research process, particularly when that research has policy aims that are meant to improve the lived experience of their research participants. Based on the evidence offered by our participants, it is clear that valuing and incorporating local knowledge fosters equality of access to and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making.

5.4.6. Forging relationships between local groups, communities and policy-makers

Something that happens within the context of the multi-stakeholder approach and (sometimes) the strongly participatory approach, and especially when these approaches are combined, is that our participants facilitate relationship-building between local groups, communities and their relevant policy-makers. This happens in the context of the research setting, when our participants bring both types of actors (and often other types, too) together to collaborate on research design and conduct. This aspect of the work is important because it forges social ties that can and often do outlive the duration of the research project, and that therefore serve as tangible and impactful lasting benefits to marginalized groups who are brought into the research process. Within participatory and co-creative research, as previous examples have demonstrated, research participants develop scientific skills and knowledge that they are then able to deploy themselves as they work directly with policy-makers to address problems in their communities.

This work is common in the approach of many of our participants, including and most notably in that of P5, P9, P11, P13 and P17. In a previously cited example, P17 recounted how a co-created CS project involved “creat[ing] a dialogue” between marginalized community members and “the local authority” so that the community members themselves could go directly to policy-makers to address environmental problems in their community that needed to be addressed. Consequently, many of the problems were addressed.

In our agriculture workshop, P13 spoke positively about the outcome of a challenging project which spanned more than three years and involved building relationships between researchers, policy-makers and

representatives of CSOs. The positive outcome, as she explained, was that a partnership was forged between the CSO representatives and the policy-makers after years of working together.

What we did, we did a knowledge brokerage project which was about three and a half years, which was about setting up communities of practice between researchers, policy people and CSO people. The aim was to foster the outcome of research findings on the one hand, and on the other hand, to explore together in those multi-actor groups the existing research reservoir on several topics. On the other hand, also giving the opportunity to the research community to better understand the needs and contexts of policy and civil society organisation. I could tell you the three and a half years were very intense and that was actually something which worked out. People meeting regularly, having the room being financed. The civil society organisations and the policy people were real partners in the project. So, they had the necessary room and that really made a difference. (P13, agriculture workshop)

As these and previously cited data extracts show, taking a multi-stakeholder and/or strongly participatory approach to research facilitates access to the science-policy interface and therefore to the policy-making process for actors who are typically marginalized from these spaces, be they community members or CSOs/NGOs. Both sets of actors are often viewed to be at odds with policy-makers and by facilitating the development of social relationships between them, our participants help both sides find common ground on which to work together toward solutions that benefit the communities in question.

5.4.7. Section summary

The goal of this section, 5.4, was to illustrate the ways in which our participants work to foster equality of access and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making. Our findings demonstrate that while indirect representation does this to a certain extent, it is direct access and representation, achieved through co-creative multi-stakeholder and/or strongly participatory research design that features inclusive and creative methods, meets the material needs of participation and ensures other benefits, values and incorporates local knowledge, and supports the development of relationships between community members and policy-makers that does so in a way that radically reconfigures the science-society relationship and the science-policy interface. Taken together, these methods and practices diversify the range of actors who are able to participate in scientific knowledge production, the viewpoints that are represented within it, expand representation within scientific outputs to include the knowledge co-created with marginalized groups, and expand access to and representation within the science-policy interface. This work intentionally diverges from traditional academic and scientific norms and practices, and therefore, is not without its challenges, which are described in the next section.

5.5. Challenges and barriers in doing this work

Our data show that researchers seeking to expand equality of access and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making face numerous challenges and barriers. These fall into three categories: 1. academic and scientific norms; 2. structural economic factors; and 3. socio-cultural barriers.

5.5.1. Academic and scientific norms and standards

Participants recounted to us how things like particular definitions of scientific rigor and academic norms and expectations can get in the way of inclusive research design and execution, how these norms and standards

manifest in funding structures and schemes that subvert this kind of work, that academic language operates as a barrier to access to research findings, and that inclusive research is often dismissed as ‘care work’ within academic institutions (as was demonstrated and discussed in Chapter 4). Together, these social forces pose challenges that our participants use creative methods to overcome (as detailed in previous sections of this chapter), but sometimes, they pose barriers to doing the work at all.

P9 spoke to how normative understandings of “scientific rigor” do not always align with how representation should be done to support inclusivity in research that is meant to support policy-making. She observed that scientific rigor often directs research to topics that are “under-studied” or “gaps in the literature” in ways that do not necessarily serve the aim of fostering equality of access and representation. She stated, “There’s a disconnect between what is required of us in science and what is required of us in trying to engage people from different and marginalised communities. I don’t really know if these things are compatible...” and later in the conversation concluded, “academic contribution doesn’t necessarily lead to inclusiveness and representation of people who need to be represented the most” (P9, interview).

Illustrating the same theme, participants in our climate workshop debated the dynamics of representation in research that is focused on and presented in high-level climate policy arenas. P1 pushed back on assertions made by other participants that representation of impacted communities should be a staple of research designed for policy uptake by pointing out that policy-makers and researchers make the assumption that the interests of “poor and vulnerable” people are represented by their governments (and recognized that this isn’t always so). Yet, P1 stated that it isn’t always possible to have broad representation in research and offered the example of policies for climate financing. He stated that he doesn’t see how one could achieve broadened access and representation in research that is focused on the policy and the finance mechanisms, because it is by definition focused on elite, high-level spaces, people and processes. He concluded, “I guess I’m pushing back a little bit against the idea that we can only have legitimate research when it involves some very broad representation. I think particularly in policy research that isn’t always, I think, feasible” (P1, climate workshop). In response, P7 pointed out that some researchers in her organization are doing exactly that by working on the ground with farmers in “developing countries” who are recipients of climate financing, on the one hand agreeing with P1 that it is not always possible to expand representation within research focused on policy, yet at the same time demonstrating that it is. This discrepancy shows that P1’s stance is pragmatic: his research focuses on high-level climate policy, and therefore representation within and access to his research is aimed toward the people who are involved in it. Yet, his stance is also shaped by the traditional academic approach that he takes to his work. His approach is not oriented to looking for ways to broaden inclusion; he values work that does this but sees it as separate from what he does.

Offering another example of how academic and scientific norms and standards can get in the way of expanding equality of access and representation in research and policy-making, P9 observed in our agriculture workshop that the Western concept of informed consent is off-putting to some groups, given their cultural and political context and social norms. Speaking about a particular Asian context that has experienced military rule, she said, “If you go to a community that hasn’t really worked with foreigners before and you ask them, can you give me consent to participate in this interview, they are automatically terrified of participating in that interview” (P9, agriculture workshop). What this example illustrates is that normative academic and scientific practice, which are developed in the West for use with Western populations, do not fit neatly into all cultural and social contexts and therefore can serve to undermine goals of inclusivity in research.

Academic language was also raised by participants as a norm and practice that acts as a barrier to improving equality of access not just within but to research. P6 observed in our climate workshop that specifically the language used to report climate science is an access barrier to people involved in the youth climate justice movement, who want to “build their own knowledge” about climate science. Of this, she said, “Scientific language is very exclusive. It’s just another barrier” (P6, climate workshop). P9 also spoke to this topic in our agriculture workshop, pointing out that working with “diverse stakeholders” requires that researchers do the work of translating their findings to their participants. They cannot simply offer an academic journal article to people who “don’t have the technical knowledge” to read and understand it.

Finally, some participants, particularly women, spoke to how purposefully compiling diverse research teams and conducting work that is designed to engage with and lift up under-served and disadvantaged groups and communities are marginalized by academic scientific norms. In our health workshop, P15 explained that the inclusive approach of the NGO she leads and the diversity of her organization’s research teams lead others, working within academic institutions and with academic norms, to dismiss their work due to a perceived lack of credibility. She stated:

There is sometimes a lack of credibility that’s been expressed because we are an NGO, non-profit organisation. A lot of the established entities don’t consider the work we do as rigorous as a result of the fact that we have such diverse teams. We have those that are academics and research experts to early career people to truly activists and those in the global health field that might not be as close to the research community. So, there is a lack of credit, there is a challenge to credibility, and we do struggle with being invited to the most influential academic tables. So, when commissions are being created by the Lancet, for example, we’re often shortlisted. But then when the commissions are selected, we are not the ones that make the cut and that has a lot to do with, I think, this way of bringing everybody into your research, the mindset isn’t quite there yet to say that that’s the best research. (P15, health workshop)

As P15 points out, there is a disconnect between diversity as a value and what is considered best practice within the scientific community. Simply having a diverse research team seems to cultivate disadvantage. On the other side of the coin, P13 described in our agriculture workshop that she has observed that participatory research is feminized and consequently marginalized within academia.

The last years I’ve been also working on gender issues and gender in research organisations and something which is quite interesting is that type of research, participatory, transdisciplinary, action research, all those types of research, particularly those types of research which are dedicated to empowering marginalised groups, are considered to be ‘care work’ within the academic system, similar to all those teaching duties. (P13, agriculture workshop)

By classifying research that opens up access and representation within the research process as ‘care work’, those within academic institutions devalue this work, along with other kinds of work that are similarly framed (like teaching, as P13 points out).

These examples demonstrate that academic and scientific norms frequently act as challenges and barriers to fostering equality of access and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making. From directing research questions, topics and sample populations in ways that undermine these aims, to fostering the use of exclusive language that poses challenges to participation and barriers to

access, to implicit bias against diverse research teams and dismissing in a sexist way inclusive work as ‘care work’, it is clear that academic and scientific norms, as they currently stand, do not support equality of access and representation.

5.5.2. Institutional and structural economic challenges and barriers

Participants observed several issues that arise due to how scientific research is funded. These range from who is eligible to receive funding, to rules about how funds are used, the geo-politics of funding, and a lack of funding for research aimed at improving equity.

Speaking specifically to how CS initiatives have been operationalized and supported through EU funding frameworks, P8 observed in our agriculture workshop that though the EU claims to have an interest in supporting CS, this is done in narrow and limited ways that reflect the limitations posed by traditional academic and scientific norms and standards. He made the point that citizens in and of themselves are not eligible for funding because this is premised on the normative definition that a “qualified scientist” must be someone with a PhD who works at a university. Though he is a PhD advanced in his career with an impressive CV and legacy in policy work, P8 himself has run into this problem because he currently operates as an independent scientist. He referred to this problem as an “institutional barrier” that serves to greatly limit the population of people who are eligible to conduct funded scientific research.

In our health workshop, P14 also spoke on this theme, and observed that not only is eligibility for funding an issue, but so too is how funds can be used. Speaking to the challenges of conducting multi-stakeholder or participatory research, he noted that most funding mechanisms do not fund the participation of representatives of NGOs in workshops, for example.

But for NGOs it's very different and it's very difficult. Now it's easy because nobody can travel but if you have a workshop, let's say in Brussels or in the UK or in Vienna, even if you can pay their travel expenses, you cannot pay them a salary or remuneration for the working time. So, there are certain institutional hurdles for NGOs to participate in these kinds of activities. (P14, health workshop)

Other participants made similar points in interviews and workshops, observing that they find it challenging to monetarily support the participation of the people they want to work with, and to ensure that the work that needs to take place at the community level can continue when a funded project has concluded.

Also in our health workshop, P15, who leads a policy-active NGO, spoke to the challenge posed by what she described as a lack of funding for “equity work.” She offered the example of doing unfunded research focused on the issue of gender representation at a global-level policy-making body, then said:

For a non-profit that doesn't have any budget with zero budget to support research, that's not what we get funded for. It is very tasking. So, finding that balance of practicing our values, creating Open Access, I would really say that we need more groups to fund equity work in our organisations and that doesn't necessarily happen. (P15, health workshop)

Her statement emphasizes a key issue flagged by many of our participants: a lack of, or restrictions on funding, that pose challenges and sometimes barriers to carrying out research that is designed to broaden equality of access and representation within scientific knowledge production and policy-making.

In an interview, P12, an African man living and working in Africa, raised another inequality that stems from normative research funding practices, which typically support European researchers to conduct research on the African continent, but not vice versa. He observed:

Most of the way these projects are structured is that it could be EU funded but the actual field work or whatever is in Africa. There's never that bi-directional knowledge exchange which is I think one of the things that I'm trying to make sure that in future projects that we develop. We have that ability to make sure that if you have a project that is maybe EU funded in Africa, there's opportunities also for Africans to do research in the EU because that doesn't happen. Some of the structure of things are always attached in a way that... It's the way it's set up and that's the way it is. It's almost like a practice, nobody ever steps back and says, maybe we need to have that kind of arrangement. (P12, interview)

The issue that P12 raises here is not simply brokered by geography but echoes colonial relationships between the two continents: Europeans travel to Africa to study Africans and their way of life and this is supported by funding mechanisms, yet the inverse is not. This is yet another example of how funding structures and schemes reify unequal access to and representation within processes of knowledge creation and policy-making.

Later, in our co-creation workshop, P12 raised an economic challenge that is both institutional and structural in nature: the defunding of public universities across Africa (an issue which resonates across neoliberal contexts, irrespective of geography). He explained that this has led to the trend of the marketization of both teaching and research within universities and that this undermines the ability of university researchers to “inform public discourse and public policy.” Rather than responding to public needs, these activities now respond to market needs. He further explained that the gap in influence has been filled by private survey companies that support business growth and the identification of new market opportunities. What he describes is therefore a research terrain in which equality of access to and representation within processes of knowledge production and policy-making is narrowed rather than expanded. He makes the point that well-funded science is needed to counteract that which is geared toward corporate interest over the common good. The consequences of this can be dire. He offered an example of what happens when public funding for university research is not available:

Unfortunately, because of the decline and decrease in public funding even these public institutions are actually trending now to pick up issues that are market-oriented where we can allow them to generate revenue and therefore sometimes and, in most cases, actually not necessarily something that's positive to a healthy discussion in the public agenda. For example, when issues of tobacco and the banning of smoking. You had legislation that took about ten years to go through in [our country], for example, because the influence of the tobacco industry was so huge across the entire system from scientists at the universities to parliamentarians and so on. So, it needed a very well-funded counter-narrative that is also informed by scientific capacity to be able to bring out the contradictions for the public to be able to have a balanced view of what the impact of smoking can be. (P12, co-creation workshop)

Speaking to a different structural economic issue and different consequences, P16 recounted in an interview how difficult it is as a sector leader for a global union to reach the most precarious and vulnerable workers in a South Asian context. Due to the flexibilization of work and the forced migratory nature of work among

some of the world's poorest people, workers in his industry of focus move from job to job on a weekly basis. This in turn makes union organizing and membership difficult, which makes it difficult to get information from these workers about what they are experiencing, and to get information about their rights to them. He observes that in places where union density is high, the union organizers on the ground are usually able to develop relationships with the precarious workforce, but in places where it is not, it seems that the global capitalist economic system and the social structure that supports it are barriers to fostering equality of access and representation within knowledge production and policy-making.

Together, these excerpts and the broader trends they represent within our data demonstrate that institutional and structural economic challenges and barriers frequently get in the way of doing co-creative and strongly participatory work. Funders (institutions) place restrictions on access to and use of funds in ways that give privileged access to those practicing the traditional academic approach and disadvantage those who take multi-stakeholder or strongly participatory approaches. Our participants also highlighted how research focused on producing equitable outcomes (in policy and in communities) is underfunded and that European funding opportunities that allow for transnational research typically reproduce colonial patterns that privilege European researchers while disadvantaging their partners in the global south. Our data show that these trends at the institutional level are couched within broader structural trends that result from the ongoing neoliberal globalization of the capitalist economy. This process has produced the privatization of universities and the commercialization of scientific research around the world, and the precarity it produces makes the world poorest and most vulnerable nearly impossible to reach, in terms of both gathering and sharing information.

5.5.3. Social and cultural challenges and barriers

In addition to challenges and barriers posed by academic norms and economic factors, participants also cited social and cultural ones. These came up primarily as trust issues, fear, and the difficulties to research that can be posed by social tensions and conflicts within groups and communities.

In our agriculture workshop, P11 spoke to how fear of being criticized or vilified, on the part of policy-makers, makes them wary of engaging in participatory settings with citizens and other stakeholders. He explained then that the challenge for researchers is to create a "safe space" for this type of research to take place:

We have to create a safe environment also for the policy-makers so that they don't think that the participatory process is just about criticizing them and they take it more personally. I think at least that's my experience, here again, from the periphery [referencing his location in an Eastern European country]. But if you can create a safe space for everyone that they feel that they can really share without shame and express their needs and ideas, then it might be very helpful. I really believe in it. (P11, agriculture workshop)

Also explaining how a lack of trust can interfere with one's research aims, P17 recounted in our health workshop how a participatory project broke down when medical professionals backed out of engaging with citizens in a project focused on understanding environmental causes. He surmised that they were afraid of damaging their reputations and/or legitimacy if they participated. He recounted:

So, there was that critical breakdown in the project in terms of that facilitation of the dialogue that I think was to do with... possibly stemming from two things. One is, I think the medical professionals found this somehow slightly threatening. I think also the fact

that it hadn't originated as a medical project, it was much more about participation and engagement with lay stakeholders, if you like—in terms of Open Science, trying to capture and understand their knowledge and their understanding and present it back to medical professionals—I think the way it was formulated by not having the medical professionals maybe as on board as they possibly could or should have been from the outset. But for whatever reason, there was that breakdown in trust between the two groups and ultimately it led to us not being able to get the two parties in the room together. We had to deal with each one separately, which wasn't the aim at all. (P17, health workshop)

Speaking to another manifestation of the colonial legacy in Africa, P18 explained that a lack of trust in research scientists among policy-makers makes collaboration difficult. A history of “data siphoning” makes policy-makers wary of sharing information with the scientific community and fearful that if they do share, they will be exploited. She recounted a typical conversation with a policy-maker, wherein they denied a request for data because “we are tired of giving our data because we know where you guys take it.” Her challenge, then, is to reframe this dynamic. She explained:

So, changing that narrative to, “Trust us, let's work together, this data is actually useful here.” From a research data gathering perspective, we have to challenge, it's just beyond consent. I have given you consent to use this, whatever you want to use it and do whatever you want to do with it. But it is just beyond consent. Can people understand what is in need for them to collect this data and can we be ethical and responsible enough to give them back that benefit that we say we are going to give them. I mean, data siphoning here, when I use it and I know that's a very strong sentiment, I am brute about it because we need to do a good job. Otherwise, we are messing up, we've messed up the environment. It's so difficult for advocates to get data so that we can help our people. (P18, interview)

Similar to his previous comment, P11 also noted in our agriculture workshop how our social tendency to group together among like individuals (based on social categories) can get in the way of collaboration within participatory settings, wherein groups of participants will want to stick together rather than collaborate across group lines. This, therefore, is a challenge for researchers who use multi-stakeholder or participatory methods to bring community members into contact with policy-makers. He observed:

There is a tendency from each of us that we choose those who are similar to us—the easy ones and we take their values and interests. Policy-makers are not different. They tend to, even without bad intentions, they tend to concentrate on those participants and those dynamics which are closer to their social words. So that's why, very marginalised and vulnerable groups, even if the participant processes are going on, many times they cannot really influence policy through the participatory process because they are so different from the life world of policy-makers. (P11, agriculture workshop)

He concluded by stating that researchers sometimes must use creative methods of sharing information in order to “shock policy-makers out of their life worlds” so that they can connect with the viewpoints and knowledge of other participants.

Articulating another tension or conflict that can manifest in participatory research projects, P9 described in our agriculture workshop how the necessity of seeking research permission from local governments in Asia can cause tension with the target community and has troubling implications:

By [getting permission] we are by default working with the power authority to gain permission to access a certain area—even if we’re working with marginalised people. That causes some tension, perhaps within the communities and in many contexts, we work with the majority ethnic group because that’s easier. (P9, agriculture workshop)

In the same workshop, P9 raised another issue that gets in the way of fostering equality of access and representation in research and policy-making—language. She observed:

We can find facilitators that speak [national languages], but when we really want to work with indigenous people whose language is rapidly becoming lost, how are we going to actually work with these groups? (P9, agriculture workshop)

In our co-creation workshop P13 raised yet another barrier that is social in nature—the digital divide that is now present in participatory research because of how the COVID-19 pandemic has limited in-person meetings. She observed, “In one of our current projects we’re working with socially disadvantaged people and there is no way to carry out an online workshop with people like that” (P13, co-creation workshop). She noted that it is not possible to establish trust and rapport online, which is a first-step in engaging marginalized groups in a research project. She also raised the question of whether participants of this nature have the material or cultural tools and resources to be able to participate in an online workshop. Even if they have internet access, the act itself of participating in an online meeting is not something to which they are accustomed. That policy-makers, researchers and other stakeholders *would* be accustomed to doing so sets the “socially disadvantaged” participants at a distinct disadvantage that exacerbates existing power dynamics within the research setting.

Considering these examples, it is clear that a lack of trust and fear can manifest within groups of diverse stakeholders or participants, and when this happens, achieving co-creative, participatory work is difficult. In the same vein, participants are often inclined to gravitate toward like participants who share the same background or stakeholder role in the project, which again can make collaborative work difficult. Additionally, researchers may find themselves working in the midst of local tensions and conflicts in the communities where they wish to work, and finally, the digital divide poses critical challenges to participatory work in times of social isolation. These issues bring to the fore the critical nature of the training of researchers to understand the social and cultural challenges they may face, and how best to navigate them to produce successful outcomes.

5.5.4. Section summary

In this section we have focused on challenges and barriers to fostering equality of access and representation in processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making. Our findings show that these coalesce around three thematic areas: academic and scientific norms and standards, institutional and structural economic challenges, and social and cultural issues. Academic and scientific norms and standards, though they have evolved some in recent decades, still mostly reflect those of the traditional academic approach, and therefore undermine those who wish to conduct co-creative, participatory research aimed at addressing pressing societal challenges in both policy and impacted communities. Similarly, the challenges and barriers to this kind of work posed by funding institutions privileges the traditional academic approach over others through restricted access to and use of funds. Zooming out, our findings demonstrate that the broader structural trends of the privatization of universities and the related commercialization of scientific research also act as challenges and barriers to conducting research in ways that foster equality of access and representation. Finally, our findings show that researchers who do this kind of work are frequently

confronted by social and cultural challenges that illustrate the importance of training in how to do this work. We turn in the next section to a discussion of how the findings presented in this chapter respond to our research questions and offer a discussion of their broader significance and implications.

5.6. Discussion and conclusion

5.6.1. Answering our research questions

ON-MERRIT is designed to critically interrogate whether the Matthew effect in academia or other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage may be present within or even exacerbated by OS and RRI practices. The task on which this deliverable reports, Task 5.3, focuses specifically on whether such dynamics may be at play and impacting participation in policy-making (which is a result of the conduct of research aligned with RRI principles and practices). This is reflected in the primary research question for this task: **who participates in RRI policy-making?** The research findings presented in this chapter reveal that these dynamics are present in both research and policy-making processes, but that they vary depending on the approach to research that one takes. In turn, the chosen approach, be it traditional academic, multi-stakeholder or strongly participatory, directly shapes who participates in RRI policy-making.

Our findings show that the traditional academic approach limits participants to researchers and policy-makers. The multi-stakeholder approach opens up participation to a range of actors that are selected to represent the views and interests of parties relevant to the problem addressed by the research. Typical actors in this context include researchers, other experts, representatives from the business world, policy-makers and other civil servants, representatives of CSOs and NGOs, and sometimes, representatives of local communities (though not always; CSOs/NGOs often serve this role in this approach). With the strongly participatory approach, which is sometimes combined with a multi-stakeholder approach, the range of actors is broadened to include people who have been historically marginalized from processes of both scientific knowledge production (research) and policy-making. Our findings demonstrate that these people/communities range from average citizens to the world's most poor and vulnerable. While their life circumstances may differ, what they share in common is that they have historically not participated in scientific research as anything other than objects of study, nor in policy-making as anything other than voters (in the best cases). In the strongly participatory approach to research, they participate as co-creators of knowledge and policy recommendations, and sometimes they participate at the science-policy interface (when this is the research setting), and sometimes they have direct interaction with policy-makers (when this has been facilitated by the research process). Therefore, who participates in RRI policy-making is directly shaped by the approach to research that is taken.

Our findings also respond to our secondary research questions. We asked, **which voices remain unheard and for which reasons?** Our findings demonstrate that this, again, depends on the approach to research that is taken by the research team. In the traditional academic approach, the views and interests of the majority of society are left out because participation is limited to researchers and policy-makers. A general public interest is often assumed, particularly with research that focuses on the domains of climate science, agriculture and health and medicine, which our participants represent. Yet, the voices of other actors are not actually present in these processes. Also with the multi-stakeholder approach, representation rather than access is often deployed to include the interests of impacted communities and populations, however direct access and voice is not a given. It is only with the strongly participatory approach that the inclusion of marginalized perspectives, views and interests are guaranteed. Therefore, our findings indicate that unless a

strongly participatory approach is taken, historically marginalized groups are most likely unheard in processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making.

Additionally, we asked, **who influences public participation in policy-making?** The findings reported in this chapter indicate that researchers are the primary determinants, depending on the approach to research that they take, as described above. However, there are other determinants that shape the contexts in which researchers work. Funding bodies, in the requirements they use to determine funding eligibility and funding scope, influence public participation in policy-making. We heard from our participants that funding that allows for the material support of marginalized participants is critical to ensuring their equitable participation in research, and we also heard that overall, funding restrictions are limiting factors. Our findings suggest that there is not enough funding support for multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory research, which therefore limits public participation in policy-making. Additionally, our findings show that academic institutions, which operate with rigid academic and scientific norms, are also influential. They are predominantly a limiting factor, as our findings show that these often get in the way of efforts to foster equality of access and representation within processes of knowledge production and policy-making. Finally, our findings suggest that policy-makers also influence this, to the extent that they are willing to participate in multi-stakeholder and participatory research projects to engage with and listen to historically marginalized people.

Finally, in an interest to learn from our participants, we asked them, **how can we improve equality of representation and access in policy-making in terms of individuals who have access to this sphere, and in terms of whose interests are represented?** Our findings show that deploying multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory research approaches broadens and diversifies the scope of actors in both processes and therefore works to improve both. This is specifically achieved by bringing in marginalized groups through inclusive methods, supporting their participation through payment and offering other immediate and longer-term benefits, by valuing and incorporating local knowledge into the production of scientific knowledge, and by forging relationships between marginalized groups and communities and their policy-makers within the research setting. Additionally, intentionally crafting diverse research teams and networks, and working with values of inclusivity and cooperation (as opposed to individualism and competition) to share knowledge and skills relevant to working at the science-policy interface serves to broaden and diversify the range of actors within the research setting, the science-policy interface and the policy-making sphere. This then has knock-on effects on the focus and form of research, which serve to support the conduct of research as described above. Our findings also suggest that intentional funding of multi-stakeholder and participatory research, in ways that are appropriate to the research design and supportive of the inclusion of marginalized groups, would serve to foster equality of access and representation within processes of scientific knowledge production and policy-making. So too would the intentional cultivation of academic and scientific institutional cultures that truly value and support diversity of people *and* approach to the production of scientific knowledge.

5.6.2. Significance and implications

Cumulatively, the findings reported in this chapter suggest that the Matthew effect, and other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage, are present in OS and RRI approaches to scientific knowledge production, the science-policy interface, and processes of policy-making. There is great evidence in these findings for bias against a strongly participatory research approach, which is rooted in feminist, anti-colonialist, and participatory action research traditions. Each of these were developed out of critiques of normative, Western scientific assumptions, values and practices, so it is not especially surprising that a regime that continues to be premised on these resists critique by marginalizing and dismissing this work, its results and those who conduct it (by not considering it 'real' science but rather 'care work' produced by people who are not 'real' scientists or experts), as well as disadvantaging those who do (by offering only limited funding for this work, which impacts employment, professional reputation and standing, career progression, and lifetime earnings).

Qualitatively, our findings suggest that positionality and relative privilege play a role in influencing the approach to research that one takes, and therefore the extent to which one's work restricts or broadens access and representation. Though our sample is small and therefore conclusive evidence cannot be drawn from this, we observe that the intersection of race, gender and global class position aligns with the predominant approach to research that our participants take. In our sample, only white men of European descent take the traditional academic approach, whereas we see diversity of race, gender, and geography with the multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory approaches (more women than men use the latter). We were unable to corroborate this observation with existing research due to a total lack of it. However, we can consider this observation in relation to the broader trends of representation of race and gender across academic disciplines, as well as in the context of the inequalities that women and people of colour face within academia.

Data from the US show that women and people of colour (excepting those of Asian descent) remain grossly underrepresented as academic faculty within STEM fields (whereas white men are vastly over-represented) and instead are concentrated within humanities and social science fields (Li and Koedel 2017). Our findings map in a way onto this trend, because it is social scientists who predominantly use co-creative and participatory research methods. We can, therefore, extrapolate that institutional biases against women and people of colour push them away from STEM fields and toward humanities and social sciences, wherein when they wish to deploy these types of research designs and methods, they experience further institutional bias.

It stands to reason that the kinds of challenges and biases researchers face when they take these approaches to scientific inquiry have negative career implications. While we cannot conclude this from the data we collected, we do note anecdotal evidence to this effect within our data and wish again to set this evidence in the context of data that demonstrates broader inequalities at play within academic institutions. Data from the US show that white people remain over-represented among postsecondary faculty, at 76% (Davis and Fry 2019), compared with being 60% percent of the total US population (United States Census Bureau 2019). Other data from the US show that the over-representation of white people is greatest among senior career ranks (professors and associate professors) and less extreme among lower career ranks (assistant professors); the same data show the over-representation of men in senior career ranks and the over-representation of women in lower ranks (National Center for Education Statistics 2019a). The same gender trend, in greater extreme, is found in the UK (Higher Education Statistics Agency 2020), and across the EU,

where women are under-represented in academic roles and grossly under-represented as professors (Healy, Ozbilgin, and Aliefendiouglu 2005).

These data demonstrate stratification within academia on the basis of race and gender and do not offer evidence as to why, but as with all data that demonstrate this, they are *suggestive* of institutional biases that favour (white) men and disadvantage all others. Stratification across career ranks by gender (and race, at least in the case of the US) directly influences the salaries and lifetime earnings that a given person, on the basis of the intersecting nature of their race and gender, is able to accrue. The unequal distribution of economic rewards for conducting academic research also bears out *within* career ranks, where the gender pay gap is observed in the US (National Center for Education Statistics 2019b) and across the EU (CARSA 2007), and a racial pay gap is observed in the US (Li and Koedel 2017) and a “minority ethnic pay gap” in the UK (Hopkins and Salvestrini 2018).⁷

We present these trends to offer context for our findings, which show that people who conduct co-creative and participatory research face institutional biases related to their research programs, but also, insofar as they are women and/or people of colour, they face additional (and likely related) institutional biases on the basis of their gender and race or ethnicity.

These trends are, of course, not contained within academic and scientific communities, but rather are manifestations of broader socio-structural inequalities of race, gender, and class (on both local and global scales) that are built into the foundations of Western societies and global society. Therefore, despite the best intentions of science policy-makers and some funders and administrators, it will take much more than stated good intentions to overcome these forces of inequality within academia and the scientific community, which manifest in systemic, interactional, and unconscious ways.

In global terms, our findings demonstrate that the legacy of imperialism between the global north and south, and most relevant to this case, between European nations and those of Africa and Asia, maintains structures of inequality that manifest in a globalized Matthew effect, as well as other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage. The practice of ‘data siphoning’, a term redefined by P18 to signal the history of data being taken away from African communities by Western scientists, is representative of a globalized Matthew effect. In this case, positionally privileged and comparatively wealthy Western scientists (who are predominantly white and male, as demonstrated by the data cited above), gather data (a valuable resource) in Africa, and bring it back to their home institutions where they profit from it (financially, in terms of career status and salary, as well as research funding) and benefit from it (in terms of career progression, reputation and professional standing). Meanwhile, the communities from which the data was taken are left with nothing accessible or usable; they are at a loss for having participated. In fact, they may be offered the opportunity to purchase access to their data, in the best-case scenario. This process mirrors the historic and present day extraction of multitudinous resources by Westerners/Northerners from the African continent (as well as from Asia and Latin America) that creates ‘unjust enrichment’ and ‘unjust impoverishment’ (to borrow terminology from George Lipsitz (2018)). Other examples offered by our participants, including the unidirectionality of research funding and fieldwork between the global north and south, and the fact that

⁷ It is worth noting that the authors were unable to find data or published research that demonstrates academic rank by race or ethnicity in the EU, nor were we able to find that which reports on academic salary by race/ethnicity in the EU. Rather, as per the evidence presented in Claeys-Kulik, Jørgensen, and Stöber (2019), it appears that hardly any effort is being made to track the compensation of staff on the basis of ethnic or cultural background. Ergo, we would like to remind the reader that the absence of evidence does not equal the evidence of absence.

Western researchers must lead the way in authoring publications based on participatory work so that “others” can be taken seriously (as described by P9 in Chapter 4), also illustrate a globalized Matthew effect.

Therefore, our findings, taken together with existing literature, demonstrate that the Matthew effect and other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage are present in academic and scientific communities, and that there are demonstrative knock-on effects in terms of the exclusive or inclusive nature of research teams, research design, the science-policy interface, and the participation of the public in policy-making. In light of this reality, some of our participants described how they work to share their accrued power, privilege, knowledge, skills, access and resources to help their colleagues develop access to the science-policy interface. This means, then, that when researchers seek to diversify their research teams, in terms of the diversity of scientific researchers but also in terms of including non-scientific experts, that they are actively broadening access and participation. Therefore, when they are not doing this, or when they are only doing this work with people who already have access to their research environment (like junior researchers or similarly positioned colleagues), then the impact of this work is limited and may in fact only support the development of scientific researchers who are already in privileged positions. We observe among our participants distinctly different approaches in this regard, and note that it is participants who embrace and articulate a feminist, post-colonial and/or strongly participatory approach, that are doing this work in ways that truly expand and diversify their research teams. P15 put it in distinctly gendered terms when she explained that the approach she takes to foster inclusion and collaboration is specifically designed to resist the “patriarchal” institutional norms within academic and scientific communities that have historically limited access and participation to (white) men, and that have contributed to the persistence of the Matthew effect.

In terms of other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage, beyond the Matthew effect, our findings show that the participation of marginalized communities in the production of scientific knowledge, the science-policy interface, and in policy-making is itself marginal (and struggling, given that it is achieved through a marginalized form of research). Even when research is guided by OS and RRI principles, if a strongly participatory approach is not taken, then direct access and participation by marginalized groups are (most often) lacking. This occurs not just because the approach to research that achieves this is conducted by a minority of scientific researchers, but also because this work is hard to do. With inadequate and inflexible funding, including the world’s poorest and most vulnerable people is challenging at best and impossible at worst. The digital divide manifests here as a resource barrier. Take, for example, the research projects recounted by P17 which relied on smartphone and smartwatch technology to facilitate co-creative, CS projects. Without funding to support this type of work, including marginalized and vulnerable populations in these projects would not have been possible. Instead, a researcher who wanted to conduct such a project would be forced to select participants who already have access to these costly consumer electronics, which by default would mean including already privileged people in the research. This reality echoes an existing critique of CS approaches to research that have tended to rely on the participation of citizens with relative wealth and resources (Herschan et al. 2020; Oti et al. 2019). Additionally, our participants who use the strongly participatory method observed in our co-creation workshop that the COVID-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on the conduct of research with marginalized groups because of their lack of access to consumer electronics and/or lack of acculturation to online meetings. This manifestation of the digital divide has made it more difficult to include marginalized groups. Further, our participants recounted the challenges of connecting with precarious workers and those that speak isolated or dying languages. Taken together with these other examples, it is again clear that without funding to support these activities, inclusion of the most marginalized people is impossible. Therefore, while some of our participants demonstrated great success in

involving marginalized groups in the science-policy interface and processes of policy-making, it's clear that they are in the minority of scientific researchers. (What's not clear is whether they are in the minority of RRI researchers; a question which would require a quantitative study of RRI research design and methods to answer.) In turn, this means that only a small fraction of marginalized people is able to participate in the policy-making process. This continuing problem of exclusion means that the relatively wealthy and privileged continue to benefit by having their interests represented in this sphere, while the most disadvantaged are further disadvantaged by their continuous exclusion from these processes.

5.6.3. Conclusion

Cumulatively, the findings presented in this chapter suggest that access to and representation within scientific knowledge production, the science-policy interface and policy-making processes continue to be controlled by an elite minority of actors located within academic institutions, funding bodies, and science policy realms. Whether intentional or subconscious, guided by an ideology that justifies their wealth and elite status, this small group of elite actors are working to preserve their power and status by reifying institutional values, norms and practices that reproduce the unequal status quo on local, national and global scales. In doing so, they are actively excluding the majority of society from access to and participation in scientific knowledge production, the science-policy interface, and policy-making. Given the way that stratification within academic and scientific communities mirrors that of society, these results are not surprising. Yet, at the same time, they present a critical problem to the proponents of OS and RRI. They suggest that those hoping to maximize the societal benefits of these paradigms must take a critical look at the way that their approach to research shapes dynamics of inclusion and exclusion. It is clear that representation in a traditional multi-stakeholder approach is not enough. The most impactful work, in terms of fostering equality of access and representation is being created by a strongly participatory approach to research.

The trend of alignment of positionality (in terms of race, gender and geography) with the research approach suggested by our data raises the question of whether such a trend bears out in large-scale, quantitative terms. This presents an opportunity for further research that specifically examines the way that positionality and relative privilege impact research approach within OS and RRI, and thereby, participation of marginalized communities in scientific knowledge production, the science-policy interface, and policy-making.

6. Findings (4): Intermediaries' experiences of Open Science and RRI in uptake of research in policy-making

6.1. Introduction

OS has been defined as “transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks” (Vicente-Saez and Martinez-Fuentes 2018). It is a varied movement to reform research through more transparent and participatory practices including OA to publications, research data sharing, opening research methods and processes, new means of transparent research evaluation, and the re-orientation of research to be more inclusive of and responsive to the needs of society and industry (Pontika et al. 2015). It has been suggested that aspects of OS will help by making scientific resources more readily available to policy-makers and other policy actors (Olesk, Kaal, and Toom 2019; Tennant et al. 2016; Willinsky 2003; 2004). To date, however, few studies have closely examined the extent to which the enabling of access influences uptake, or the drivers and barriers which may support or confound such use.

This chapter aims to address this gap by examining the experiences and opinions on this matter of our cohort of researchers who act as intermediaries and “knowledge-brokers” in policy processes, including how they understand and enact principles of OS in their own work and the relationship between OS and RRI. RRI is a science policy movement, especially prominent in Europe, which seeks to better integrate science with society (Owen, Macnaghten, and Stilgoe 2012; Schomberg 2019). As we shall see, although awareness of RRI as a distinct agenda was generally low amongst our participants, especially those from outside Europe, respondents were very receptive to its stated aims. Amongst those who were familiar, RRI was defined primarily as involving societal actors in research to optimise outcomes for the societal good.

The chapter is structured as follows: (1) first we report on our participants' views on various elements of OS, especially as they may influence the uptake of scientific evidence in policy-making; (2) we then move on to report their views on RRI, with a particular focus on how RRI fosters normative elements of scientific practice seen as somewhat lacking in OS; (3) finally, we report their views on general or framework conditions which they believe affect the uptake of both OS and RRI, especially for those working within university contexts.

6.2. Open Science at the science-policy interface

Asked for their overall impressions of OS, all respondents reported being generally in favour of its values such as accessibility, transparency and participation. Some registered a somewhat vague optimism that OS may help with uptake of scientific information in policy-making. This depended heavily on their definition of OS, however. In the words of one participant whose research work takes place on behalf of a trade union:

I don't know, at that moment how we can use this Open Science approach to make our local union leaders to understand that [climate] changes will be happening based on the scientific evidence and how they will use those evidence to influence their policymakers to secure their jobs or to reskill and retrain the workers to the renewable energy sectors. I'm still thinking how we can utilise this Open Science to influence policymakers. But I think there's many possibilities out there. (P16, health workshop)

In general, as we shall see, narrow definitions of OS as merely enabling transparency in and access to research products and processes were seen as only marginally helpful, while the collaborative and participatory aspects of OS, if fully embraced, were seen as most potentially fruitful. In this first subsection we report these findings according to specific themes, including elements of OS such as OA, Open/FAIR data and CS, as well as general thematic issues such as translation and knowledge-transfer, transparency and trust in research, to reflect on how a focus on mere physical access rather than the enabling of cognitive access (making findings intelligible and relevant to a range of stakeholders) limits the uptake of OS and impacts who potentially benefits.

6.2.1. Open Access and uptake amongst policy-makers

Amongst our respondents there was general support for the broad aims of OA, and some weak evidence that OA may foster uptake of scientific evidence in policy-making. P7 reported in the climate workshop, for example, that especially for those in developing countries, it is sometimes difficult for policy-makers to access non-OA scientific literature. They even reported having been contacted by policy-makers from the Ministry in their home country in the global north asking, “can you help us with accessing this article because we actually don’t have access” (P7, climate workshop). P7 said they hence thought OA “definitely helps”, and later continued:

I definitely think policy-makers have little time. So, if they can click on the paper and open it, they might look at it and they might pick it up. But if they have to find ways to purchase the article or find someone who has login details, it’s much less likely that that would get into the policymaking process. (P7, climate workshop)

In one case, already discussed in depth in Chapter 3, a researcher was contacted by a representative of a political party on the basis of an OA article in a relatively high-profile journal. The respondent speculated that OA could have improved the visibility of the research to instigate this engagement:

[A]ctually I haven’t asked about it. But it could also be that someone from the support staff read this research. I’m not sure. But actually, it’s interesting in a way that actually yes, there is some feedback on, or in some way they are reading scientific papers. (P4, climate workshop)

However, the relative rarity of this interaction visible in the respondent’s surprise that “there is some feedback” suggests that even if OA were a factor, this case is certainly the exception rather than the rule. Rather, respondents suggested that making the scientific literature *physically* accessible is a minor issue compared to making it *intellectually* accessible. In the words of P1:

Policy-makers need to have access to Open Science...? They’re not going to read that stuff. What is important to them is the translation step between stuff being published in academic journals, whether that’s Open Access or not. (P1, interview)

In the climate workshop, P2 said:

When we talk about communicating research results, then it doesn’t necessarily need to be—and maybe it better not be—in terms of peer-reviewed academic journals because who is going to read those? (P2, climate workshop)

Others agreed that OA was important but hardly central in this regard. In their interview, P4 advised:

In some way, yes, I agree it's important. On the other hand, I think the problem is that there's too much information and you just cannot read all the papers anymore. So, maybe Open Science is more important for researchers but for policymakers, it's too much anyway. So, the problem is to know how to filter and how to listen to the trusted sources. (P4, interview)

Respondents' opinion that enabling physical access to primary scientific literature will not greatly empower stakeholders involved in policy processes applied not only to policy-makers but also to other groups, especially publics with lower levels of education:

Yeah, I agree completely with what P13 was saying about the issue of accessibility, for whom we work with diverse stakeholders and putting a peer-reviewed journal article on a platform where you're working with stakeholders that are illiterate—not technically. They don't have the technical knowledge; the message has to be distilled first in order to reach the right audience. So, that's one issue with that. (P9, agriculture workshop)

We will return to the relative importance of cognitive over physical accessibility (Merlo et al. 2015) and will return to this theme later. For now, let us note that our findings here contradict expectations from the scholarly literature that OA to research publications will significantly benefit policy-making. ElSabry's (2017) study of the OA policies of research-funding organisations found that a sixth explicitly mentioned that OA would benefit public sector policy researchers. Already in 2003, Willinsky (2003) noted that paywalls were often mentioned as a difficulty for policy researchers, who largely restricted themselves to OA sources. Willinsky hence foresaw OA as a potential “counterforce to policymakers' reliance on a small number of academic consultants as gatekeepers and sources for research.” In addition, an influential review of the “academic, economic and societal impacts of Open Access” claimed that “if an article has fewer restrictions for journalists, citizens, businesses, and policy-makers, it seems logical that this would enable the research to be publicly re-used. Furthermore, those parties may be more likely to promote articles which are publicly accessible into different communication channels.” The authors of that study concluded that “increased access to scholarly outputs might help foster a culture of greater scientific education and literacy, which in turn could have a direct impact on public policy” (Tennant et al. 2016). Curiously, however, these theories have not been tested in depth since Willinsky's investigation in 2003 to probe how OA affects uptake and use of information amongst policy-makers. Hence, our finding here of intermediaries' experiences of policy-maker practices, which converges with the findings in ON-MERRIT D5.1 (Reichmann et al. 2020) and D5.2 (Correira et al. 2021) of policy-makers' own reports of their behaviours, indicates that OA has a very minor potential value in enabling uptake of research findings. Rather it is the translational work of making science intellectually accessible which is key, a point to which we return later. We will next, however, examine some concerns our participants raised regarding the value of scientific publishing for building trust and legitimacy, and the impact of new business models for OA publications upon their work.

6.2.2. Exclusion in Open Access publishing and issues of legitimacy

Participants, especially in the context of our climate workshop, emphasised the legitimacy conferred by scientific publishing. For example, in speaking of what they called the “political economy of publishing”, one respondent said:

[I]f you do that, then of course it's helpful also for the scientific communication. The incentive to do is [...] that also the impact factor is a part of what builds up reputation [...] But it's a particular incentive of course for researchers to have stuff published in that because it plays an important role for the advancement of their career. The political economy of publishing, I just wanted to say, is an important thing. (P2, climate workshop)

Later in the same workshop, another said:

[T]his is also why in [our institution], even though our mandate is to bridge science and policy, we do publish in the scientific literature because it adds to the trust basis, doesn't it? It gives the credibility that perhaps certain policymakers would expect or otherwise they wouldn't [...] If you're not a university, then this idea that some think tank is politically motivated is very difficult to otherwise get rid of. (P1, climate workshop)

However, in terms of actually influencing policy, respondents usually separated academic impact achieved through peer-reviewed publications from policy impact which was more likely realised via policy briefs. In this regard, the former was often seen as a “nice-to-have” in terms of engagement but still not central, referring back to the necessity of translational work:

[I]n terms of being effective in working at the interface of science and policy, it's probably not the high impact publication that helps unless, maybe it's a Science or a Nature commentary, something very brief and high-level that everybody comes across (P2, climate workshop)

In addition to the issue of intelligibility already flagged, the time that publishing takes was noted as an issue:

[T]he issue of timing that we discussed before, obviously publication, an academic journal takes quite a bit of time, sometimes years before you go through the review process. So, we issue policy briefs or working papers as a way of engaging with policymakers much earlier. (P7, climate workshop)

A further issue that was strongly identified by multiple participants was meeting payments for Article Processing Charges (APC) to make articles OA:

So, when we talk about Open Science publications, the resources involved to have access to those... You had the example of peer-reviewed journals that are run by big transnational publishing houses such as Elsevier, Sage, etc., etc. So, there's a lot of resources involved to get into that. (P2, climate workshop)

This emerged as a major issue in other workshops and interviews. Since this issue relates directly to ON-MERRIT's concern that some actors may be disadvantaged by current OS policies, we quote at length:

Yes, Open Access policies in some cases are anti-Open Science, I think. If you finance also publications because in order to get them in Open Access, this process itself can be negative because still then the publication is the focus. Whether it's Open Access or not Open Access, you reward actually still the publication by financing them in Open Access. It seems this is all about publications, so I always say to universities, why you actually complain so much about the costs of publications, why are you not open a website of your university and let researchers publish on your own website, create your own platform. You

don't need the publishers. Why you don't do it? Why they don't do it? Because they are just too attached to the old system. (P8, interview)

Maybe one more issue is that funding, I think it's very important for Open Access because of course now we want to publish Open Access as well. But for me, when I was a postdoc, it was an issue because I was... some research was driven by my own interest and wasn't within an ongoing project. It was my own initiative or maybe a hobby and then I couldn't publish Open Access because it wasn't a part of a project and I didn't have any funding for publishing Open Access. So, I think this might be an issue for scientists who are in early career or at least earlier stage. Maybe this would be important to... maybe they would need some more additional support for publishing with Open Access. (P4, climate workshop)

For us not every project comes with Open Access. We go through [the institution] to request it and every time you get funds, unless it was already built into the grant, [the institution] sometimes steps forward and pays for certain articles to be published as Open Access but we have to make a case for it. So, I think it definitely is an issue and I would think for other less resourced universities this would be a greater issue. (P7, climate workshop)

There are those imbalances in terms of capacities between within not only the society in general but also within the research and innovation landscape. I'm a bit concerned about that if research policy would not have a clear commitment to support, balancing of those hierarchies within the research funding programs, we would end up with those who have high capacities could take high advantage out of all this Open Access thing. (P13, agriculture workshop)

For those without institutional affiliations this was a major barrier which acted as a disincentive to engage in scientific publication:

[Concerning] the barrier side of it is... this is something we've really run into since we aren't linked to an academic institution that already pays for Open Access.... For example, we had a great research team, a very tight team that put together an amazing article that went through peer review process and was accepted in a high impact journal but the very last step of it... In the past we haven't had these issues because we've been often invited to write articles, this was not an invited article, it was one that we had submitted. The publication fee was around \$6,000 and it's required to be Open Access which is part of our values but there was no way that we could afford that because we have zero budget for publications. We have a very small staff, work volunteer wise and none of our academic affiliations that many of us have were paying for Open Access. So, even though we had a very geographical balanced team, had a lot of LMIC, we went back to the reviewer or the journal and tried to make a case, they only gave us 20% discount and when you take a look at 6,000—20%, yes, it's great but it's not going to make a substantial impact. So, we were really under the threat of not being able to publish that. We were lucky, we had some donor relations and were able to get one donor to sponsor the paper. But again, those relationships were privileged relationships because the team is based... we're based in the US and had relationships to people with that kind of money to donate,

where there's a lot of private donation culture here in the United States. But a lot of our researchers on the team were looking at local resources, local grants, and there was just nothing available. So, I think that it's also about just looking at resource flow in this area and some countries and some places just have a lot of money to put into this stuff. But if you look at, from groups like non-profit organisations, we definitely really struggle. I don't think our struggle is unique to just [organisation]. It's a universal aspect and again, this is probably one of the reasons that non-profit organisations just choose not to engage in research and we're losing out on so much knowledge and expertise because these are the groups that are at the front lines in these communities. Instead of having an outsider research come and try to do a focus group, you could actually learn so much if that was happening in real time. So again, a lot of reasons for why we need to look at this and the challenges we were facing. (P15, health workshop)

These concerns are supported by the literature, which shows that APC-based OA risks stratifications of publishing as well-resourced researchers can cover even the highest APCs while less well-resourced researchers cannot (Pourret et al. 2020; Boudry et al. 2019; Siler et al. 2018; Batterbury 2017; Sotudeh and Horri 2008; Gray 2020; Christian 2008; Davison et al. 2005; Eilers, Crowther, and Harvey 2017; Tennant and Lomax 2019; Monge-Nájera 2018). Even in well-resourced areas like the UK, rising costs (Copiello 2020) of APCs is recognised as an issue which will mitigate OA's net benefits (Jubb et al. 2017). Although many publishers offer fee-waivers and discounts to authors unable to pay, restrictive terms and administrative burden, as well as the extent to which they seemingly place authors in the position of asking for “charity”, undermine their utility (Lawson 2015; Burchardt 2014). This may have effects on specific demographics. For instance, Niles et al. (2020) found that women tend to take cost into consideration significantly more than do men when deciding where to publish. This issue is made especially pressing by the citation advantages linked to OA publishing (Tennant et al. 2016; Ottaviani 2016). Usually seen as an important driver for motivating OA, in the light of equity such an advantage may in fact merely further fuel a classic Matthew effect, privileging those actors with the resources to pay for OA in the most prominent journals.

Hence, to the extent that actors from outside the academic system or those without access to resources, like those working in independent research institutes, cannot access funds they are potentially excluded from OA publishing and hence the legitimacy afforded evidence through its association with peer-reviewed publication. Although scientific publishing is often seen as of higher concern for the career progression of those within the academic system, with more informal forms of communication like policy briefs and personal contact preferred as ways to reach policy-makers, obviously it is still very important for building reputation (see Chapter 4). If it is the case that barriers to OA publishing from APC discourage publication, those from outside the system or less well-resourced are potentially excluded from this legitimacy.

6.2.3. Translation and filtering of information

We have seen in the case of OA publications that our participants thought they were somewhat helpful but hardly sufficient for fostering research uptake in policy-making. This led to a discussion of the work needed, once evidence had been created, to translate and filter that into forms most easily received by the various stakeholders, including policy-makers:

I agree it [Open Science] is important. On the other hand, I think the problem is that there's too much information and you just cannot read all the papers anymore. So, maybe Open Science is more important for researchers but for policymakers, it's too much anyway. So,

the problem is to know how to filter and how to listen to the trusted sources. (P4, interview)

What became clear, however, was that this translational work is itself an expert activity and that better resourced institutions are here potentially primed to benefit. Many participants from global north institutions reported distinct roles having been created. One respondent from an institute affiliated with a prestigious university, whose mission is to influence policy-making through their research, reported that their institute had a dedicated policy and communications team, including a “Head of Translation”, who “actually help[s] in the design of research”, helping to put “scientific findings into the language and format that is digestible for policymakers”, and then “proactively promote our research outputs in the media and social media, in various policy-making forums” (P7, climate workshop).

The important role of the traditional media as well as social media in this translational work was acknowledged. Collaboration with institutional press or public relations departments was flagged as key:

[N]ot only writing, publishing papers but also being in touch or maybe also doing ourselves like also social media contributions and blog contributions or some newspaper articles based on our scientific papers. Some we can do ourselves, but some also can be done in collaboration with other non-scientist persons. There may be press department at our organisations are very important for supporting such work. (P4, climate workshop)

Here again, resources seemed key:

I think it's an important role ... is training also, to train academics to actually be comfortable to talk to media. A lot of my colleagues and myself included, I hate talking to the media. Or I did until I received proper training on how to deal with it. The same goes for policy-making. (P7, climate workshop)

P2 suggested that such dedicated support structures are often the result of changes in the policies of research funders and governments to require more evidence of societal engagement, reflecting on how such framework conditions influence the practices of researchers:

[I]t could also be a longer or a medium-term effect of the research assessment exercises, where you have to demonstrate that your research is important socially and not just about whatever, some nice ideas. Maybe then also universities engage in even changing their internal structures to address that need—which again, just to address the more general point is a question of the institutional settings in which all of this is taking place and what dynamics are involved there, so that we don't just see the science and the policy world but also the broader institutional setups that really, I think play quite a significant role. (P2, climate workshop)

The issue of translation and filtering applies not only to policy-makers, however. For many of our participants working directly with communities, making that knowledge directly accessible to those communities was of key importance. Here again, the issue is of how to put that knowledge in intelligible forms—especially difficult where dealing with differing levels of education and technical competences:

I think Open Science is not only for the expert or the policymakers but what is important is how the less educated people can understand the situation. (P16, interview)

[I]f you're talking about accessibility, you always need to talk or to consider for whom—and I'm not sure if this is appropriately operationalised as if it is done right now, as P11 said. Anyone who would be interested in or who would like to engage with research, I think that's not the case. (P13, agriculture workshop)

Yeah, I agree completely with what P13 was saying about the issue of accessibility, for whom we work with diverse stakeholders and putting a peer-reviewed journal article on a platform where you're working with stakeholders that are illiterate—not technically. They don't have the technical knowledge; the message has to be distilled first in order to reach the right audience. So, that's one issue with that. (P9, agriculture workshop)

Summarising this, we can say that to maximise impact, knowledge must be made not only physically but also cognitively accessible to all stakeholders. However, achieving this is self-evidently a resourceful activity. A dominant theme in our data so far is that enabling access is not enough and this is also the case for societal impact. In policy uptake of scientific knowledge, for example, it has been suggested that OS will help by making scientific resources more readily available to policy-makers and other policy actors (Olesk, Kaal, and Toom 2019; Tennant et al. 2016; Willinsky 2003). However, such uncritical narratives of openness fail to address structural barriers in knowledge production. Firstly, more high-profile OA output from established actors may lead to further over-representation of knowledge produced by dominant groups (ElSabry 2017; Hillyer et al. 2017; Okune et al. 2016). Perhaps more importantly, though, in addition to access, as described at length in Chapter 4, relationships between academics and policy-makers are a main factor in policy uptake of science (cf. Oliver, Lorenc, and Innvær 2014). Policy-makers, with limited time to make decisions and to seek advice heuristically rely on (personal) networks of experts that have previously contributed to policy-making (Dodson, Geary, and Brownson 2015). Researchers' and intermediaries' translation are particularly important in this regard (Gold 2009), with tailored messages a key driver of uptake (Boyko, Kothari, and Wathen 2016). Building relationships and fine-tuning messaging require time and effort and can be significantly bolstered by support structures within research-performing institutions (Abekah-Nkrumah et al. 2018). Hence, researchers with access to such support are advantaged in ensuring uptake.

Again, the most well-resourced stand to benefit most. Ironically, this fact extends even to the demonstration of impact. As Bornmann (2017) points out, institutional societal impact is often assessed based on case-studies which are “expensive and time-consuming to prepare.” This all suggests that uptake of scientific knowledge, even in an age of OS, remains prone to dynamics of cumulative advantage.

We can also raise a further point, which is that the translational model arguably applies best to the linear and interactive models of the science-policy interface (c.f. Chapter 1). Rather than a limited model of knowledge-production where science is produced and must then be packaged in the most fitting form, in a participatory or embedded model, where there is increased emphasis on participatory formats of societal engagement which foster discursive processes between researchers, policy-makers and other stakeholders, then it may be the case that greater shared understanding is assured from the start. We return later to these themes of upstream engagement to ensure understanding from the beginning. For now, we will move on to Open Data and perceptions of transparency and trust.

6.2.4. Open/FAIR data

We next consider participants' thoughts on the potential for Open Data to facilitate uptake of science in policy-making. Here, our participants reported some hope that opening access to research datasets might

help enable research uptake and empower decision-making on specific issues amongst policy-makers. This is especially pertinent for those dealing with communities in developing countries, where a wealth of research data generated in those contexts is no longer accessible to the involved communities:

There's actually quite a lot of research projects that have collected data. But these data have not been made available for decision-making ... We have many cases where we know that different science groups have data, for example, on air pollution but they can't make it available to government when government wants this data as part of the decision-making because they're not expected to do that. But this data might find its way to other international institutions, and you have to then purchase it at a very high cost and so on. (P12, interview)

Another participant continued this sentiment, terming it “data siphoning” and advising it leads to duplication of research and lack of effective data for decision-making in the countries of origin:

I feel for my people. When we look back twenty years and we cannot find data ... we are forever—because of lack of data—quite rotating in a very small circle ... trust me some of the things that people are thinking are like 'aha', are not new. I used to see projects doing that twenty years plus, but where is the data? The data is in the United States somewhere because we had to report.... [G]oing forward, if the world wants to make a meaningful change we cannot play around with data. Knowledge management is weak ... [I]f you don't have facts ... plans are very weak because we have poor data gaps. So, in terms of data siphoning perspective, the world of development partners needs to feel very ashamed that there is one partner who has more credible data about any country than the other. Data for Africa, Asian nations, we need to make sure that the same set of quality information is what we also are seeing if then we are to take development to the next level.... Can people understand what is in need for them to collect this data and can we be ethical and responsible enough to exactly give them back that benefit that we say we are going to give them. I mean, data siphoning here, when I use it and I know that's a very strong sentiment, I am brute about it because we need to do a good job. Otherwise, we are messing up, we've messed up the environment. It's so difficult for advocates to get data so that we can help our people. (P18, interview)

P18 even reported that such perceptions of data siphoning can discourage policy-makers from collaborating:

What increasingly I hear as an advocate, we have a problem in convincing our decision-makers today. If you share credible data with us, it's for our own use. We are not being engines to send it to another place. We would like to work with you—that has brought that tension where, 'No, no, we are tired of giving our data because we know where you guys take it.' So, changing that narrative to 'Trust us, let's work together, this data is actually useful here.' (P18, interview)

However, our participants also flagged a wealth of cognitive, social and political issues that potentially limit the power of open data.

Firstly, just as with our above discussion of how making scientific publications physically accessible is not sufficient but must be accompanied by measures to support cognitive accessibility, making data

understandable to affected communities was seen as crucial. Referencing how to bring scientific information on dangers of asbestos to industrial workers in South Asian countries, one participant said:

My question ... [is] how we can deliver this scientific evidence or data on occupational health and safety to uneducated workers because those workers cannot read, cannot access internet, most of them do not have smartphones. This is I think the challenge because there's a literacy gap between the vulnerable workers ... So, I think that our challenge in the future is that how to make this scientific evidence or data will be easily available or easy to understand by those uneducated, the workers on the ground, especially in the developing countries. (P16, health workshop)

Similarly, P18 reflected on the women she engaged with to generate data about quality of care in villages to state:

[D]ata is about people's voices. It's about people's experiences. So, we can't have these disconnects and I don't want to be talking for my women. I want them to be able to understand what facts mean and when they see an abuse and when they see success and how to celebrate it and how to call it out. (P18, interview)

Next, another respondent flagged potential difficulties in making participant data containing personal data open:

[I]n general Open Access is good and open data is good but with some personal data it is actually problematic. Maybe not all data can be then Open Access. (P4, climate workshop)

This complemented a concern flagged by another participant that OS must also respect historical and situational contexts:

I think it's not as simplistic as one assumes and that we're working in contexts where democratic processes are not the norm or the custom and we're trying to impose participation on groups of people that are not used to participation.... [E]ven something as basic as asking for consent is a very Western way of doing research. If you go to someone in [a country with a history of military rule] and ask them, is it okay if I take in this information from you, I'll share it and I'll not share it, etc., etc., they get frightened because they're not used to being asked this question. They're not used to, oh my God—thinking what is going to happen to the words that I say. Historical contexts have ensured that these systems of non-consent and oppression are in place, so it's very hard for us to go and say that this practice of research, as great that this is, it should be implemented in this way. (P9, interview)

P9 is here reporting her experience that contexts of post-colonialism and authoritarianism, combined with experiences of structural racism or sexism, influence willingness to participate in scientific processes. Making those processes open, even with strict guarantees of anonymity, may hence further inhibit willingness to participate amongst some in those communities.

Finally, participants raised issues of what we may term “strategic openness”. This applied especially to those working with the academic system, for whom the pressure to publish academic papers may inhibit willingness to share data. As P8 advised, the system of incentives in academia currently means that scientists may be strategic in when to make their data open (if at all) to ensure priority in publication:

If you as a researcher want to practice Open Science, then you will experience that actually your practice is penalised in a system rather than incentivised. It's penalised because if you want to share your data early or your knowledge early that means that maybe somebody else can publish it at your cost that your career is determined by whether you have a good publication in a high impact or whatever. (P8, interview)

These findings echo the literature on the subject, which suggests that the proposed benefits of Open Data are often dissociated from specific research contexts. Here, some suggest that the Open Data movement has overestimated the homogeneity of research environments (Olmos-Peñuela, Benneworth, and Castro-Martínez 2015), resulting in a generalised “assumption that all scientists will benefit from releasing data, no matter where they are based” (Rappert and Bezuidenhout 2016). Such an assumption fails to appreciate that conditions for making data available differ across disciplines (Borgman 2015) and regions (Rappert and Bezuidenhout 2016). Contexts differ depending on issues like the readiness-level of data formats (Weinshall and Epstein 2020) and whether research involves human subjects (Cychosz et al. 2020; Bargh et al. 2019; Ross, Iguchi, and Panicker 2018). For these disciplinary reasons, a blanket appreciation of open data as inherently democratic is problematic (Johnson 2014; Johnson 2018). Data inequalities are also cumulative, shaped by individual and community characteristics, access to infrastructure, and political and economic factors (Cinnamon 2020, 218), affecting the abilities of different groups to partake in the ‘gift economy’ (Klump 2017) of academia. As ethnographies of (non-Western) research (Bezuidenhout et al. 2017) show, access is not enough to guarantee the utility of Open Data because the latter requires resources such as skills, money, and computing power (Johnson 2018). Those working in environments where these are in short supply can fear that opening data sets will put them at a disadvantage (L. Bezuidenhout et al. 2017; L. M. Bezuidenhout et al. 2017; Rappert and Bezuidenhout 2016). Making use of Open Data is also closely linked to data literacy, potentially marginalising those that cannot engage with data effectively (Atenas, Havemann, and Timmermann 2020; Yoon and Copeland 2019; D’Ignazio and Bhargava 2018). If so, the landscape of open data may not be the democratisation of knowledge, but just a further mechanism whereby the rich get richer.

6.2.5. Transparency and trust

The ways in which transparency in OS may foster trust also emerged as an important theme for many participants. There was recognition that opening data may deepen trust in research for which there are perceived conflicts of interest, for instance in ensuring reporting of all medical and pharmaceutical trials including negative results: “you have access to all the data that is produced and all the research results that are produced” (P14, health workshop). In the words of other participants:

[I]n terms of transparency and making data available: We all know that most of our research that have been published, even in most of these renowned journals, they never ask for the data. But yet they have been reviewed by experts, following just the methods that we have outlined. But yet, as one of the discussants already said, you may be getting funding from a company or from somebody who will make you skew your data towards what the donor actually wants. So, once that data is available, people can actually have that data interpreted in so many ways. How now do you give that trust in Open Science in terms of all the people that are out there while the data have not been reviewed by the reviewers? That's a major issue now of trust and data. (P5, climate workshop)

I mean, closed science doesn't work in the end as well and that's what you also see with vaccines. I mean, this is one of the reasons why second stage clinical trials for ninety percent of the cases fail, is because companies work in secrecy, and they don't share their data and information. (P8, interview)

However, the limits of such transparency and how they can affect trust arose in an illuminating contribution from P1. In this case, anti-climate-change activists used the lack of what may be referred to as tacit knowledge about how the data was analysed to advocate that the data could not be trusted:

I remember that discussion in the US at the time when the access to data, there was a discussion about what form the data would need to be in, whether that was the raw data or processed data. I think raw data can be made available but processed data, that of course includes the knowledge and skill of the analyst and that wasn't made available and that then was twisted into a trust issue. I think what it came down to, about reproducibility of science requires that those who want to reproduce also have similar skills and knowledge to actually do that. I think this was a typical debate that was going about these elitist scientists were not willing to share their data even though what they did share was the raw data but not the processed one, because there's of course also often a competitive element in research. Even though the methods and so on are transparent, I guess there are limits to what you can actually share without basically making all the work that you've done redundant. (P1, climate workshop)

In this case, there also seemed to be a related dimension of strategic openness, wishing to maintain some competitive advantage by keeping certain methods of analysis confidential. The case demonstrates the tensions in transparency and trust. Full transparency is not possible. Each opening of some data or methods is a decision to leave some closed, and motivations for these decisions can always be questioned.

As a related issue, transparency of funding was also mentioned as a potential positive for groups seen as potentially partisan:

The idea of a think tank is that it's some kind of partisan lobby organisation, and I guess many are, which is also why we don't really like using that term. But yeah, we try to be very transparent as an organisation but also in individual projects as to where the money comes from and what we'd like to achieve; trying to be transparent in who we select as stakeholders if we have stakeholder engagement. I think all of that is and should be part of research integrity. (P1, climate workshop)

Finally, transparency in peer review of funding proposals was also seen as important:

As you've been talking about funding mechanisms, there is also this issue of transparency in regard to peer review processes and funding allocation as core practices. This is also super narrow because this is not the meeting the core of how to steer research and innovation, this is research agendas, and this is completely untransparent how the researchers' agendas are set up. Maybe even more transparent on the European level compared to if you go down to other policy levels, national or even regional level, completely untransparent. So far away from Open Science and that's not addressed here, the agenda setting, which is paving the way for anything else which is happening afterwards. (P13, agriculture workshop)

The excerpts in this section are very insightful with respect to how what is perceived as evidence, and how evidence is perceived, is shaped by non-epistemic factors like reputation, perceived bias or conflicts of interest. Here transparency is seen as an important means of mitigating distrust and enabling confidence in the epistemic worth of the evidence.

6.2.6. Citizen Science

Given the general theme of participation in policy-making, CS also emerged as an important theme for discussion. Strengthening the relationship between science and society is a key pillar of OS. CS seeks to foster inclusion in knowledge production by involving the public in scientific processes. Practices range from research where the public contribute data to scientific projects via crowdsourcing platforms, to “extreme citizen science” or “strongly participatory science”, wherein members of the public participate in all aspects of research and are able to make valuable use of the research results in ways that benefits their lives and communities (English, Richardson, and Garzon-Galvis 2018; Allen 2018). It is the latter, rooted in traditions of participatory research, that most directly and strongly challenges the dynamics of inequality within academia (Morales-Doyle and Frausto 2020; English, Richardson, and Garzon-Galvis 2018).

CS approaches were mentioned by some of our participants as potentially positive in driving upstream engagement by including communities to understand their most pressing concerns to drive problem formulation:

[W]ithin my team, there's, my background is in participatory mapping and participatory GIS [Global Information Systems], which involves using maps as a way of creating dialogue between local communities typically and collecting information in a way that can be transformed into a form that decision-makers, policymakers can understand. But then we've also got Citizen Science people ... where our particular speciality is identifying the problems the communities are interested in, and then collecting information relevant to that or Citizen Science processes relevant to that rather than going in with a 'we would like to talk to you or we would like you to help us understand or collect data on air pollution', when they're most interested in water quality. (P17, health workshop)

Another element of CS is the mobilisation of communities to crowd-source data collection. P17 raised a case, however, in which the crowd-sourced nature of data collected via CS methods was used to delegitimise data seen by policy-makers as inconvenient with respect to their policy goals:

So, it's Citizen Science, at its most fundamental of residents collecting data for themselves to then use in their own process. But I know the city authorities found that really challenging for two reasons. One was because they questioned the validity of those measurements because the pollution sensors aren't actually very good, most of them. The data the residents were collecting wasn't accurate enough for any—what's the word—legal process or legal challenge. Also, they just found that whole engagement using a scientific basis is threatening or challenging to them and their authority on the topic of air pollution but also transport planning and the plans for the city. So, they did engage with those people to try and as I said inform them about the problems with the sensors and why the data they collected couldn't be used in any legal basis to challenge a planning application. But rather than finding that helpful, I think they wished it just would go away. So, I think there is that contradiction of you'd hope that opening up all of these kinds of approaches to better understand, say conditions in the city, would lead to better policy

and planning and decision-making. But potentially, I think it just introduces new lines of conflict for people between communities and authorities. (P17, interview)

This was in the context of a local policy decision regarding measures to improve air quality that potentially could impact planning for a new development and hence economic growth and development. In this case, the use of communities as data-collectors was problematic both because the instruments used were open to question, but also because, as P17 expanded upon later, the findings derived from this data on air quality would challenge a contrary policy-goal to build new homes:

It's which policy and which development goal takes precedent, I guess, and in that context, it was an annoyance that there was any challenge to that national goal to having x number of new homes within the city by a certain time period. They didn't want that challenge. (P17, interview)

The political nature of this framing is clear. The data was open to question as a result of its collection methods, but the fact that policy-makers did question it seems heavily related to its political inconvenience. Had the data supported the goal of building more homes, policy-makers may have been much more accepting of it. Policy-makers disputed citizens' data because their results were not in alignment with the policy goals (cf. Chapters 3 and 4 for the importance of congruence). Had the data come from scientists (legitimate scientists), they might still have disputed their relevance, but given that the data came from citizens, policy-makers had an easier job of disputing its validity which made reaching their policy aims easier.

P14 raised another issue in their interview, namely that because CS is currently fashionable, it is often adopted for reasons of political expediency which leads to only the token involvement of communities:

Nowadays, the emphasis is very strongly on Citizen Science in terms of involving the public already in the research process, and this is a good development but can also be token participation. (P14, interview)

In the climate workshop, P2 also raised concerns about "tokenism" and uncritical assumptions that all CS approaches will improve equity in representation in the interface between science and policy:

But the idea that stakeholders and the aggregation of stakeholders and equality or greater equity among those stakeholders might help improve the representation of public interest is full of assumptions. I mean, you have mediations here and you have translations here and you also have deliberations about what exactly is an interest, the norm. So, that I find really tricky about the representation. I think it's then also different in the world of research when you talk about Open Science, or we had Citizen Science. Again, there the question also what's the relevance of representation there? What kind of contribution do we then expect? What kind of access is it about? (P2, climate workshop)

According to the literature, ideally participatory research should be directed by a self-reflexive, critical, ethics-focused approach to research design, conduct, distribution of labour (Timmermann 2019) and financial benefits (Saleh et al. 2020; Kumar 2019; Timmermann 2019), outputs and impacts (Godrie et al. 2020; Kumar 2019; O'Leary 2018; Burke and Heynen 2014; Saleh et al. 2020). Questions of equality, justice and equity are often centred (Ottinger 2017; Kumar 2019; Hendricks et al. 2018; O'Leary 2018; Raphael 2019; Allen 2018) and the knowledge produced reflects the lived experience and situated expertise of the participants and communities upon which the research is focused (Morales-Doyle and Frausto 2020; Mena et al. 2020; Holzmeyer 2019; Allen 2018). Further, those that participate in CS and participatory projects

develop scientific expertise that would otherwise be unavailable to them, making them more effective democratic actors who are able to challenge policies, civic expertise, and corporate power in pursuit of justice and equality (Kimura and Kinchy 2016; O’Leary 2018; Krings, Kornberg, and Lane 2019; Allen 2018; Misonne 2020; Eymard 2020; Barzyk et al. 2018; Hendricks et al. 2018).

Here we can see that CS has a potential role in engaging the public in scientific processes and thereby facilitating engagement in policy creation. However, levels of engagement can vary and, from the contributions of our participants regarding tokenism, we can see that merely instrumental uses of CS may not greatly improve the situation. Indeed, CS has been criticised by some as also, in some circumstances, perpetuating inequalities. When participants serve merely as free data collectors, those who primarily benefit are researchers (Vercammen et al. 2020; Derrien et al. 2020; Prudic et al. 2019; Burke and Heynen 2014). Where such practices bridge the global north and south, data extraction absent anything else echoes colonial exploitation (Saleh et al. 2020). Additionally, there are issues of biased inclusion in terms of the populations that are invited to participate in traditional CS (Herschman et al. 2020; Oti et al. 2019), with the most marginalized groups likely to be left out (Derrien et al. 2020; Friedrich, Reichel, and Renkert 2020; Vercammen et al. 2020; Katapally 2019). Likewise, there is biased participation in the crowdsourcing of information (Bright, De Sabbata, and Lee 2018). Finally, approaches taken by well-intentioned researchers may also reinforce existing inequalities, like when a paternalistic stance is taken towards participants (see the use of “provide voice” in Hendricks et al. 2018); research seeks to prove the quality and validity of citizen-generated data, thereby reifying the expertise divide between scientists and the public (Vercammen et al. 2020; Ottinger 2017; Derrien et al. 2020); or when science education is framed as a unidirectional resource coming strictly from scientists (e.g., Beattie, Hippenmeyer, and Pauler 2020). All these have implications for equity in CS relating back to ON-MERRIT’s themes of how cumulative advantage can impact participation in OS, especially related to issues of digital divide, differential levels of resources and skills, and data equity. Again, it is non-dominant actors who are at risk. Shelley-Egan et al. (2020) criticise such instrumentalisation of participants as demonstrating that in OS, “publics operate as citizen scientists collecting or systematising data without necessarily reflecting on or critiquing the broader institutional and societal frameworks for uptake.”

Hence, we should be alert to possible negative effects of overly-instrumentalist implementations of CS, and constantly ask whose voices are represented in CS projects, and for which reasons? Is CS always challenging the normative dimensions of the ivory-tower model of academia, and if not, should it be? We will examine such questions further in the following section, where we discuss the relationship between OS and RRI.

6.2.7. Subsection summary

In this subsection we have reported our participants’ views on OS, especially with regard to its potential to reshape the science-policy interface. We saw that, contrary to some optimistic claims, OS perhaps has only a limited potential to do so if it is focussed too narrowly on enhancing accessibility and transparency of research. Although OS may have some impact in enabling access to policy-makers, and opening data could help transparency and trust in research, our participants highlighted issues with exclusion from OA publishing caused by the APC-model of OA (especially for those outside universities) and in translating this information into forms cognitively accessible to stakeholders. The dimensions of participation enabled by CS were seen as most potentially useful, but here a sometimes narrowly instrumental view of what participation means in this context could also prove problematic.

6.3. Views on Responsible Research and Innovation

Our participants also reflected upon the wider aims of what is termed Responsible Research and Innovation, especially how this interrelates or might complement the OS movement. To begin to illuminate the importance of RRI for many participants, we will first report their thoughts on how OS's interactions with industry perhaps reveal it to be lacking a normative dimension which, as examined in the rest of this section, RRI may be able to provide.

6.3.1. Open Science and industry

Many respondents questioned the terms on which OS engages with industry. P1 pointed out that commercial interests and issues of competitiveness changed the context of OS (P1, interview). In the health workshop, P17 argued that there is an asymmetry in the relationship between the two, with industry players under no obligation to engage with OS:

[O]ne thing that's been interesting to me I guess around this whole access to data and openness about data is just the differences between the processes for data collection and then transparency and archiving of data that I have to go through in a university setting versus what commercial companies—particularly that are now collecting huge amounts of data on individuals—how different their processes are and their transparency and openness and access. Obviously, they're collecting it for commercial gain and commercial purposes, but I at the end of a process have to archive it, make it available for future research, anonymise it, all kinds of ethical, very valid processes, the data I'm sharing with various service providers and particularly online sources. I have no concept of where it's going and how it's being used and how it's influencing decisions. It may be a completely different research question, but it's one that occurs to me. (P17, health workshop)

This in turn is reflected by a wider concern that the OS paradigm is not sufficiently critical of the role of the market system per se, and that this may even be its strength in gaining support amongst research policy-makers driven by a need to demonstrate return-on-investment and potential for economic growth. This point was made strongly by three participants in our agriculture workshop:

[O]f course I can see the advantages of Open Science and I would also support it. But when it comes to its operationalisation, I see that it's not aiming at changing something in the system actually, but it's just taking single points and when it comes then to crucial points, then it's simply not relevant. This would be my main criticism on that.... there were also quite substantial economic reasons why they introduced the Open Science, particularly the open data initiatives in order not always to reproduce everything and save resources and money by making it accessible to other research groups as well. But if there is a clear economic interest connected to a certain activity, opting out is not an issue at all. So, this is super high priority and that's tracking me a bit to be honest, because it's not consistent in my point of view. (P13, agriculture workshop)

[T]o me why Open Science is preferred because it's not threatening the system. It's captured by the system; it's well fit into the system. Open innovation was a term also taken by businesses, so it's very much into this market society as I call it, what we are living in and taking up issues of responsibility, genuine ethical responsibility and maybe political responsibility also about our roles and influence, that's more uncomfortable. (P11, agriculture workshop)

With Open Science, the practice of it seems to be very easily commercialised so, maybe that's why there's a drive for that movement. (P9, agriculture workshop)

These points show participants concerned about an issue raised by Fernández Pinto (2020), who argues that current OS policies risk perpetuating the commercialisation of science. Firstly, the focus on opening *publicly* funded research allows industry the “privileged position of adopting openness as they see fit,” adopting openness where it is commercially attractive or improves public image (cf. Leonelli 2013) and ignoring it in less favourable circumstances, such as where findings may impact sales. Secondly, policy focus on OS’s potential to spur innovation means that the science-industry connection is deepened without critical reflection on the “epistemic and social justice challenges” of private sphere research, including scandals in corporate-sponsored scientific research (c.f., McGarity and Wagner 2010; Michaels 2008; Oreskes and Conway 2010), conflicts of interest and their influence on research work (cf. Lundh et al. 2017), and the ways in which strong intellectual property regimes might inhibit or corrupt scientific research (cf. Biddle 2014). For Fernández Pinto, therefore, the issue lies in the unequal terms on which OS engages industry, with the latter privileged. This asymmetry in favour of industry can in turn be seen as an endorsement within OS of the marketization of science and the specific neoliberal vision of the academy which underlies it (cf. Holzmeyer 2019).

In light of this, we should take seriously a strand of critique which links OS to broader trends to reshape the academy under neoliberal principles to emphasise market principles of competition, foregrounding its economic role in training the workforce and fostering new products and services, at the expense of the social mission to provide upward mobility for marginalised populations (Slaughter and Rhoades 2000; Maisuria and Cole 2017; Canaan and Shumar 2008; Mirowski and Sent 2002). For some critics, OS has the potential to merely fuel these developments. In the words of Tyfield (2013), OS’s legacy may be defined by its “effects on the construction of a new moral economy of knowledge production,” meaning the marketisation of science for the benefit of corporations (Tyfield 2013, 29). Similarly, for Mirowski, OS will result in a “platformisation” of science—for-profit firms colonising the research landscape with a host of tools, seeking to construct “the One Platform to Rule Them All” (Mirowski 2018, 197). Such developments could see, in the words of Kansa (2014), the “cause of ‘openness’ subverted to further entrench damaging institutional structures and ideologies.” Certain central assumptions of OS seem to further promote the commodification and marketisation of research. Making science more responsive to the market risks further intensifying competition at the expense of communalism. Not only does this risk lock-in by commercial vendors, but logics of data accumulation and tracking further enframe researchers as something to be measured in a regime of surveillance capitalism. This in turn disadvantages community-focused research that is often dismissed as “care work”, as was discussed in Chapters 4 and 5.

For respondents, then, OS seemingly lacks an ethical directionality, and it is potentially this which makes it so attractive to policy-makers driven, above all, by the promise of economic growth. It is in this light that participants would highlight the particular importance of the normative dimensions of Responsible Research and Innovation.

6.3.2. Normative Dimensions (1): Mission-driven research

Building on such concerns, our participants almost uniformly pronounced themselves in favour of the principles of RRI, especially to foster greater participation of societal actors through increased upstream engagement and responsiveness to local needs (cf. Chapter 5 for ample description of participants’ use of these methods in their own research).

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a science policy movement, especially prominent in Europe, which seeks to better integrate science with society (Owen, Macnaghten, and Stilgoe 2012; Schomberg 2019). Deriving from a tradition of participatory research, Technology Assessment and anticipatory governance, RRI aims to avoid “expert hubris” and unintended consequences. Although awareness of RRI as a distinct agenda was generally low amongst our participants, especially those from outside Europe, respondents were very receptive to its stated aims. Amongst those who were familiar, RRI was defined primarily as involving societal actors in research to optimise outcomes for the societal good. Example:

[F]or me, RRI only works as a concept if it is real with real ethical meaning in terms of social justice and addresses structural issues of domination and all kinds of—and also the political one that relates to this vision of what society we would to live in, basically. These are always uncomfortable questions, much easier to take for granted that we are living in the best possible world and just tinkering with it a bit, but not challenging it. (P11, agriculture workshop)

In this sense, as was pointed out by one participant (P8, interview), OS can be seen as a necessary element of RRI, but OS alone will not ensure responsible outcomes. It was in this context of the normativity of OS, that the need for RRI emerged as a clear theme amongst participants:

With Open Science, the practice of it seems to be very easily commercialised so, maybe that’s why there’s a drive for that movement. But with RRI, there are numerous ways in which different people can interpret these but in principle, I see it as about inclusiveness and equity and hopefully trying to improve the lives of those who are most vulnerable and marginalised. (P9, agriculture workshop)

P8 spoke in a similar vein in their interview, suggesting that greater reforms were needed amongst public authorities to regulate innovation and intellectual property rights and place greater demands upon private-sector partnerships to better align science with society and give better normative constraints and direction to innovation:

[O]ne element of Responsible Research Innovation in distinction to Open Science is that it becomes more value-driven because even Open Science is not necessarily giving a direction to innovation. Although already with Open Science you can achieve already quite a lot because openness, as I said, openness relates also to openness to actors. So, that means that you involve research with other knowledge actors. Be it NGOs or industry or public officers or citizens. But if you include all these other knowledge actors, that means also they have an interest at stake in the process. So, even only by opening up, the chance that you will give innovation more direction is possible. This is also why I say Open Science will make science more responsive to societal developments but not necessarily has the mechanisms to drive innovations towards them. There you need more—and this is my story about responsible innovation—you need to change the conditions on the market. That means for example, the relation between how we deal now with innovations is in a too neutral sense. (P8, interview)

6.3.3. Normative Dimensions (2): Upstream engagement

A key dimension in this regard was the expansion of participatory aspects to fully embrace what is known as “upstream engagement”, bringing stakeholders into research processes from the very start to ensure, for

example, that scientists begin by asking the right questions and funders fund relevant research. P14, for example, said:

Nowadays, it's very fashionable to, we involved them in the research, let's do Citizen Science. It's not only about this, it's also about our political decisions, where does the money go, which kind of research are we funding. Stop doing research on flying to Mars. Stop Mars missions. We need the money for something else. So, it should be public involvement in decision-making on the level of program making, on the level of evaluation of research projects, on the level of... So, it's after acceptance and then it's post-evaluation. So, it should be public engagement along the entire line which doesn't mean that we blur the boundary between lay knowledge and expert knowledge. But it means that there should be an interaction and we should use the entire toolbox we already developed in the last thirty years of doing that. (P14, interview)

P9 argued that such an enhanced normative framing of science as specifically targeting what is beneficial for society will help level power dynamics and avoid what they termed the “elite capture of knowledge”:

Just one aspect. I'm sure others have other comments, is that using a multi-stakeholder participatory approach can equalise the power dynamics between different stakeholder groups so that there is no elite capture of knowledge that one researcher or the policy-maker is the one with the expertise, that everybody can have an opportunity to contribute and in their contribution there is expertise and there is an opportunity to even the power dynamics. (P9, agriculture workshop)

At the same time, such upstream engagement with policy-makers themselves was argued by others to have distinct benefits:

[T]o say that Open Science is beneficial for policy-making, I say... I mean, it's a very minute, very small aspect of it because you have to take that data and engage with the policy-makers. It's not only engaging at the end of the research. It should be right from the beginning in terms of co-creation because when you co-create with them, they will come to discover other issues or problems that they never thought about. (P5, interview)

I mean, the tricky point from RRI and Open Science is of course that you involve policymakers earlier in a process than you normally have. This can happen in different degrees. You can have a radical case in which for example citizens or/and stakeholders with their problem definitions are already part of the research process itself... You will see a massive input of stakeholders and even citizens in defining what actually the research question is and what we should address. So, if you do that then of course that's a radical case and as you maybe have sensed, I'm a radical. So, I like to pursue that route. Of course, that has the advantage that the problem definition itself is co-defined by stakeholders, but this can be a long process. But at the same time, when successful, then of course the influence on policy is also high. But this presupposes an organisation on the side of public authority like the European Commission now is doing with [a] mission-oriented process. But you can have also other degrees. My first point was actually in the beginning, does it fit to the problem definition in [the] existing agenda—this was actually assuming that you are not from an RRI context, but just the question of how scientific information is taken up in policy. Normally, I think in STS circles, it's very often the thought that science

determines very often problem definitions. But my view is actually the other way around. I think policy is relatively resistant towards scientific information. ... I think problem definitions, sometimes they remain implicit. This is a challenge, I think, [that] needs to be articulated and there is always a social-political component in this which requires discussions with everybody. (P8, agriculture workshop)

Our two participants here both attest to the power of bringing policy-makers on board early, not only to enable them to have input into what is important in research, but also for encouraging them to think through issues in new ways and thus potentially make them more receptive to the eventual outcomes of the research. Yet in previous sections we have discussed how policy agendas of particular policy-makers are often somewhat inflexible and that the surest way to ensure uptake is that findings should be congruent with political agendas. P13 discussed the difficulties involved here in the context of research into the local food supply system:

We did it in a project context which was an experimental setting. The experimental setting helped to get the people on board to also engage policy people and to try to think in a different type of approach. But the problem was exactly with the policy agenda. The policy context in reality does not change with that. So, trying to come up with different ways of how to define the problem on the one hand, but on the other hand being embedded in this quite stable policy agenda context which is out there. In our case, it was even only a regional context. I'm not talking about any higher-level governance issues and still that's a super difficult thing because I'm wondering how to bring that from this small group of people, from those single participating policy actors back into the whole policy landscape where they are supposed to act then. (P13, agriculture workshop)

Additionally, in the excerpt presented above, P8 reflected upon the extent to which uptake of information depends upon how evidence fits to the problem definition in existing agendas to suggest that although upstream engagement may delay decision-making, it may strengthen the potential for policy consensus in the long-run.

An important point here was raised by P17 in their interview, namely that changes in this regard also require commitment from policy-makers to also adapt to this new paradigm:

I think with the Open Science thing, I think it needs, to be most effective to my mind it's also requiring a shift in the knowledge from the planners and policy-makers, or not knowledge, a shift in their beliefs about what the role of communities or other stakeholders in processes are. That's potentially quite a change of mindset for them. I think that's probably what's needed to make the most benefit of an Open Science agenda or involvement. (P17, interview)

Despite these difficulties, however, participants attested that this approach can lead to policy success:

[T]o me, I think Open Science is critical but it's not just about publishing or letting information on the internet, but how do you take that information and translate it into policy. We are now engaging in the aspect that we call Citizen Science. It's still part of the co-creation but making sure that all the different stakeholders, especially the society, are involved because before most research was just done without the society and the implication was that when it comes to implementation, they're just saying not in my

backyard, we were not properly consulted, our views were not taken into consideration. The one that is done right at the very beginning, then there's high probability of accepting the whole project, buy-in, and then implementation. That's why we look at it holistically, not just taking bits and pieces and going about them. (P5, interview)

So, having the community involved in the science meant we ended up adopting a larger air quality management area than I think the council officers expected. But also having the people involved in the whole process led to the politicians having confidence that they wouldn't be unelected at the next cycle if they adopted such a big air quality management area. So, I think it can have influence all the way through. (P17, health workshop)

6.3.4. Normative Dimensions (3): Resonant research

Another key aspect of RRI approaches which successfully foreground inclusion of societal actors was what we may term the “resonance” of research outcomes with those communities where knowledge is produced. In our section on Open Data above, we discussed the ways in which some participants with a strongly participatory approach and an almost advocacy-influenced approach to research were heavily motivated to ensure that findings were directly impactful upon the understanding of affected communities. We saw that there are dangers of data-siphoning, with richer organisations taking data but not giving back. However, “giving back” is about more than just making the data available—especially where uptake and understanding amongst affected communities is at issue. Referencing how to bring scientific information on dangers of asbestos to shipbreaking workers in South Asian countries, one participant said:

My question ... [is] how we can deliver this scientific evidence or data on occupational health and safety to uneducated workers because those workers cannot read, cannot access internet, most of them do not have smartphones. This is I think the challenge because there's a literacy gap between the vulnerable workers ... So, I think that our challenge in the future is that how to make this scientific evidence or data will be easily available or easy to understand by those uneducated, the workers on the ground, especially in the developing countries. (P16, health workshop)

Similarly, P18 reflected on the women she engaged with in a developing nation to generate data about quality of care in villages to state:

[D]ata is about people's voices. It's about people's experiences. So, we can't have these disconnects and I don't want to be talking for my women. I want them to be able to understand what facts mean and when they see an abuse and when they see success and how to celebrate it and how to call it out. (P18, interview)

As already stated in previous chapters, transformative processes of inclusive knowledge production are most beneficial for affected social groups where that knowledge is directly useful for them. Acknowledging the political nature of knowledge as a tool of empowerment, we see the immediacy of effects for actors, without requiring policy action through the elite system, as creating tangible benefits within their context of application. As said in the previous chapter, stratification within scientific communities presents a critical problem for proponents of OS and RRI, with strongly participatory approaches rather than traditional multi-stakeholder approaches required to truly foster equity in processes of knowledge production.

The challenges of ensuring such direct resonance within affected communities is hence highlighted by our two participants here. Moreover, we must remind ourselves that just making the data available is not

necessarily enough, especially where uptake and understanding amongst affected communities is at issue. Difficult yet necessary translational work may remain. Yet this is potentially mitigated where communities are engaged in participatory processes from the start. P18 suggested partnerships amongst research stakeholders as one key to aiding this understanding:

The only one thing that I would add into what you said is the principle of partnerships because data does not use itself. It's one thing to earn people accolades and ensure that I have done so much and I published so much. Those who produce data, whether open or not, you have to—there's what I call beginning with an end in mind. Among the many principles of open data, one way not to make the same mistakes even with other walls that we are trying to break in the context of open data, is to think about partnerships of all the different consumers so that you celebrate the data that you're giving from a point of—there's somebody else who knows how to use it, to follow through and make an impact. Those are the connections that we need to make. In whichever way, at the end we strengthen how the world appreciates, supports, and uses open data and sources. (P18, interview)

6.3.5. Subsection summary

In this subsection we have seen that respondents criticised interpretations of OS which too narrowly focus on issues of accessibility and transparency of research. Rather, they believe that science should embrace principles of RRI to deepen its mission-driven normative dimensions. In this regard, especially the facilitation of what we have termed upstream engagement and resonant research will ensure research responds to local needs and is of most immediate benefit to those communities involved.

6.4. Barriers to change

Through the contributions so far, we have seen that although participants were generally in favour of OS, they thought that in a narrow definition of expanding access and transparency it only had limited potential to impact policy-making. Rather, participants largely endorsed an expanded definition of OS which enacts the mission-driven normativity and sensitivity to radical stakeholder participation of RRI via mechanisms like upstream engagement and designing for resonance. In this final section, we will note some overarching framework constraints which participants also raised, several of which presented challenges for uptake of these practices amongst researchers and intermediaries, and which should be seen as urgent challenges in shaping a science ecosystem which allows understanding and participation at the science-policy interface to flourish.

6.4.1. Competition over collaboration

Firstly, two participants specifically linked OS and RRI to make the point that the current system is too skewed towards competition over collaboration. P13 saw OS and RRI as a potential corrective in this regard:

In my point of view, there is this huge value of Open Science and RRI, of this whole transparency of process and things like that which, I personally am very much in favour of that as I think that how our research system is working right now is much too competitive and not that productive anymore, because lots of the energy just goes into competition instead of being productive and collaborate. (P13, agriculture workshop)

Similarly, P8 sees OS as a fundamental shift in collaborative working, but frames this as a potential barrier to uptake of OS since the rewards system is currently designed for a different paradigm. They advocate incentivising practices instead of outputs:

This transition means not rewarding particular outputs of science publications but rewarding how researchers behave. So, this is a big step because inherently to Open Science isn't old type of research behaviour and that means also that the appreciation of researchers in their work has to become different at universities and research organisations. This is actually very difficult because the universities globally, one, is very attached to the idea of scientific excellence. Nobody knows what it means. It's only scientists who decide what it is. So, it's a mechanism to keep society out. But the consequence is that research and innovation does not produce what we want to get out of science. Actually, the state of affairs is rather disappointing. (P8, interview)

Interestingly, both participants link this privileging of competition over collaboration to deficiencies in the current system. Yet while for P8 it is inefficiencies and lack of inclusion in scientific processes that are at issue, for P13, it is the ways in which the rhetoric of excellence fosters cumulative advantage in terms of resources:

I think that how our research system is working right now is much too competitive and not that productive anymore, because lots of the energy just goes into competition instead of being productive and collaborate. That's one of the core issues which I'm really concerned about. So, there are those imbalances in terms of capacities between, within not only the society in general but also within the research and innovation landscape. I'm a bit concerned about that if research policy would not have a clear commitment to support, balancing of those hierarchies within the research funding programs, we would end up with those who have high capacities could take high advantage out of all this Open Access thing. (P13, agriculture workshop)

6.4.2. Recognition and rewards

The clear requirement for reward and recognition schemes to be adapted came through from other respondents, especially in the frame of how policy work is rewarded within an OS context.

The pressure to publish in peer-reviewed journals was clearly felt from those within the traditional bounds of academia:

In terms of research evaluation, you also have a clear hierarchy and the clear incentives where to engage. Then the question is, what are the assessment systems that value what you do? But in terms of being effective in working at the interface of science and policy, it's probably not the high impact publication that helps ... When we talk about publications, in a way then it's also the question of how is research funding and research funding organised? (P2, climate workshop)

P2 continued on this point, seeing the need for impact beyond publications and demonstrations of “expected societal benefit” to be a necessary “part of the funding game that when you submit a proposal” with a need to be creative, especially in contexts of fundamental research (P2, climate workshop). The way in which narrow research assessment schemes inhibit OS uptake was also mentioned by P8:

[Y]ou have to start rewarding Open Science practices. What does it mean? That means that we should not reward the number of publications or the number of citations or something like that. What we should reward is how researchers behave. Do they work together? Do they collaborate or are they open to collaboration? Are they sharing knowledge in data? Do they use open infrastructures? This is research behaviour. (P8, interview)

6.4.3. Funding and project logics

In addition, the logic of project funding was also seen as an issue, especially by P11 who made the point at length throughout their interview and workshop contributions:

I cannot say that we are completely free because these EU projects put on the researchers some constraints. So, this is not free money. There is a work plan which you have to execute but we try to be as flexible as possible within the workplace. Time to time, of course, we experience problems with these project constraints. So, this project-based life of researchers, I think is already constraining Open Science to a great extent. If the EU or anyone would ... finance research in a more trustful way, not setting so much this bureaucratic burden on research, then I think researchers will be freer and will be more beneficial socially. But that's my opinion. (P11, interview)

There was also recognition that OS and RRI were general trends which could be harnessed to achieve funding. P11, noting that their broader work within the participatory action research tradition fit naturally within the RRI paradigm noted the need to rebrand to fit the current policy fad:

To tell the truth, in a sense there is a big chunk of opportunism to use RRI because this was financed. A lot of things that financed through RRI. We researchers are moving towards concepts which EU likes and then finances, that's true. But don't... I think in one sense this is pragmatic, but of course it can create problems. (P11, interview)

The issue with such rebranding is that if not done with true intent, it just becomes empty lip-service:

There are so many terms, but the bottom line for me is whether we as science, as a structure, are we democratic trying to address and go against dominations, different dominations or we are just trying to use these as buzzwords and don't change our practices too much. (P11, agriculture workshop)

6.4.4. Subsection summary

Respondents identified key challenges for uptake of OS and RRI in relation to influencing policy-making which relate directly to the framework conditions of academia. Firstly, they identified a culture which too strongly favours *competition over collaboration*. Secondly, they highlighted a system of *rewards and recognition* which focus too heavily on quantity of publications over the quality of research per se, especially the timely and transparent communication of research via OS methods and the engagement of societal actors through methods of RRI. Finally, participants raised concerns regarding *research agendas and funding* which foster short-termism and lead researchers to take up the language but not necessarily the spirit of OS and RRI.

6.5. Discussion: Towards Responsible Open Science

In this chapter we have examined our participants' views on the extent to which OS and RRI might reshape the science-policy interface. Our results show that participants were sceptical of OS's potential to achieve

much in this regard, especially where an instrumental interpretation of OS is used. Although OS may have some impact in enabling access to policy-makers, and opening data could help transparency and trust in research, our participants highlighted issues with exclusion from OA publishing caused by the APC-model of OA (especially for those outside universities) and in translating this information into forms cognitively-accessible to stakeholders. The dimensions of participation enabled by CS were seen as most potentially useful, but here a sometimes narrowly instrumental view of what participation means in this context could also prove problematic.

Through our presentation of participants' views on RRI, especially as they related to OS, we saw a very strong belief amongst many that science should embrace principles of RRI to deepen its mission-driven normative dimensions. In this regard, especially the facilitation of what we have termed upstream engagement and resonant research were seen to potentially ensure that research responds to local needs and is of most immediate benefit to those communities involved.

Finally, we reported the ways in which prevailing values, as institutionalised through research policies and cultures, potentially hinder uptake. Heavy competition for resources, reward schemes which undervalue OS and RRI, and funding schemes which foster a "Realpolitik" approach to adoption of the language, but not necessarily the sentiment, of these agendas are all potential barriers in this regard.

What are the implications of this, especially for OS and RRI policy? Firstly, a perceived key distinction between OS and RRI revealed here is that in contrast to RRI, OS's ambitions seem more pragmatically focussed, especially in terms of engagement with the public. In an excellent analysis, Shelley-Egan et al. (2020) expand at length on this issue. They state that "RRI's approach to opening up extends to an invitation to publics to co-define the aims and means of technical processes in order to increase their alignment with public values," "Open Science restricts ambitions for opening up to adjustments and improvements to processes based on quality criteria ultimately rooted in the existing research system." OS is thus seen as insufficiently critical of the value and direction of science. It is also seen as failing to fully appreciate "societal voices and citizens as legitimate conversation partners and beneficiaries of technology and knowledge," engaging publics on asymmetrical terms that seek mere dialogue between "technical experts and societal voices." Hence, "RRI focuses more on producing (ethically and socially) "good" outcomes than on resulting in the (epistemically and functionally) "best" outcomes, while OS for its part remains agnostic about the former and concerns itself almost entirely with the latter, and more often concerns itself with issues of efficiency, optimization, integration and potential." The authors suggest that this "pragmatism and instrumentality" of OS leaves it in line with prevailing political and institutional (i.e., neoliberal) aims.

Such a purely technocratic definition is no doubt at odds with the view of OS held by many advocates. Yet the equivocal nature of "Open Science" means that such readings are at least plausible, and hence should be taken as a call for the OS community to more fundamentally appraise the way its priorities are presented, and the deeper ways in which societal voices can be engaged as equals in setting research agendas. It further illuminates the ways in which the radicality of OS can be questioned, and the extent to which OS merely enables the further neoliberalisation and commodification of research knowledge. We have seen that indeed, for many of our participants, such critique of OS indeed seemed relevant. Through their criticisms of the asymmetrical relationship between OS and industry and of limited conceptions of access, representation and participation, our participants hence largely prescribed a version of what we may term *Responsible Open Science* that enacts the ethical directionality of RRI for stronger normative and mission-based framings of knowledge creation, especially through enabling upstream engagement for full involvement of stakeholders

from agenda-setting onwards, and ensuring knowledge creation is resonant, bringing immediate benefits, to stakeholders.

In addition, our findings seem to highlight a need for OS to better account for the ways in which resources and network-positionality influence outcomes. The resource-intensive and networked nature of OS means it is also vulnerable to these logics. Explicitly linking authorship channels to possession of resources potentially stratifies OA publishing. The expensive infrastructures and training necessary to participate in engaging with open data and methods means those privileged in these regards are primed to benefit most, at least initially. The importance of such underlying competences means that ensuring access is not enough to ensure equity of opportunity in an OS world, absent broader measures to overcome the digital divide.

These findings all highlight ways in which the optimistic rhetoric of OS is not represented by the reality of practices at present. Inequalities and dynamics of cumulative advantage pervade modern scholarship, and our results show that despite its potential to improve equity in many areas, OS is not exempt. Merton advises that cumulative advantage directs our attention to “the ways in which initial comparative advantages of trained capacity, structural location, and available resources make for successive increments of advantage such that the gaps between the haves and the have-nots in science (as in other domains of social life) widen until dampened by countervailing processes” (Merton, 1988). Given its commonly-held aim of increasing equity, any potential for OS to actually drive inequalities must be taken seriously by the scientific community in order to realise the aim of making science truly open, collaborative and meritocratic. Key measures which could act as “countervailing processes” in this regard are an expanded conception of Responsible Open Science which acknowledges the importance of research that is mission-driven, fosters upstream engagement and produces outcomes that are resonant within research contexts.

7. Discussion

ON-MERRIT aims to critically interrogate whether OS lives up to the positive claims of its proponents in a multitude of ways and whether the Matthew effect in academia, or other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage, may be present within or even exacerbated by OS and RRI practices. Of particular interest to ON-MERRIT Task 5.3, on which this deliverable reports, is whether OS does in fact support scientific uptake by policy-makers, and, to the second point, whether the Matthew effect or other forms of cumulative advantage or disadvantage may be at play and impacting participation in policy-making. These concerns are reflected in the primary research questions for this task: **1. What factors influence scientific uptake by policy-makers? 2. Which societal actors, both within and outside of academia, participate in RRI research and policy-making?** Secondly, we ask: **Who influences public participation in policy-making? Which societal actors are excluded, and why?** To answer these questions, we undertook qualitative research consisting of in-depth interviews and three thematic workshops with RRI researchers and those with RRI-resonant practices (18 participants total). The research findings presented in Chapters 3–6 allow us to answer these questions. Here, we first offer a summary of key findings, followed by a discussion organized around our research questions, before discussing the implications of our results and the limitations of our research.

7.1. Summary of key findings

As presented in **Chapter 3**, policy-making is a complex and multifaceted social activity. The approaches taken in practice vary considerably. Three different policy models have been identified by the empirical analysis presented with this report: a) representative democracy, b) deliberative democracy, and c) participatory democracy. One of our most salient findings concerns the changing role and function of knowledge across these three types of policy-making: representative democracy is associated with the provision of policy processes with scientific knowledge; deliberative democracy is associated with knowledge integration over the course of public debates; participatory democracy is associated with co-creation of effective, transdisciplinary knowledge to tackle societal challenges. The three types are not mutually exclusive. Although they emerged consecutively, today, they exist side-by-side. Our participants showed considerable awareness of these different spheres of policy advice and shared that they often adjusted their strategies for interacting with policy-makers, depending on the sphere, and seeking to produce uptake accordingly. We found that approaches that seek to inform individuals and institutions of representative democracy favour communication (translation, policy briefs, direct communication, trust relationships, etc.). Deliberative democracy-oriented approaches invite citizens to attend public deliberation processes to achieve a broadly shared consensus. Participatory approaches seek to produce effective knowledge needed to act upon societal challenges and to bring about change; this is best achieved when a broad set of civil society actors and policy-makers are jointly engaged both in the creation and implementation of the relevant knowledge. Looking specifically at factors that influence uptake, we found that congruence with policy goals is a key factor for successful knowledge integration within the representative democracy model and that international organisations such as UN, WHO, EU and OECD play a decisive role in defining the normative foundation of these policy goals; political culture largely determines whether policy-makers are receptive to deliberative forms of policy-making; and that, by deploying upstream engagement and linking communities to policy-makers, participatory approaches promise higher degrees of effective knowledge integration as required to tackle societal challenges and advance societal benefits.

Chapter 4 builds on these findings by shining a light on the social relationships between researchers and policy-makers, which are the foundation upon which much of the work described in Chapter 3 takes place.

In doing so, we found that our participants rate relationships with policy-makers as highly important in influencing scientific uptake in the policy realm. Relationships are important because, as the literature shows (see Chapters 1 and 4), this is how policy-makers prefer to receive expert information. Our findings show that policy-active researchers understand that the relationships they cultivate with policy-makers provide the basis for educating policy-makers and for learning from them—both of which are critical for uptake. Importantly, our findings also show that these relationships only work when they are based on the perceived credibility and legitimacy of the researchers. These are often achieved with academic credentials and affiliation, however, because the processes of constructing both are social in nature, we found that access to these resources are inequitably distributed across society-wide axes of power and inequality—namely, race, gender and geography. Being granted access to relationships with policy-makers working in elite spheres, for example, typically requires a certain configuration of privilege. In our sample, white men of European descent (and some white women) and non-white men within non-white contexts, have been able to attain this type of access. While some participants who can be described as marginalized within the scientific community are also (sometimes) able to develop this type of access, what we heard more often from them is that they must rely on other strategies to engage with policy-makers, like practicing emotional labor, partnering with more prominent and/or Western scientists, using the media, and using participatory research methods to develop relationships with policy-makers outside of their elite spaces and/or to implement practical change in communities outside of the sphere of representative democracy. In all cases, relationships can be neither cultivated nor maintained without some degree of congruence between the goals of both researchers and policy-makers. Finally, we found that some of our participants use the values and practices of RRI to reconfigure the normative terms of science in ways that are meant to produce uptake and support societal benefits.

Turning specifically to the question of access and representation, in **Chapter 5** we documented that policy-active researchers take three different approaches to research that can be seen to align with the three policy models described in Chapter 1 and elaborated in Chapter 3. These three approaches—traditional academic, multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory—directly influence both the degree of access and representation that are present within the research process and the science-policy interface, as well as the types of access and representation that are present. Our findings show that the traditional academic approach offers the least amount of access and representation, since the actors involved tend to be only researchers and policy-makers. The multi-stakeholder approach offers greater access and representation, though indirect representation of impacted communities and marginalized groups is often used (via NGOs and CSOs) rather than direct access and representation. The strongly participatory approach offers the greatest degree of equality of access and representation by bringing marginalized groups directly into the research process, the science-policy interface, and policy-making. Focusing specifically on how our participants work to foster equality of access and representation, we found that they strategically deploy creative and participatory research designs and methods to include a diverse array of marginalized groups, across cultural and geographic contexts, into their research process. They also take care to meet the material needs required for participation and look for ways to provide other benefits to participants, beyond knowledge acquisition. One important benefit is the relationships that are forged between their own research participants and policy-makers, when both groups are present in the research setting (and when the science-policy interface coincides with the research setting). In cases where this happens, participants, often from marginalized groups, leave the research project with an expanded social network and set of social skills that allow them to follow-up with policy-makers to address problems in their communities. Cumulatively, the work of those who deploy multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory research approaches democratizes knowledge production, knowledge acquisition, and policy-making. We also found,

however, that those doing this work face challenges and barriers that range from academic and scientific norms and standards, structural economic conditions and funding mechanisms, as well as social and cultural challenges and barriers within the research setting.

Finally, in **Chapter 6**, we turned our attention to the question of whether OS influences uptake of scientific advice, its relationship to the Matthew effect and other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage, and the degree to which our participants align their values and practices to OS and RRI. We found that policy-active researchers do not believe that OS has a significant bearing on uptake, excepting a few anecdotal accounts to the contrary. They agree that access to scientific literature and data is not an issue for policy-makers; rather, filtering and translation are. This resonates with both the existing literature and our own findings, which establish that policy-makers prefer to receive information through relationships, rather than printed sources. Beyond that, our findings demonstrate a critical view of OS among policy-active researchers, especially those who engage in multi-stakeholder and strongly participatory methods, who criticize OA for failing to ensure cognitive access in addition to physical access, and for squeezing out under-resourced researchers and non-traditional research teams with high APCs. We found greater support for Open/FAIR data, in particular, as a way to repair the damage done by ‘data siphoning’ in the global south, coupled with the assertion that data too must be cognitively accessible. We found general support for CS, especially from our participants who actively practice it, yet also concerns about it being used in tokenized ways or as illegitimate from the policy-maker standpoint. We found general support for RRI, even though our participants who come from outside the EU were unaware of this model. Regardless of awareness, we found that they approach and conduct research and the science-policy interface in ways that resonate with its values, practices and concerns. They believe that it is an effective way of including a diversity of societal actors in policy-making through upstream engagement and that it can effectively respond to local needs. Here too, we found that our participants encounter challenges and barriers to engaging in RRI-resonant research and policy-making. They name competition within academia and scientific communities, existing rewards schemes within both, and the logics of funding and projects as key barriers to the diffusion of RRI practices.

7.2. Answering our research questions

7.2.1. What factors influence scientific uptake by policy-makers?

Collectively, our findings show that awareness and understanding of the policy model in which one wishes to exert influence are critical because these then determine the set of strategies that one should use in order to achieve uptake. Related to this, congruence between research aims and policy goals is also key. Other factors include the policy positions taken at certain international organizations (e.g., UN, WHO, OECD, EU, etc.) which serve to define the normative foundation for policy-making. Therefore, aligning with goals articulated by these organizations is an effective way to achieve uptake at other scales of policy-making. Our findings also show that political culture, or receptivity to input, influences uptake, as does the practice of upstream engagement and the fostering of relationships between communities and their policy-makers. Simultaneously, and related to many of these factors, the strategic development and maintenance of relationships, on the part of researchers with policy-makers, is also a key factor. These facilitate the two-way transfer of information and knowledge, which helps to foster alignment. Establishing trust and credibility throughout the process of relationship building, therefore, is also of critical importance. Without either, positive working relationships will not exist, nor will uptake. Notably, we found that while there was some limited evidence for the impact that access and transparency can have on uptake, our findings do not support that OS practices are consistently fostering scientific uptake by policy-makers. However, we did find that the

use of RRI-resonant values and practices, particularly upstream engagement and participatory methods that put policy-makers into contact with marginalised and impacted communities, often lead to uptake.

7.2.2. Which societal actors, both within and outside of academia, participate in RRI research and policy-making?

Our findings show that the policy model at play, and the approach to research and the science-policy interface taken by policy-active researchers, determine who participants in RRI-resonant research and policy-making. Our findings show that the policy model, be it 1) representative democracy, 2) deliberative democracy or 3) participatory democracy, dictates through existing norms who participates. Largely overlapping with these three models, the three different approaches to research evidenced in our data—1) traditional academic, 2) multi-stakeholder and 3) strongly participatory, do the same. With the first, it is primarily researchers and policy-makers who participate. With the second, the range of actors is opened to include various stakeholders selected for the relevance to the problem at hand. These typically include researchers, other experts, representatives from the business world, policy-makers and other civil servants, representatives of CSOs and NGOs, and sometimes, representatives of local communities (though not always; CSOs/NGOs often serve this role in this approach). With the third, the range of actors is further broadened to include people who have been historically marginalized from processes of both scientific knowledge production and policy-making. Our findings demonstrate that these people/communities range from average citizens to the world's most poor and vulnerable. While their life circumstances may differ, what they share is that they have historically not participated in scientific research as anything other than objects of study, nor in policy-making as anything other than voters (in the best cases). In the strongly participatory approach to research, they participate as co-creators of knowledge and policy recommendations, and sometimes they participate at the science-policy interface (when this is the research setting), and sometimes they have direct interaction with policy-makers (when this has been facilitated by the research process).

As a subquestion to this one, we also asked, **which societal actors are excluded and why?** The answer, again, to this question depends entirely on the policy model at play and the approach to research taken. Considering the answer to the previous question, it is clear that the first is the most exclusive and the third the most inclusive. However, to be more precise, we observed in our findings that societal-wide dynamics of power and inequality are at play in both realms, determining who is excluded from both. Our findings show that the social construction of credibility and legitimacy, which are necessary for developing relationships with policy-makers, are intersected with historical hierarchies premised on race, gender, geography (in the geopolitical sense), as well as institutional affiliation—something that is largely dependent on the three factors previously listed. Additionally, our findings indicate that researchers without adequate funding or institutional support for policy-oriented work are also left out. On the societal side, our findings show that the world's most poor and vulnerable remain largely left out. Difficult to reach due to the digital divide, language marginalization, and limited resources for this type of work, they are left out, despite the best efforts of our participants.

7.2.3. Who influences public participation in policy-making?

Our findings show that several actors influence public participation in policy-making. These include researchers, policy-makers, funders, and academic and scientific institutions. It's not possible to say based on our findings which is most influential, so we emphasize that we do not discuss them here in order of importance. Our findings show that researchers influence this by their choice of approach to research. Policy-makers influence it based on their willingness to engage with the various approaches to research that the siting of the science-policy interface implies. Funders influence it by offering only limited support for RRI-

resonant research that engages diverse members of the public in policy-oriented research processes, and academic and scientific institutions (individually and collectively), influence it by maintaining norms and values that run counter to this aim and discouraging and disincentivizing researchers from facilitating it.

7.3. Interpretations and implications

The research presented in this report has illuminated much of the ‘black box’ of the science-policy interface and of policy-making. We learned that working at the science-policy interface is a contextual and complex experience that requires deep knowledge and insight to be effectively navigated. Given that academic/scientific researchers are, for the most part, not formally trained to do this type of work, these findings suggest that only a small proportion of researchers around the world are positioned to do this effectively. Therefore, the proportion of broader publics, and in particular marginalized people around the world, who are given access to or represented within the science-policy interface is also quite small. Within this limited pool of policy-active researchers, our findings have demonstrated that dynamics of power and inequality are present within the science-policy interface and operate in ways that further advantage historically privileged actors while disadvantaging historically marginalized ones. To us, these facts signal that, despite the good work being done by RRI-resonant researchers and those practicing RRI and OS in ways that aim to truly democratize knowledge production, access and engagement, there is much work to be done in terms of fostering greater equality of access and representation within both research and policy-making. The systems of inequality that plague our societies—racism, sexism, ageism, classism, heteronormativity, and the legacy of colonialism, to name a few—are present within both realms, and therefore solutions require equity work far beyond the scope of this research.

Yet, there are clear and actionable steps that can be taken by those in positions of power to keep moving scientific research and RRI-resonant policy work in a more equitable direction. Our participants called for more funding support and more *flexible* funding support for equity-oriented, co-creative, participatory research. Funders do in fact hold a lot of power here. If this work is not funded, then it simply cannot be done. Our participants observe that both funding calls and stipulations need to be reoriented to support this kind of work, which often cannot be clearly defined in a funding proposal due to the co-creative nature of it. Further, doing this kind of work requires funding support for the participants of this research, not only for the researchers. Currently, funding schemes offer little flexibility in this regard, which undermines the ability of RRI-resonant researchers to bring marginalized, especially impoverished, people into research and policy-making. Additionally, it is clear that academic and scientific institutional norms, values and practices do not adequately support this kind of work. On the contrary, they undermine and discourage it. A reorientation of values would be necessary within both academic science and funding bodies to make changes here.

Our findings also signal a need for OS leaders and policy-makers to engage in some critical self-reflection about the values and practices of the paradigm. Our findings indicate that policy-oriented researchers do not, for the most part, find it, in its existing form, inspiring or helpful to their work. They call for a scientific paradigm that values collaboration over cooperation, diversity and inclusion over homogeneity and exclusion, solutions-oriented research over purely academic research (or commercially-oriented research), and upstream engagement with policy-makers, other stakeholders and impacted communities in order to ensure that the views and knowledge of those most relevant to the problem at hand are part of framing it and the solutions proposed to address it. Further, they call for a science that provides immediate and lasting benefits to the communities and populations that are focused under its lens, which includes providing cognitive access to all scientific outputs. Such an expanded conception of what we call *Responsible Open*

Science would have particular resonance for mission-driven research that seeks to support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Another issue highlighted by our findings is the persistence of the digital divide and how it manifests in research and policy-making. Given the salience of relationships between researchers and policy-makers, we heard from some of our participants that the COVID-19 global pandemic has made their work more challenging, because in-person meetings all but vanished for more than a year, as did the interpersonal interactions that happen around them. On the one hand, having to interact online rather than in person may level the playing field for policy-active researchers, taking away some of the advantage that certain actors have. On the other hand, it may prevent some from effectively entering the science-policy interface at all, if they are not able to meet policy-makers in person to develop the trust and credibility that must be present for these relationships to be productive. There are also negative implications in terms of including broader publics and marginalized communities. We heard from our participants that the pandemic made co-creative, participatory work rather challenging, for the same reasons, and, that online meetings pose a barrier to the participation of marginalized groups who may not have access to the technology necessary to participate, and if they do, may not be accustomed to interacting in such a way. Where a digital divide may not be present, an imbalance in cultural capital may act as a barrier. The ongoing nature of this global pandemic (it continues as we conclude this work in September 2021) and the likelihood of disruptions to social life caused by future global pandemics⁸ implies that these conditions and their impacts on equitable scientific knowledge production and engagement at the science-policy interface must be taken seriously and mitigated, as much as possible.

7.4. Limitations of this study

While we observed and reported on clear trends in the data that we gathered for this research, we recognize that we worked with a small sample size that was not randomly constructed, and therefore understand that research conducted on a larger scale with a randomized sample could produce different results. One trend of note here is that we observed some apparent overlap between participant positionality, approach to research, and how they interact at the science-policy interface. Our data suggest that power and privilege, organized around the intersections of race, gender, age and geographic positioning, may serve to direct researchers toward research approaches with greater or lesser degrees of equity, in terms of access and representation, embedded within them. Yet, again, we recognize that we cannot draw conclusions about this from our small, non-randomized sample. Again, a larger study with a randomized sample could be used to study this and draw conclusive results.

Additionally, our findings are limited, to a certain extent, to applicability in the European context. While our sample does include participants from Asia, Africa and North America, their numbers are not great enough to indicate any trends within these regions. Finally, due to the time constraints of project logics, we were unable to compare domains within our data (climate, agriculture, health) to identify any domain-specific trends or similarities or differences across domains. However, our data allow for this and present the possibility for this type of analysis at a later date, during the synthesis phase of the ON-MERRIT project.

⁸ <https://www.cgdev.org/event/whats-next-predicting-frequency-and-scale-future-pandemics>

8. Conclusion

With this study we sought to critically interrogate a claim made by proponents of OS, that OS fosters uptake of science by policy-makers, and to critically interrogate the degree to which RRI practices foster equality of access and representation within processes of knowledge production and policy-making. Based on the qualitative research undertaken in ON-MERRIT Task 5.3, we found that while there are several key factors that influence scientific uptake by policy-makers, OS is not chief among them. Rather, awareness on the part of policy-active researchers of the policy model in which they operate (representative democracy, deliverable democracy, or participatory democracy), knowledge of how to do so successfully, and the ability to forge relationships with policy-makers necessary to do so are the key factors that influence uptake. Looking at who participates in RRI-resonant research and policy-making, and who is left out, we found that using multi-stakeholder and participatory approaches, and deploying upstream engagement in both, opens access and representation to a broad range of societal actors, including historically marginalized groups. Yet, we also found that there are significant barriers to this work posed by academic and scientific institutions, funders, and policy-makers themselves. And, despite the best efforts of our participants, the world's most poor and vulnerable remain, for the most part, left out.

The qualitative methods we deployed in this study generated ample usable data and effectively answered our research questions. Yet, regarding the question of who influences public participation in policy-making, our findings left us with the impression that a large-scale quantitative survey of who—in terms of race, gender, age, geographic position—is doing RRI and RRI-resonant research would yield a clearer and stronger answer to this question.

In the broader context of the ON-MERRIT project, the results of this study contribute to a new understanding of the role of OS outputs in policy-making (they are quite limited) and illuminate the ways in which the Matthew effect manifests in RRI research and policy-making. Our findings demonstrate that systems of inequality, including racism, sexism, ageism, classism and lingering colonialism manifest in academic/scientific and policy-making contexts in ways that advantage already privileged actors while further disadvantaging those already operating at a disadvantage (sometimes even shutting them out entirely). Specific to the cross-cutting issue of gender, our findings indicate that women researchers in particular, in the RRI context, are practitioners of multi-stakeholder and participatory research, and engaging in the science-policy interface in ways that reflect these approaches. We are not able to conclusively speak to why this is the case, but our findings suggest that women may be 'pushed' in this direction by dynamics of inequality that drive them out of traditional academic approaches and elite policy-making spaces. It may also be the case that experiencing systemic inequality orients a researcher toward equitable research practices, however, again, we cannot conclude this based on our findings. Further research into the effect of gender on approach to research and policy-making would need to be conducted to do so. Finally, regarding the ON-MERRIT project's interest in the issue of sustainable development and the societal challenges that are implicated in the UN SDGs, our findings offer insight into how research can be designed to effectively respond to pressing on-the-ground realities and how researchers (and societal actors) can interact with policy-makers to work collaboratively toward both immediate and longer-term solutions.

8.1. Recommendations

Building on the discussion presented in Chapter 7, we offer the following set of preliminary recommendations to RRI policy-makers (funders and governments), academic and scientific institutional leaders, and researchers. (These recommendations will be refined during the synthesis phase of ON-MERRIT, which will include co-creation processes with the three target groups listed above.)

If increased uptake of scientific evidence/advice by policy-makers in pursuit of socially beneficial outcomes (e.g. the SDGs) is the goal, then:

RRI policy-makers (funders and governments) should:

1. Fund activities that support training for interacting at the science-policy interface
2. Fund research that uses multi-stakeholder and participatory design and methods (especially creative methods) because these are best poised to produce uptake and on-the-ground change
3. Fund research activities that specifically take place at the science-policy interface, wherever that may be, given the policy model at play
4. Foster internal change to ensure policy-makers themselves are more open to upstream engagement, co-creation of policy goals and collaboration in multi-stakeholder and participatory research

Institutional leaders should:

1. Support and provide training for interacting at the science-policy interface
2. Further support or create where needed dedicated departments/roles for supporting researchers to work at the science-policy interface and/or do this on their behalf
3. Support and reward research that involves upstream engagement and participatory methods to foster uptake by policy-makers and practical implementation on the ground
4. Support and reward research that uses multi-stakeholder and participatory design and methods (especially creative methods) because these often produce uptake and implementation

Researchers should:

1. Understand which policy model they are operating in and what set of strategies are best suited to producing uptake within it
2. Practice upstream engagement
3. Practice multi-stakeholder and participatory methods
4. Develop relationships with policy-makers and organizational administrators
5. Seek to develop congruence with policy goals through deliberative and participatory processes
6. Look to policy-leading international organizations to support normative claims and goals
7. Support the development of relevant knowledge and skills among junior colleagues and diverse research teams
8. Foster the development of relationships between impacted communities and policy-makers
9. Engage in training on tailoring presentation of research results for target audiences

If making scientific knowledge production, the science-policy interface, and participation in policy-making more equitable (particularly as regards the inclusion of historically marginalized actors) is the goal, then:

RRI policy-makers (funders and governments) should:

1. Fund research that takes a multi-stakeholder and/or participatory approach rather than the traditional academic approach, because these foster inclusion while the latter is exclusive in nature
2. Fund activities that support the development of self-reflexive research practices and critical awareness of how power dynamics and positionality are at play in processes of both knowledge production and policy-making
3. Specifically fund researchers who are marginalized within academic and scientific contexts: women, people of colour in majority/dominant white cultures, and people from the global south/other peripheral places
4. Support and fund research practices that take an open and accessible approach to dissemination and data sharing
5. Support and fund research that seeks to include the poorest/most vulnerable/most marginalized members of global society
6. Add flexibility to both funding calls and stipulations of use to allow for the unknowns that are part of participatory processes and for the allocation of funds necessary to support the participation of marginalized people
7. Fund collaborative research proposed by diverse research teams, especially those teams that include non-scientific actors

Institutional leaders should:

1. Support and reward research that takes a multi-stakeholder and/or participatory approach rather than the traditional academic approach, because these foster inclusion while the latter is exclusive in nature
2. Support and provide training in the development of self-reflexive research practices and critical awareness of how power dynamics and positionality are at play in processes of both knowledge production and policy-making
3. Support and provide training in multi-stakeholder and participatory research design and methods
4. Seek to balance inequalities within academic and scientific institutions by hiring and supporting the career development of researchers who are marginalized within these contexts: women, people of colour in dominant white cultures, and people from the global south/other peripheral places
5. Support and reward research practices that take an open and accessible approach to dissemination and data sharing
6. Support and reward research that seeks to include the poorest/most vulnerable/most marginalized members of global society
7. Give researchers working with stakeholders and marginalized groups access to portions of research budgets to use in flexible ways to support inclusion of marginalized groups in participatory processes
8. Support and reward collaborative research conducted by diverse research teams
9. Support and provide training on how to conduct equitable, participatory research in online settings during times of social isolation

Researchers should:

1. Take a multi-stakeholder and/or participatory approach to research rather than the traditional academic approach, because these foster inclusion while the latter is exclusive in nature
2. Develop for yourself, and support development among others, self-reflexive research practices and critical awareness of how power dynamics and positionality are at play in processes of both knowledge production and policy-making
3. Actively and intentionally cultivate diverse research teams and networks (in terms of race, gender, academic age, geographic location, stakeholder role, organizational/professional background, type of knowledge brought to the table)
4. Foster relationships between diverse stakeholders, particularly marginalized groups, and their relevant policy-makers
5. Practice open and accessible dissemination and data sharing practices
6. Conduct research that seeks to include the poorest/most vulnerable/most marginalized members of global society
7. Share skills and knowledge with colleagues and within broader research networks of how to conduct equitable, participatory research in online settings during times of social isolation

9. References

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Annex 1 Policy Brief: Integrating policy relevant research to counter societal challenges

Key Messages

- Climate change, sustainable agriculture and public health present urgent societal challenges that require decisive policy action.
- A sound knowledge basis is needed to counter these societal challenges with effective measures.
- Knowledge most effectively facilitates socially inclusive change if collaboratively produced through the participation of a broad set of stakeholders and societal actors comprising scientific, local and practical expertise.
- Funding policies need to prioritise research design that secures effective uptake and implementation of collaboratively produced and socially sound knowledge in the policy domain.
- Responsiveness on the part of policy makers is equally required for successful knowledge integration

The ON-MERRIT project - Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research & Innovation Transition

The [ON-MERRIT project](#), funded by the European Commission under the “Science with and for Society” funding programme, is a 30-month effort to study potential effects of cumulative advantage (otherwise known as the Matthew effect) in the Open Science transition in academia, industry, and policy making based on three case studies (agriculture, climate, health) all related to the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals. The research applied a multi-disciplinary approach combining qualitative analyses of promotion policies, surveys of academics, industry professionals, and policymakers with workshops featuring policy-active researchers. The recommendations presented in this policy brief stem from research into access and representation of various groups in policy-making processes with the aim of engaging researchers who take part in participatory evidence-gathering for projects aligned with RRI via a series of three expert workshops, each themed for one case study domain. Experts invited to these workshops were initially asked to share experiences of participatory processes and to reflect on possible barriers to participation. In a second step, they were asked to reflect on their own experiences with facilitating policy-making through their research, and to question how the voices of various stakeholders and civil society actors (including their own) were or were not heard, for which reasons. Additionally, we invited them to reflect specifically on the role of OS and RRI in fostering equitable participation in and access to research and policy-making. Bringing together individual assessment and group discussions, the experiences and reflections of the workshop participants inform knowledge about the Matthew effect and other forms of cumulative advantage and disadvantage in the participation of public actors in evidence-gathering activities and the uptake of research by policy-makers.

Introduction

This policy brief identifies key societal actors working at the science-policy interface who influence public participation in policy-making and address key factors enhancing uptake of research outputs by policy-makers. It is however especially important to overcome forms of social exclusion in the integration of policy relevant research.

The research conducted by the ON-MERRIT project suggests that the traditional (democratic) political system is inaccessible to most citizens but especially so for peripheral and marginalised groups. Policy makers are often perceived as an elite group who predominantly take advice from prestigious institutions and renowned individuals. Although well established and effective to some degree, critics claim that this predominant system is not well positioned to address pressing societal challenges and even less capable to develop and implement effective measures to tackle these challenges. The identified criticism has two main dimensions: a) the dominant system excludes large parts of society from participation and is thus undemocratic, and b) the dominant system does not deliver effective solutions to pressing social problems. This policy brief proposes steps to overcome these two major shortcomings.

Identifying dominant societal actors

Three groups of societal actors are decisive for integrating the outputs of policy relevant research. Their central position presents a considerable cumulative advantage which is often perceived as inaccessibility and low responsiveness.

- 1) **The role of institutionalized policy advice is decisive.** Policy-relevant knowledge has its institutional anchorage in ministries, public administration and governmental agencies. In addition, advisory boards, ethics committees, parliamentary Technology Assessment agencies and competent authorities are decisive locations of institutionalized policy advice. These institutions play a crucial role in implementing policy relevant research in concrete policy actions.
- 2) **Renowned universities and other research institutions are in the center of policy relevant research.** To secure the uptake of research results, personal interaction between policy makers and researchers is decisive. Above all, this requires researchers to develop the communicative skills necessary to bring the world of policy making and the world of science closer together.
- 3) **International Organisations exercise strong influence on national and local policy processes.** This is especially true for the OECD (economic policies), the United Nations (sustainable development), and the WHO (public health). Other supranational organizations such as the World Bank are likewise important. For European national policy makers, the European Union is a formative policy actor. Expertise that enters the policy domain via these decisive international organizations exercises great leverage over national and local policy practices.
- 4) **Institutional and personal reputation** and academic merits impact heavily on the recognition and uptake of scientific knowledge by central policy actors. However, uptake also depends on the willingness of those who are expected to take up. If policy makers refuse or ignore policy relevant research, those who provide expertise must not be blamed. Uptake depends equally upon the responsiveness of policy makers.

Aiming at transparency, openness, and responsibility

In recent years, new forms of research have been advocated in order to make scientific practices more accessible, equitable, transparent and ultimately more beneficial for society. Based on our results, we present those features of research suitable to avoid cumulative advantages in the production of policy relevant knowledge:

- 1) **The values of Open Science:** Open Science proposes more accessible, equitable, transparent research practices. These values are broadly shared amongst those who carry out policy relevant research.
- 2) **Effective Communication:** The effects of Open Science on research uptake are limited as policymakers prefer personal communication and face-to-face interaction to engaging with academic literature.
- 3) **Access is not enough:** Open Science needs to be conceived broadly. Scientific practices are more effective if they open up to collaborative engagement with policy actors and civil society actors in all phases.
- 4) **Societal benefits:** Research can only be responsive to the grand societal challenges such as climate change if scientific practice is given a normative foundation. RRI and RI propose frameworks by which this ambitious goal can be attained.
- 5) **Reciprocity:** Participatory research benefits from the free accessibility of knowledge resources, but it can only develop its full potential if measures are taken to give back the outcomes of collaborative engagement to those participating.
- 6) **Provision of Resources:** Resources are needed to secure effective implementation, comprising those engaged in the co-creation of the knowledge and their active participation in its implementation.

Taking action

The decisive policy intervention to achieve higher levels of socially beneficial research is via the design of research programmes. As primary actors, policy makers are advised to consider the following points when defining research programmes and respective calls for tenders:

- 1) **Policy goals:** The deliberation of concrete policy goals need to be made a part of the research process. This is best achieved via upstream engagement.
- 2) **Co-creation:** Actionable knowledge needs to be co-created and include practical and situated expertise in order to secure effective implementation
- 3) **Inclusion:** The design of research programmes need to secure inclusion of civil society actors and engage peripheral and marginalised groups of society.
- 4) **Reciprocity:** There needs to be an immediate benefit for participants of co-creation activities.
- 5) **Methods:** Funding calls should explicitly require methods that enable social inclusion, upstream engagement and co-creation of effective knowledge.

Annex 2: Participant recruitment email

Invitation Email Text for Participants

Dear PARTICIPANT,

We are writing to request your participation in our Workshop on Climate Science and Policy-Making, which is an online, 3-hour event scheduled for Thursday, the 29th of October, 2020.

The proposed workshop will include 7 participants from around the world, representing a diversity of research and professional backgrounds and activities across academia and civil society. Our objective is to contribute to the understanding of the use of science in the policy-making process, and of the effects of equality and exclusion (in particular Matthew Effects) in this process.

Based on your expertise in XYZ, we believe your participation could help use to achieve these objectives, specifically by discussing the following questions:

1. How can we further enable the uptake of scientific research in the process of policy-making?
2. How can we improve equality in representation, access and impact in policy-making in terms of individuals (including academics, policy-makers, civil society actors, practitioners, and the public at large) who have access to this sphere, and in terms of whose interests are represented and whose are not?
3. Does or can Open Science, specifically, change the uptake of science in policy-making?

Please let us know if you are able to participate by DATE.

This workshop is part of the larger ON-MERRIT project (Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research & Innovation Transition). This project, funded by EU Horizon 2020, investigates the impact of Open Science practices in academia, industry, and policy with a particular focus on institutions and individuals working in the areas of agriculture, climate and health (key pillars of the UN Sustainable Development Goals). For more information, see the project website linked above. You may also read our Scoping Report to learn about the background for this workshop.

See the attached Save the Date announcement for more detailed information.

We look forward to hearing from you and very much hope you will be able to join us in this work.

Respectfully yours,

NAME

on behalf of NAMES, from the ON-MERRIT project team

Annex 3: Preliminary interview recruitment email

Dear PARTICIPANT,

Thank you for agreeing to participate in our upcoming workshop on TOPIC and policy-making. We are grateful for your willingness to give your time to our research. So that the workshop time is used in the most productive and efficient way, we would like to schedule a preparatory conversation with you to get to know you and your work a bit better, and to help you to prepare to participate.

With your consent, we would like to record this conversation for research purposes. It is our aim to protect your anonymity throughout the research process and in any forms of dissemination. We will provide a detailed informed consent form for your review and signature prior to this conversation.

The topics we would like to cover in this conversation include:

1. Your research focus and its relationship to policy;
2. Your experience participating in policy-making processes;
3. The populations represented by your research and expertise in the process of policy-making;
4. Your experience with or awareness of Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation principles and practices and their (possible) relationship to policy-making; and
5. Your feedback on our planned workshop design.

We expect that an hour will be sufficient for this conversation.

As our schedules are fairly flexible, please let us know a couple of days and times that work for you, up to two weeks prior to the scheduled event.

With many thanks and kind regards,

NAME

On behalf of NAMES from the ON-MERRIT team

Annex 4: Informed consent form

Research Project: ON-MERRIT - Observing & Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research and Innovation Transition

Institution: Institute of Interactive Systems and Data Science, TU Graz

Project Lead: Tony Ross-Hellauer (tross@know-center.at; +43 (316) 873 - 32800)

Work Package Lead: Bernhard Wieser (bernhard.wieser@tugraz.at; +43 (316) 873 - 30661)

Contributors: Nicki Lisa Cole (Facilitator) (ncole@know-center.at; +43 (316) 873 - 30622), Stefan Reichmann (Ethnography) (stefan.reichmann@tugraz.at; +43 (316) 873 - 30676)

Date of the Workshop:

Workshop Topic:

Project Website: on-merrit.eu/

Your participation in our research

We would like to thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. This workshop is part of a series of three workshops targeting various academic fields (climate science, agriculture, and health) where we ask domain experts who work in policy-related areas to share their experience. These workshops are intended to study the role of research outputs in policy-making processes.

To facilitate later analysis, the entire workshop will be recorded on our end, to be transcribed at a later stage by UniChamp GmbH. At no stage of this process will parts of the recordings or transcripts be shared with anyone beyond the project team. For data analysis, all references that could lead to identifying the person speaking will be stripped from the data: in particular, names of persons, institutions, or projects. When cited in academic publications, transcripts will be removed from their context as far as possible to ensure anonymity.

We would like to make explicit, however, that as people working in academia/policy, you can be regarded as public figures to varying degrees. This means that there is a small chance that we will be unable to fully anonymise the data, i.e. make it impossible for people working closely with you to identify who was speaking. We propose that we will:

- attend to phrases or ways of speaking that might render participants identifiable before any further analysis occurs, and
- share with you the redacted transcripts for cross-checking before we perform any further analysis.

Contact data that might render participants identifiable will be saved separate from the collected data and will under no circumstances be shared with third parties. After the project ends, these data will be deleted completely, unless you explicitly agree to be contacted for future related research projects. Participation in this research is voluntary, and you can withdraw from participating and your consent to data being collected or analysed at any moment without any consequences.

Formal Agreement

I hereby promise that I will, for the duration of the workshop, refrain from:

- recording the workshop, in full or in part, on any device

- disclosing details about the workshop or other participants to third parties

Consent

Having read and understood all of the above, I hereby consent to (tick all that apply):

- participating in one interview prior to the workshop
- participating in one workshop (specified above)
- the workshop being recorded on the end of the project organizers
- storage of the workshop recording by the researchers at least for the duration of the project
- sharing the recording with [UniChamp GmbH] for the purposes of transcription (to be deleted immediately thereafter)
- the transcripts being used - in anonymized form (as described above) - for scientific analysis
- excerpts of the transcripts being used in scientific publications, so long as all identifying information is removed in advance
- being contacted regarding follow-up questions for this project

We, the workshop organizers, on behalf of the project ON-MERRIT, hereby declare that we will adhere to the provisions specified above.

NAME

DATE

Annex 5: Interview guide for pre-workshop interviews

1. Introduce interviewer and note-taker
2. Briefly describe project and goals of WP5, workshops and today's interview
3. Any questions?
4. Tell us about your research focus, methods and their relationship to policy
5. Tell us about your experience interacting with the policy-making processes
 - a. Based on your experience, how do you understand the policy process to work?
 - b. What is your role/the role of scientific information in these processes?
 - c. Who are the key actors and institutions providing and conveying the relevant knowledge to policy-makers?
 - d. What tools, strategies or methods do you use when interacting with policy-makers?
 - e. What are the barriers to uptake of scientific policy advice in the policy-making process?
6. Tell us about the populations represented by your research and expertise in the process of policy-making
7. Tell us about your experience with or awareness of Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation principles and practices and their (possible) relationship to policy-making in the scope of your work.
8. Feedback on our workshop design

Annex 6: Example workshop email prompt

Dear participant,

In advance of our workshop on Agricultural Science and Policy-Making taking place on Thursday, January 21st from 9:00-13:00 CET, please find below some final guidance and requests from us prior to the event.

Our meeting will take place in this online meeting room: [redacted]

We ask that you please:

- Login to the meeting 10 minutes prior to the workshop start time to ensure that all tech is working properly.
- Use a headset with a microphone to ensure optimal audio quality for all involved.
- Be sure to mute yourself when you are not speaking.

Attached you will find a schedule for the workshop.

As we have discussed with most of you in our preliminary conversations, we would like you to prepare some materials to pre-circulate prior to the workshop, if your schedule allows. If it is not possible to prepare and circulate the requested materials, it will be sufficient if you are able to think about these points prior to the workshop and prepare some notes for yourself.

We would be grateful if you could prepare the following:

1. A brief professional bio (2-3 sentences) including the focus of your research and policy expertise and information about your experience working with policy-makers.
2. A one-page overview of a success case and a failed case based on your experience attempting to extend your scientific expertise into the policy-making process. For each case, provide a brief overview of the research findings/scientific guidance in question, your intended aim for influencing policy and which policy-makers you targeted (governments, organizations or institutions), the method(s) of engaging with policy-makers and other relevant policy-making process stakeholders, and the outcome of how your scientific expertise was or was not reflected in a policy change or a new policy being enacted. Please reflect in each case on equality of representation in terms of your research team, policy-making actors and other involved stakeholders, and in terms of whose interests were represented by the research and any policy that was enacted/changed.
3. Please read our attached brief primer on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Open Science and reflect on what impact, positive or negative (if any) you think either could have on the science/policy interface, the uptake of science by policy-makers, and equality of access and representation in science and policy-making.

Please return your bio and prepared cases to Nicki by Tuesday, January 12th.

Finally, we would be grateful if you could complete this very brief demographic survey to help support our analysis of the data we are collecting via this workshop. It will take just a minute or two to complete: [redacted]

With many thanks for your time and support,

Nicki Lisa Cole, PhD

Annex 7: Overview of Open Science and RRI (workshop prompt)

Overview of Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation

Prepared by Stefan Reichmann and Nicki Lisa Cole

12 October 2020

What is Open Science?

Open Science is contested. This brief summary lists the most common meanings. Taking its point of departure in a critical analysis of what stands in the way of the wide reuse of scientific knowledge, the main thrust of Open Science (OS) is to remove barriers to accessibility and the re-use of scientific outputs. It is therefore an umbrella term for a variety of values and practices that orient around making the scientific process and the knowledge it yields more reproducible, accessible, shared and collaborative. These parameters can include a range of practices, from Open Access publications, to sharing of notebooks, increased sharing of methods and the sharing of code; to Open Data and increased transparency of research evaluation and the peer-review processes.

Hypothesized benefits include the belief that OS will foster better and more efficient science, economic growth, increased transparency and democratization of knowledge production, increase the diversity of those represented by and within scientific research, and support the uptake of scientific research by policy-makers.

OS is in the process of being widely institutionalized to fully unfold its intended benefits following a growing recognition of its potential benefits by the scientific community, including policies (both at the national and institutional levels) to increase public access to publicly funded research and to encourage data sharing.

What is Responsible Research and Innovation?

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is considered by its proponents to be a novel form of addressing the science-society relationship. RRI combines a wide variety of perspectives, each with its own history and unique relationship to (some of) the other perspectives. Open Access (OA) is now conceived to be an important element of RRI and has been declared one of the six pillars of RRI, alongside gender, ethics, governance, public engagement, and science education. While a new term, none of the pillars of RRI are new. They resonate with longstanding feminist, post-colonial, queer and anti-racist critiques of science, and they are concerns that have been discussed under different names and perspectives for decades, including, among others, Technology Assessment (TA) and Anticipatory Governance. A novel aspect of RRI is its normative framing of responsibility in terms of societal impact.

OS and RRI share a vision of enhanced utilization of scientific knowledge towards societal needs and economic prosperity (see Tennant, Jacques, and Collister 2016 for the benefits of OS; see e.g. Rip 2014 for the benefits of RRI).

Recommended Reading

- Leonelli, Sabina, Daniel Spichtinger, and Barbara Prainsack. 2015. 'Sticks and Carrots: Encouraging Open Science at Its Source'. *Geo* 2 (1): 12–16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/geo2.2>.
- Mirowski, Philip. 2018. 'The Future(s) of Open Science'. *Social Studies of Science* 48 (2): 171–203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306312718772086>.
- Owen, R., P. Macnaghten, and J. Stilgoe. 2012. 'Responsible Research and Innovation: From Science in Society to Science for Society, with Society'. *Science and Public Policy* 39 (6): 751–60. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs093>.
- Owen, Richard, and Mario Pansera. 2019. 'Responsible Innovation and Responsible Research and Innovation'. In *Handbook on Science and Public Policy*, 26–48. Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Piwowar, Heather A., and Todd J. Vision. 2013. 'Data Reuse and the Open Data Citation Advantage'. *PeerJ* 1 (October): e175. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.175>.
- Rip, Arie. 2014. 'The Past and Future of RRI'. *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 10 (1): 17.
- Schomberg, René von. 2019. 'Why Responsible Innovation'. In *The International Handbook on Responsible Innovation. A Global Resource*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Suber, Peter. 2012. *Open Access*. MIT Press. Cambridge, MA.
- Tennant, Jonathan, Damien Jacques, and Lauren Collister. 2016. 'The Academic, Economic and Societal Impacts of Open Access: An Evidence-Based Review'. Edited by Lauren Collister. *F1000Research* 5. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.8460.1>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship'. *Scientific Data* 3 (March): 160018.

Annex 8: Example Workshop Schedule (for participants)

Workshop on Climate Science and Policy-Making

Thursday, 29 October, 2020

10:00-13:00 CET

Facilitated by Dr Nicki Lisa Cole, Senior Researcher, Know-Center GmbH for the ON-MERRIT project

Organized and hosted by Dr Bernhard Wieser (TU Graz), Stefan Reichmann (TU Graz), and Dr Tony Ross-Hellauer (Know-Center GmbH & TU Graz)

Questions Addressed by the Workshop

1. How can we further enable the uptake of scientific expertise in the process of policy-making?
2. How can we improve equality in representation, access and impact in policy-making in terms of individuals (including academics, policy-makers, civil society actors, practitioners, and the public at large) who have access to this sphere, and in terms of whose interests are represented and whose are not?
3. Does or can Open Science, specifically, change the uptake of science in policy-making?

Workshop Agenda and Schedule

1. Welcome and introductions (10 minutes)
2. Discussion of successful and failed cases (60 minutes)
3. Comfort break (10 minutes)
4. Discussion focused on equality of representation (30 minutes)
5. Comfort break (10 minutes)
6. Discussion of RRI & OS and their relationship to policy-making (30 minutes)
7. Opportunity to share additional contributions/ask questions (10-20 minutes)
8. Concluding remarks (5 minutes)

Annex 9: Demographic survey

Demographics

Please type in your gender.

Please tell us your nationality.

● Policy-making is often tied to a national context. Knowing how our workshop sample is distributed across nationalities will help us better understand our data.

What is your race and/or ethnicity?

Next

Education & Academic Background

This section contains questions about your academic background such as field of expertise/training and academic age. You will be able to manually type in all of your answers.

What field do you primarily work in?

What is your highest completed degree?

When did you receive your highest completed degree? Please type in the year in the format yyyy.

Annex 10: Example Workshop Facilitation Guide

1. **13:00: Welcome and introductions (20 minutes)**
 - a. Welcome and introduction of the team (2 min)
 - b. Introduction to ON-MERRIT (5 min)
 - c. Introduction to WP5 (4 min)
 - d. Today's workshop (1 min)
 - i. Driving questions
 - ii. Goals
 - e. Introduce the participants (5 min)
 - f. Agenda and schedule (1 min)
2. **13:20: Discussion of successful and failed cases (75 minutes)**
 - a. Discussion of failed cases (35 minutes)
 - i. Institutional, relational or political factors
 - ii. Social context
 - iii. Tactics/methods of engaging with policy-makers
 - iv. Research funding
 - v. Research design/methods
 - vi. Access, status, perceived legitimacy
 - b. Discussion of successful cases (30 minutes)
 - c. Reflections (10 minutes)
 - i. Summation of similarities and differences across participants' experiences that tease out how the policy process works and how science becomes a part of it (or doesn't)
 - ii. What do we learn from the experiences described in these cases?
 - d. *Elucidate how the policy process works. In what ways does/can scientific expertise play a fruitful and productive role in policy-making, thereby having an impact?*
3. **14:35: Comfort break (10 minutes)**
4. **14:45: Discussion focused on equality of representation (45 minutes)**
 - a. Who is represented in your cases?
 - i. What is good about this? What can be improved?
 - ii. Issue of Matthew Effects
 - iii. Process of knowledge making
 - b. Who is not represented by these cases?
 - i. Challenges/barriers to inclusion
 - c. How can we improve the situation?
 - d. *Possible role of ME is to enable those that are already close to power to become closer and more influential and those that are at the periphery to become even more marginalized and have a harder time getting their voice heard.*
5. **15:30: Comfort break (10 minutes)**
6. **15:40: Discussion of RRI & OS (45 minutes)**
 - a. Overview of OS & RRI
 - b. Discussion
 - i. OS influence engagement with stakeholders
 - ii. Impact on what is presented to policy-makers

- iii. Impact on engagement with policy-makers
- iv. Reflect on implications, positive and negative
 - 1. Implications in terms of RRI
- 7. **16:25: Comfort break (5 minutes)**
- 8. **16:30: Open Discussion (20 minutes)**
- 9. **16:50: Concluding remarks (10 minutes)**
 - a. Overview of key takeaways
 - b. Conflicts unearthed or questions posed by participants' contributions and discussion
 - c. Research next steps

Annex 11: Co-creation workshop agenda and facilitation guide

Agenda for Science and Policy-Making Co-Creation Workshop

20th May, 2021

13:00-15:00 CET

Hosted by Nicki Lisa Cole, Bernhard Wieser, Stefan Reichmann, Tony Ross-Hellauer and Ilaria Fava
Graz University of Technology, Know-Center GmbH, Göttingen University

1. Welcome (10 min)
 - a. Introductions
 - i. Ask participants to give a brief introduction (name, title, affiliation and location)
 - b. Overview of agenda and goals
 - i. Send IdeaBoardz link in the chat: [link redacted]
 1. *Add initials before your notes*
2. Presentation of preliminary findings (20 min)
 - a. RQs and objectives
 - b. Methods
 - c. Preliminary findings
 - d. Preliminary conclusions
3. Breakout room discussions (15 min)
 - a. Participants share one-on-one their initial responses and formulate questions, criticisms, other feedback and prepare to share with the group
 - b. Use IdeaBoardz for this
 - c. *Our team checks in on a room at the 5-minute mark to see if they need help/answers to questions*
4. Feedback discussion (45 min or longer)
 - a. Receive feedback from participants and discuss issues raised as they come in
 - b. Use online collaboration tool to organize feedback around themes (tool: https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_Ig5MjA=/)
 - i. compile feedback in the tool as discussion evolves
5. Further discussion questions (if time allows) (20 min)
6. Next steps (10 min)
 - a. Explain our next steps in data analysis and writing
 - b. Gauge interest in further co-creative activities
 - i. Compile ideas for further activities in collaborative tool

Annex 12: Index Code System

Code System	Memo
Code System	
Index Codes	This code tree was used to organize the data by structuring it around broad topics of discussion, as defined by the interview guide and focus group discussion guide.
Q1: Research-policy connections	<p>Interview: Tell us about your research focus and its relationship to policy</p> <p>Workshop: pull from discussion of successful and failed cases</p>
Q2: Policy-making process	<p>Interview: Tell us about your experience interacting with the policy-making processes</p> <p>a. Based on your experience, how do you understand the policy process to work?</p> <p>i. Attend to the relevant scales (local, state, regional, global)</p> <p>b. What is your role/the role of scientific information in these processes?</p> <p>c. Who are the key actors and institutions providing and conveying the relevant knowledge to policy-makers?</p> <p>i. Role of leading institutions and organizations and your interaction with them</p> <p>ii. Interactions between global level organizations/institutions and regional and national-level policy</p> <p>iii. How are localized manifestations addressed?</p> <p>d. What tools, strategies or methods do you use when interacting with policy-makers?</p> <p>i. Open or closed information?</p> <p>e. What are the barriers to uptake of scientific policy advice in the policy-making process?</p> <p>Workshop: Discussion of successful and failed cases</p> <p>i. Institutional, relational or political factors</p> <p>ii. Social context</p> <p>iii. Tactics/methods of engaging with policy-makers</p> <p>iv. Research funding</p> <p>v. Research design/methods</p> <p>vi. Access, status, perceived legitimacy</p>
Q3: Access and representation	<p>Interview: Tell us about the populations represented by your research and expertise in the process of policy-making (pre-workshop interview guide, Pos. 24)</p>

	<p>Workshop: Who is represented in your cases?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What is good about this? What can be improved? ii. Issue of Matthew Effects iii. Process of knowledge making <p>b. Who is not represented by these cases? (wp5.3_workshop1_guide, P. 2: 1393)</p> <p>Challenges/barriers to inclusion (wp5.3_workshop1_guide, P. 3: 3)</p>
Q4: OS/RRI	<p>Interview: Tell us about your experience with or awareness of Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation principles and practices and their (possible) relationship to policy-making in the scope of your work.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Posit the theory and ask for response: is access, awareness or uptake the issue? If not, then what? (pre-workshop interview guide, Pos. 25-26) <p>Workshop:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OS influence engagement with stakeholders ii. Impact on what is presented to policy-makers iii. Impact on engagement with policy-makers iv. Reflect on implications, positive and negative 1. Implications in terms of RRI

Annex 13: Phase 1 Code System

Code System	Memo
Horizontal Codes	This code tree is designed to include codes that we believe cut across the entire dataset and are not limited to occurring within one sector of the data, as defined by index coding.
Quote	Use this code to flag any particularly evocative quotes that you want to be able to find and/or use in a publication. If you use this code, attach a memo to the coded text that explains why you flagged this quote/what it illustrates or signals to you.
Aha!	Use this code to flag any aha! moments that come up for you while coding. If you use this code, add a memo to the coded text to explain what it made you realize so that it can be referenced in a publication if needed.
Actors	This parent code refers to any mention of actors in a sociological sense -- people, groups or organizations that are part of or related to research and policy-making processes.
Individuals	This code applies to mention of individual actors that are named in discussion research and policy-making processes.
Communities	This code applies to communities that are discussed in relation to research and policy-making processes (i.e., impacted communities or participating communities).
Lobby groups	This code applies to lobbying groups that are mentioned that impact research and policy-making processes (more likely the latter, though these also influence research funding, and therefore they influence research).
CSOs	This code applies to the mention of civil society organizations/NGOs that are mentioned in discussion of research and policy-making processes.
Businesses	This code applies to businesses/corporations that are mentioned in reference to research and policy-making processes.
Institutions	This refers to any type of formal institution that is referenced in regard to research and policy-making processes, e.g., a university, funding body, parliamentary body, governing body, etc.

Social role & self-identity	This code applies to how participants conceive of themselves/their positionality in processes of research and policy-making, as well as the role they assume or articulate has been assigned to them.
Gender	This code applies to any mention of gender as a factor in research and policy-making processes.
Race/ethnicity	This code applies to any mention of race and or ethnicity as factors in the research and policy-making processes.
Inequality	This code applies to any mention of inequality.
Access	Use this code for any discussion of the issues of access in processes of research or policy-making.
Representation	Use this code for any discussion of representation in terms of participation in research or policy-making processes.
Social Relations	A parent code under which particular types of social relations can be coded and under which the tone of the social relation can be categorized. Use this code when discussion of social relations does not fall into any of the child codes.
Tone of SR	
Collaborative	Apply this code to discussion of collaborative social relations with any person or entity.
Antagonistic	Apply this code to discussion of antagonistic social relations with any person or entity.
With whom	
With other researchers	
With other stakeholders	
With participants/impacted communities	
With policy-makers	
Engagement	Use this code for any discussion of interaction apart from dissemination (bi-directional interaction), for example with policy-makers, the public, participatory design, training, capacity building, etc.
Research design & methods	This code applies to any discussion of research design and research methods.

Constraints	Refers to organizational and institutional constraints that impact research processes and engagement with policy-making processes.
Academic	This code refers to constraints imposed by academic norms and incentive structures.
Bureaucracy	This code refers to restraints imposed by bureaucracy and administrative burdens.
Funding	This code refers to the constraints imposed on researchers and policy engagement by funding systems.
Project-based work	This code refers to constraints imposed by the nature of project-based work.
Legitimacy	This code applies to any discussion of legitimacy of any kind.
Data	This code applies to any discussion of data.
Dissemination	Use this code for any discussion of dissemination of research findings, via publications, policy briefs, press conferences, news media, social media, etc.
Policy skills	This code applies to description of the skillset that is needed to successfully engage policy-makers and impact the policy-making process.
Views of policy processes	This code applies to any discussion of policy-making processes specifically.
Views of policy-makers	This code applies to discussions of policy-makers, in terms of who they are, what they do, what they want, how they operate. In other words, participants' knowledge and imaginaries of policy-makers.
Socio-political context	This code applies to any discussion of how the socio-political context relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Sustainability targets	This code applies to any mention of sustainability targets, like SDGs, NDCs (nationally determined contributions), and the Paris Agreement, among others.

Annex 14: Phase 2 Code System

Code System	Memo
Horizontal Codes	This code tree is designed to include codes that we believe cut across the entire dataset and are not limited to occurring within one sector of the data, as defined by index coding.
Quote	Use this code to flag any particularly evocative quotes that you want to be able to find and/or use in a publication. If you use this code, attach a memo to the coded text that explains why you flagged this quote/what it illustrates or signals to you.
Aha!	Use this code to flag any aha! moments that come up for you while coding. If you use this code, add a memo to the coded text to explain what it made you realize so that it can be referenced in a publication if needed.
Actors	This parent code refers to any mention of actors in a sociological sense -- people, groups or organizations that are part of or related to research and policy-making processes.
Nation states	For reference to specific nation states as actors.
Administration	For references to the administrative bodies within nation states (e.g., departments, ministries, etc.).
Parliament	For reference to parliamentary/legislative bodies within nation states.
Government	For reference to governments within nation states.
Media	For reference to traditional media as an actor in processes of research or policy-making.
Researchers/Experts	For reference to researchers and other experts.
Policy-makers	For reference to policy-makers as people or groups of people (rather than policy-making bodies).
Individuals	This code applies to mention of individual actors that are named in discussion research and policy-making processes.
Communities	This code applies to communities that are discussed in relation to research and policy-making processes (i.e., impacted communities or participating communities).

Lobby groups	This code applies to lobbying groups that are mentioned that impact research and policy-making processes (more likely the latter, though these also influence research funding, and therefore they influence research).
CSOs	This code applies to the mention of civil society organizations/NGOs that are mentioned in discussion of research and policy-making processes.
Businesses	This code applies to businesses/corporations that are mentioned in reference to research and policy-making processes.
Institutions	For reference to formal institutions not captured by the other codes in this category.
Publishers	Refers to mentions of publishers as actors within the process of knowledge production and dissemination.
policy-making bodies	For reference to policy-making bodies.
Funding bodies	For reference to funders/funding bodies specifically or generally.
Universities	For reference to universities specifically and generally.
Social role & self-identity	This code applies to how participants conceive of themselves/their positionality in processes of research and policy-making, as well as the role they assume or articulate has been assigned to them.
Evidence-maker	For use when participants self-describe as creators and providers of evidence, absent any advocacy or advising.
Advisor	For use when participants self-describe as advisors to policy-makers/policy-making bodies.
Advocate	For use when participants self-describe as advocates for changes in policy/new policies to be implemented.
Social relations	A parent code under which particular types of social relations can be coded and under which the tone of the social relation can be categorized. Use this code when discussion of social relations does not fall into any of the child codes.
Tone of SR	
Collaborative	Apply this code to discussion of collaborative social relations with any person or entity.

Antagonistic	Apply this code to discussion of antagonistic social relations with any person or entity.
With whom	
With other stakeholders	
With policy-makers	
Socio-political context	This code applies to any discussion of how the socio-political context relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Political culture	Refers to descriptions of political cultures, e.g., representative democracies, authoritarian regimes, participatory democracies, etc.
Systemic change	Refers to descriptions of or calls for systemic change.
Social change	Refers to processes of social change in the past, present or future.
Legitimacy	This code applies to any discussion of legitimacy of any kind.
Credibility	Refers to discussion of the credibility of participants or others.
Reputation	Refers to discussions of professional reputation of participants or others.
Trust	Refers to discussions of trust in processes of research and policy-making.
Power dynamics	Refers to discussion of power or power dynamics, generally speaking.
Economic inequality	Refers specifically to discussion of economic inequality.
Colonialism	Refers to power dynamics and relations of colonialism and its legacy.
Racism	Refers to racist acts, speech, relations, practices, structures or systems.
Sexism	Refers to sexist acts, speech, relations, practices, structures or systems.
Ageism	Refers to ageist acts, speech, relations, practices, structures or systems.
Margins/periphery	Refers to discussions of being on the margins/periphery (include marginalized/marginalization).

Elite/ism	Refers to discussions of elite things and people broadly speaking, and practices and values of elitism.
Privilege	Refers to specific mention of privilege as experienced by participants or others.
Inequality	Refers to inequality generally.
Socio-demographics	Refers to socio-demographic characteristics of participants and others, as discussed generally.
Age	Refers to age of participants or others, as it relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Geography	Refers to geography of participants or others, as it relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Gender	This code applies to any mention of gender as a factor in research and policy-making processes.
Race/ethnicity	This code applies to any mention of race and or ethnicity as factors in the research and policy-making processes.
Policy arenas	This parent code refers to discussion of policy arenas, aka spaces or places where policy-making (informal and formal) takes place.
Education	Refers to education as a policy arena inasmuch as participants describe what happens in educational spaces as connected to policy-making processes.
Social movements	Refers to social movements as policy arenas inasmuch as participants discuss them as playing a role in policy-making processes.
Media & social media	Refers to the traditional news media and to social media as arenas where policy-making takes place.
Communities of practice	Definition taken from Wenger-Traynor: A group of people who 'share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly'.
Workplace	Refers to the workplace as a policy arena inasmuch as policy-making is described by participants as happening with workplaces.
Representative governments/policy bodies	Refers to formal policy-making arenas recognized by the state.
Views of policy processes	This code applies to any discussion of policy-making processes specifically.

Views of policy-makers	This code applies to discussions of policy-makers, in terms of who they are, what they do, what they want, how they operate. In other words, participants' knowledge and imaginaries of policy-makers.
Policy knowledge & skills	This code applies to description of the skillset and knowledge that is needed to successfully engage policy-makers and impact the policy-making process.
Translation	Refers to the specific skill of translating scientific evidence so that policy-makers can understand it.
Conflicting logics	Use to code instances when different institutional or organizational logics conflict, e.g., conflicting timescales for research projects and policy-making processes.
Competing interests	Use to code when competing interests of various kinds are described by participants, e.g., competing political interests, or business versus science, or researchers competing for funding and publication, etc.
Policy outcomes	This parent code refers to discussion of outcomes of participating in policy-making processes.
Failures	Use when participants discuss failed attempts at influencing policy based on their research/expertise.
Successes	Use when participants discuss having their research or expertise successfully taken up by policy-makers and/or seeing it reflected in policy changes or new policies.
Policy goals	Refers to specific goals that participants may have in terms of influencing policy.
Framework conditions	(Renamed from constraints): Refers to framework conditions that surround and shape/impact research processes and engagement with policy-making processes.
Policy fads	Refers to trends or fads in policy-making that influence how participants conduct research and/or interact with policy-makers (e.g., 'mainstreaming' or 'adaptation' or 'RRI').
Wealth/resources	Refers to the wealth and resources of participants and others, as relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Civic funding	Refers to public budgets and their impact on research and or policy-making.

Politics	Refers to impact of politics on research and policy-making.
Academic	Refers to how academic norms and incentive structures impact research and interaction with policy-makers.
Bureaucracy	This code refers to constraints imposed by bureaucracy and administrative burdens.
Research funding	Refers to how funders and funding impact research and policy engagement.
Project-based work	This code refers to the way project-based work impacts research and engagement with policy-making.
Views of science/knowledge production	Use when participants articulate explicit or implicit views about the production of science and/or knowledge.
Access	Use this code for any discussion of the issues of access in processes of research or policy-making.
Representation	Use this code for any discussion of representation in terms of participation in research or policy-making processes.
Engagement	This parent code refers to discussion of interaction apart from dissemination (bi-directional interaction), for example with policy-makers, the public, participatory design, training, capacity building, etc.
As an educational process	Refers to engagement conducted for educational purposes, e.g., in schools or with students or youth, or with the general public through events.
As a research process	Refers to engagement when it occurs through the research process, e.g., involvement of participants and/or communities relevant to the research, or with policy-makers or other stakeholders when this is built into the research.
As a policy process	Refers to engagement with policy-makers as an effort to have science/expertise taken up in the policy-making process (separate from the research process).
Materialities of engagement	Refers to the material aspects of carrying out engagement, with specific artifacts, platforms or tools.
Upstream engagement	Definition taken from Sage Encyclopedia of Science and Technology Communication: "Upstream engagement is a catchphrase referring to recent developments that attempt to bring members of the (multiple) publics and stakeholders together in dialogue about emerging

	technologies, before research and development (R&D) trajectories are established."
Research design & methods	This parent code applies to any discussion of research design and research methods.
Question setting	Use when participants discuss the values, processes and practices that inform how they formulate research questions.
Design	Refers to discussions of research design and the values that inform it.
Goals	Refers to the articulation of goals that participants have for their research.
Participants	Refers to discussion of those who participate in participants' research.
Data collection	Refers to processes of data collection as described by participants, as well as the values that surround it.
Data analysis	Refers to the data analysis part of the research process.
Ethical issues	Refers to ethical issues within the research process as stated by participants.
Cultural awareness	Refers to cultural awareness as it is discussed by participants as something that factors into the research process.
Critical self-reflection	Refers to when participants engage in critical self-reflection as they discuss themselves as part of the research process.
Benefits/payoffs to participants	Refers to the ways in which research participants may benefit from being part of the research process or its outcomes; including financial compensation for participating.
Challenges to participation	Refers to challenges our participants face in including certain participants in their research processes.
Exploitation of participants	Refers to ways in which participants may be exploited within research processes.
Data	This code applies to any discussion of data.
Dissemination	Use this code for any discussion of dissemination of research findings, via publications, policy briefs, press conferences, news media, social media, etc.

Sustainability targets	This code applies to any mention of sustainability targets, like SDGs, NDCs (nationally determined contributions), and the Paris Agreement, among others.
Domain-specific issues	This parent code refers to instances when participants make it clear that there is something particular about the research/policy domain that influences what is going on.
Climate	Refers to when participants discuss particularities of research and policy-making that are specific to the climate domain. Auto coding was done to capture the word 'climate' in any sentence on 19.05.2021.
Agriculture	Refers to when participants discuss particularities of research and policy-making that are specific to the agriculture domain. Auto coding was done to capture the words 'agriculture' and 'food' in any sentence on 19.05.2021.
Health	Refers to when participants discuss particularities of research and policy-making that are specific to the health domain. Auto coded for 'health' occurring in any sentence on 19.05.2021.
TRH Vertical Codes	This parent code houses vertical codes created by Tony.
SR Vertical Codes	This parent code houses vertical codes created by Stefan.
NC Vertical Codes	This parent code houses vertical codes created by Nicki.
BW Vertical Codes	This parent code includes vertical codes created by Bernhard.
Knowledge (type, work, translation, disagreement.)	
Power issues (authority, threats, disempowerment...)	
Resources	
Policy arena	
Science Policy interface	
Time issues	
Uptake of knowledge (explicitly)	

Annex 15: Phase 3 Code System

Code System	Memo
Horizontal Codes	This code tree is designed to include codes that we believe cut across the entire dataset and are not limited to occurring within one sector of the data, as defined by index coding.
Quote	Use this code to flag any particularly evocative quotes that you want to be able to find and/or use in a publication. If you use this code, attach a memo to the coded text that explains why you flagged this quote/what it illustrates or signals to you.
Aha!	Use this code to flag any aha! moments that come up for you while coding. If you use this code, add a memo to the coded text to explain what it made you realize so that it can be referenced in a publication if needed.
Actors	This parent code refers to any mention of actors in a sociological sense -- people, groups or organizations that are part of or related to research and policy-making processes.
Nation states	For reference to specific nation states as actors.
Administration	For references to the administrative bodies within nation states (e.g. departments, ministries, etc.).
Parliament	For reference to parliamentary/legislative bodies within nation states.
Government	For reference to governments within nation states.
Media	For reference to traditional media as an actor in processes of research or policy-making.
Researchers/Experts	For reference to researchers and other experts.
Policy-makers	For reference to policy-makers as people or groups of people (rather than policy-making bodies).
Individuals	This code applies to mention of individual actors that are named in discussion research and policy-making processes.
Communities	This code applies to communities that are discussed in relation to research and policy-making processes (i.e., impacted communities or participating communities).

Lobby groups	This code applies to lobbying groups that are mentioned that impact research and policy-making processes (more likely the latter, though these also influence research funding, and therefore they influence research).
CSOs	This code applies to the mention of civil society organizations/NGOs that are mentioned in discussion of research and policy-making processes.
Businesses	This code applies to businesses/corporations that are mentioned in reference to research and policy-making processes.
Institutions	For reference to formal institutions not captured by the other codes in this category.
Publishers	Refers to mentions of publishers as actors within the process of knowledge production and dissemination.
policy-making bodies	For reference to policy-making bodies.
Funding bodies	For reference to funders/funding bodies specifically or generally.
Universities	For reference to universities specifically and generally.
Social role & self-identity	This code applies to how participants conceive of themselves/their positionality in processes of research and policy-making, as well as the role they assume or articulate has been assigned to them.
Evidence-maker	For use when participants self-describe as creators and providers of evidence, absent any advocacy or advising.
Advisor	For use when participants self-describe as advisors to policy-makers/policy-making bodies.
Advocate	For use when participants self-describe as advocates for changes in policy/new policies to be implemented.
Social relations	A parent code under which particular types of social relations can be coded and under which the tone of the social relation can be categorized. Use this code when discussion of social relations does not fall into any of the child codes.
Tone of SR	
Collaborative	Apply this code to discussion of collaborative social relations with any person or entity.

Antagonistic	Apply this code to discussion of antagonistic social relations with any person or entity.
With whom	
With other stakeholders	
With policy-makers	
Socio-political context	This code applies to any discussion of how the socio-political context relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Political culture	Refers to descriptions of political cultures, e.g. representative democracies, authoritarian regimes, participatory democracies, etc.
Systemic change	Refers to descriptions of or calls for systemic change.
Social change	Refers to processes of social change in the past, present or future.
Legitimacy	This code applies to any discussion of legitimacy of any kind.
Credibility	Refers to discussion of the credibility of participants or others.
Reputation	Refers to discussions of professional reputation of participants or others.
Trust	Refers to discussions of trust in processes of research and policy-making.
Power dynamics	Refers to discussion of power or power dynamics, generally speaking.
Economic inequality	Refers specifically to discussion of economic inequality.
Colonialism	Refers to power dynamics and relations of colonialism and its legacy.
Racism	Refers to racist acts, speech, relations, practices, structures or systems.
Sexism	Refers to sexist acts, speech, relations, practices, structures or systems.
Ageism	Refers to ageist acts, speech, relations, practices, structures or systems.
Margins/periphery	Refers to discussions of being on the margins/periphery (include marginalized/marginalization).

Elite/ism	Refers to discussions of elite things and people broadly speaking, and practices and values of elitism.
Privilege	Refers to specific mention of privilege as experienced by participants or others.
Inequality	Refers to inequality generally.
Socio-demographics	Refers to socio-demographic characteristics of participants and others, as discussed generally.
Age	Refers to age of participants or others, as it relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Geography	Refers to geography of participants or others, as it relates to processes of research and policy-making.
Gender	This code applies to any mention of gender as a factor in research and policy-making processes.
Race/ethnicity	This code applies to any mention of race and or ethnicity as factors in the research and policy-making processes.
Policy arenas	This parent code refers to discussion of policy arenas, aka spaces or places where policy-making (informal and formal) takes place.
Education	Refers to education as a policy arena inasmuch as participants describe what happens in educational spaces as connected to policy-making processes.
Social movements	Refers to social movements as policy arenas inasmuch as participants discuss them as playing a role in policy-making processes.
Media & social media	Refers to the traditional news media and to social media as arenas where policy-making takes place.
Communities of practice	Definition taken from Wenger-Traynor: A group of people who 'share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly'.
Workplace	Refers to the workplace as a policy arena inasmuch as policy-making is described by participants as happening with workplaces.
Representative governments/policy bodies	Refers to formal policy-making arenas recognized by the state.
Local, municipal, provincial	
UNO, EU, WHO	

Views of policy processes	This code applies to any discussion of policy-making processes specifically.
Views of policy-makers	This code applies to discussions of policy-makers, in terms of who they are, what they do, what they want, how they operate. In other words, participants' knowledge and imaginaries of policy-makers.
Policy knowledge & skills	This code applies to description of the skillset and knowledge that is needed to successfully engage policy-makers and impact the policy-making process.
Translation	Refers to the specific skill of translating scientific evidence so that policy-makers can understand it.
Conflicting logics	Use to code instances when different institutional or organizational logics conflict, e.g., conflicting timescales for research projects and policy-making processes.
Competing interests	Use to code when competing interests of various kinds are described by participants, e.g., competing political interests, or business versus science, or researchers competing for funding and publication, etc.
Policy outcomes	This parent code refers to discussion of outcomes of participating in policy-making processes.
Failures	Use when participants discuss failed attempts at influencing policy based on their research/expertise.
Successes	Use when participants discuss having their research or expertise successfully taken up by policy-makers and/or seeing it reflected in policy changes or new policies.
Policy goals	Refers to specific goals that participants may have in terms of influencing policy.
Framework conditions	(Renamed from constraints): Refers to framework conditions that surround and shape/impact research processes and engagement with policy-making processes.
Policy fads	Refers to trends or fads in policy-making that influence how participants conduct research and/or interact with policy-makers (e.g., 'mainstreaming' or 'adaptation' or 'RRI').
Wealth/resources	Refers to the wealth and resources of participants and others, as relates to processes of research and policy-making.

Civic funding	Refers to public budgets and their impact on research and or policy-making.
Politics	Refers to impact of politics on research and policy-making.
Academic	Refers to how academic norms and incentive structures impact research and interaction with policy-makers.
Bureaucracy	This code refers to constraints imposed by bureaucracy and administrative burdens.
Research funding	Refers to how funders and funding impact research and policy engagement.
Project-based work	This code refers to the way project-based work impacts research and engagement with policy-making.
Views of science/knowledge production	Use when participants articulate explicit or implicit views about the production of science and/or knowledge.
Access	Use this code for any discussion of the issues of access in processes of research or policy-making.
To research	
To policy-making	
Representation	Use this code for any discussion of representation in terms of participation in research or policy-making processes.
In research	
In policy-making	
Engagement	This parent code refers to discussion of interaction apart from dissemination (bi-directional interaction), for example with policy-makers, the public, participatory design, training, capacity building, etc.
As an educational process	Refers to engagement conducted for educational purposes, e.g. in schools or with students or youth, or with the general public through events.
As a research process	Refers to engagement when it occurs through the research process, e.g. involvement of participants and/or communities relevant to the research, or with policy-makers or other stakeholders when this is built into the research.

As a policy process	Refers to engagement with policy-makers as an effort to have science/expertise taken up in the policy-making process (separate from the research process).
Materialities of engagement	Refers to the material aspects of carrying out engagement, with specific artifacts, platforms or tools.
Upstream engagement	Definition taken from Sage Encyclopedia of Science and Technology Communication: "Upstream engagement is a catchphrase referring to recent developments that attempt to bring members of the (multiple) publics and stakeholders together in dialogue about emerging technologies, before research and development (R&D) trajectories are established."
Research design & methods	This parent code applies to any discussion of research design and research methods.
Question setting	Use when participants discuss the values, processes and practices that inform how they formulate research questions.
Design	Refers to discussions of research design and the values that inform it.
Goals	Refers to the articulation of goals that participants have for their research.
Participants	Refers to discussion of those who participate in participants' research.
Data collection	Refers to processes of data collection as described by participants, as well as the values that surround it.
Data analysis	Refers to the data analysis part of the research process.
Ethical issues	Refers to ethical issues within the research process as stated by participants.
Cultural awareness	Refers to cultural awareness as it is discussed by participants as something that factors into the research process.
Critical self-reflection	Refers to when participants engage in critical self-reflection as they discuss themselves as part of the research process.
Benefits/payoffs to participants	Refers to the ways in which research participants may benefit from being part of the research process or its outcomes; including financial compensation for participating.

Challenges to participation	Refers to challenges our participants face in including certain participants in their research processes.
Exploitation of participants	Refers to ways in which participants may be exploited within research processes.
Data	This code applies to any discussion of data.
Dissemination	Use this code for any discussion of dissemination of research findings, via publications, policy briefs, press conferences, news media, social media, etc.
Sustainability targets	This code applies to any mention of sustainability targets, like SDGs, NDCs (nationally determined contributions), and the Paris Agreement, among others.
Domain-specific issues	This parent code refers to instances when participants make it clear that there is something particular about the research/policy domain that influences what is going on.
Climate	Refers to when participants discuss particularities of research and policy-making that are specific to the climate domain. Auto coding was done to capture the word 'climate' in any sentence on 19.05.2021.
Agriculture	Refers to when participants discuss particularities of research and policy-making that are specific to the agriculture domain. Auto coding was done to capture the words 'agriculture' and 'food' in any sentence on 19.05.2021.
Health	Refers to when participants discuss particularities of research and policy-making that are specific to the health domain. Auto coded for 'health' occurring in any sentence on 19.05.2021.
COVID-19	6/1/2021 2:59 PM Lexical Search - ANY: covid corona pandemic covid-19 Within: Document Only in activated documents
Impact	6/3/2021 1:35 PM Lexical Search - ANY: impact Within: Document Find whole words Only in activated documents

TRH Vertical Codes	This parent code houses vertical codes created by Tony.
Access is not enough	
Citizen Science	
Constraints on OS	
Definitions/characteristics of OS	
In contrast with RRI	
Evaluation of research	
Incentives/reward systems	
Open Access to publications	
Open/FAIR Data	
Opportunism	
OS support services	
OS-industry relation	
Transparency	
Views of/opinions on the value of OS	
In contrast with RRI	
Views of/opinions on the value of RRI	
SR Vertical Codes	This parent code houses vertical codes created by Stefan.
Regional Level	
Continuity of Relationships	
Participation Fatigue	
NC Vertical Codes	This parent code houses vertical codes created by Nicki.
BW Vertical Codes	This parent code includes vertical codes created by Bernhard.
Knowledge (type, work, translation, disagreement...)	
Resources	
Science Policy interface	

RRI (responsiveness, giving back to ...)	
Time issues	
Uptake of knowledge or policy (explicitly)	